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Special Delivery: Programming with Mailbox Types

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SIMON FOWLER

University of Glasgow, UK
(email: Simon.Fowler@glasgow.ac.uk)

DUNCAN PAUL ATTARD

University of Malta, Malta
(email: Duncan.Attard@um.edu.mt)

DANIELLE MARSHALL

University of Glasgow, UK
(email: Danielle.Marshall@glasgow.ac.uk)

SIMON J. GAY

University of Glasgow, UK
(email: Simon.Gay@glasgow.ac.uk)

PHIL TRINDER

University of Glasgow, UK
(email: Phil.Trinder@glasgow.ac.uk)

Abstract

26 The asynchronous and unidirectional communication model supported by *mailboxes* is a key reason for
27 the success of actor languages like Erlang and Elixir for implementing reliable and scalable distributed
28 systems. Although actors eliminate many of the issues stemming from shared memory concurrency,
29 they remain vulnerable to communication errors such as protocol violations and deadlocks. Behavioural
30 types make it possible to detect communication errors early in the development process, but most work
31 has addressed channel-based languages rather than actor languages.

32 *Mailbox types* are a novel behavioural type system for actors first introduced for a process calculus
33 by de'Liguoro and Padovani in 2018, which capture the contents of a mailbox as a commutative
34 regular expression. Due to aliasing and nested evaluation contexts, moving from a process calculus to a
35 programming language is challenging. This paper presents Pat, the first programming language design
36 incorporating mailbox types, and describes an algorithmic type system. Pat is a higher-order functional
37 language with sums, products, and lists, along with interfaces that allow finer-grained reasoning about
38 mailbox contents. Typechecking in Pat detects four classes of behavioural error: protocol violation,
39 unexpected message, forgotten reply and self-deadlock, as well as the usual data type errors.

40 The Pat type system makes essential use of quasi-linear typing to tame some of the complexity
41 introduced by aliasing. We make use of a *co-contextual* algorithmic type system, achieved through
42 a novel use of backwards bidirectional typing, and we prove it sound and complete with respect to
43 our declarative type system. We implement a mailbox type checker, and use it to demonstrate the
44 expressiveness of Pat on a factory automation case study and a series of examples from the Savina actor
45 benchmark suite. This establishes a foundation for applying mailbox typing to practical actor languages
46 such as Erlang, Elixir and Scala/Akka.

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1 Introduction

Software is increasingly concurrent and distributed, but coordinating concurrent computations introduces a host of additional correctness issues like communication mismatches and deadlocks. Communication-centric languages such as Go, Erlang, and Elixir make it possible to avoid many of the issues stemming from shared memory concurrency by structuring applications as lightweight processes that communicate through explicit message passing. There are two main classes of communication-centric language. In *channel-based* languages like Go, processes communicate over channels, where a `send` in one process is paired with a `receive` in the recipient process. In *actor* languages like Erlang or Elixir, a message is sent to the *mailbox* of the recipient process, which is an incoming message queue; in certain actor languages, the recipient can choose which message from the mailbox to handle next.

Although communication-centric languages eliminate many coordination issues, some remain. For example, a process may still receive a message that it is not equipped to handle, or wait for a message that it will never receive. Such communication errors often occur sporadically and unpredictably after deployment, making them difficult to locate and fix.

Behavioural type systems (Hüttel et al. 2016) encode correct communication behaviour to support *correct-by-construction* concurrency. Behavioural type systems, in particular *session types* (Honda 1993; Honda et al. 1998; Takeuchi et al. 1994), have been extensively applied to specify communication protocols in channel-based languages (Ancona et al. 2016). There has, however, been far less application of behavioural typing to actor languages. Existing work either imposes restrictions on the actor model to retrofit session types (Fowler and Hu 2026; Harvey et al. 2021; Mostrous and Vasconcelos 2011; Tabone and Francalanza 2021, 2022) or relies on dynamic typing (Neykova and Yoshida 2017b). In general, session types are built around the idea of ordered communication channels. Channels are a significantly different communication model to the many-to-one unordered communication model supported by mailboxes, and therefore using session types in an actor language typically requires users to rewrite their applications. We discuss these systems further in §7.

Our approach is based on *mailbox types*, a behavioural type system for mailboxes first introduced in the context of a process calculus (de'Liguoro and Padovani 2018). We present the first programming language design incorporating mailbox types and we detail an algorithmic type system, an implementation, and a range of benchmarks and a factory case study. Due to aliasing and nested evaluation contexts, the move from a process calculus to a programming language is challenging. We make essential and novel use of quasi-linear typing (Ennals et al. 2004; Kobayashi 1999) to tame some of the complexity introduced by aliasing, and our algorithmic type system is co-contextual (Erdweg et al. 2015; Kuci et al. 2017), achieved through a novel use of backwards bidirectional typing (Zeilberger 2015).

1.1 Channel vs. Actor Communication

Channel-based languages comprise anonymous processes that communicate over named channels, whereas actor-based languages comprise named processes each equipped with a mailbox. Figure 1 contrasts the approaches, and is taken from a detailed comparison (Fowler et al. 2017).

Actor languages have proven to be effective for implementing reliable and scalable distributed systems (Trinder et al. 2017). Communication in actor languages is asynchronous and unidirectional: many actors may *send* messages to an actor *A*, whereas only *A* may *receive*

Fig. 1. Channel- and actor-based languages (Fowler et al. 2017)

from its mailbox. Mailboxes provide *data locality* as each message is stored with the process that will handle it. In channel-based languages, since it is possible to send channel names over other channels, such languages must either sacrifice locality and reduce performance, or rely on complex distributed algorithms (Chaudhuri 2009; Hu et al. 2008).

Although it is straightforward to add a type system to channel-based languages, adding a type system to actor languages is less straightforward, as process names (process IDs or PIDs) must be parameterised by a type that supports all messages that can be received. The type is therefore less precise, requiring subtyping (He et al. 2014) or synchronisation (de Boer et al. 2007; Tasharofi et al. 2013) to avoid a total loss of modularity (Fowler et al. 2017).

The situation becomes even more pronounced when considering behavioural type systems: communication errors might be prevented in channel-based languages by giving one end of a channel the session type $!Int.!Int.?Bool.End$ (send two integers, and receive a Boolean), and the other end the *dual* type $?Int.?Int.!Bool.End$. Behavioural type systems for actor languages are much less straightforward due to the asymmetric communication model required by mailboxes. In practice, designers of session type systems for actor languages either emulate session-typed channels (Mostrous and Vasconcelos 2011), or use *multiparty session types* to govern the communication actions performed by a process, requiring a fixed communication topology (Fowler and Hu 2026; Neykova and Yoshida 2017b).

1.2 Mailbox Types

de'Liguoro and Padovani (2018) observe that session types require a *strict ordering* of messages, whereas most actor systems use *selective receive* to process messages out-of-order. Concentrating on *unordered* interactions enables behavioural typing for mailboxes with many senders.

Mailbox typing by example: a future variable. Rather than reasoning about the *behaviour of a process*, mailbox types reason about the *contents of a mailbox*. Consider a *future variable*, which is a placeholder in a concurrent computation. A future can receive many *get* messages that are only fulfilled *after* a *put* message initialises the future with a value. After the future is initialised, it fulfils all *get* messages by sending its value; a second *put* message is explicitly disallowed. We can implement a future straightforwardly in Erlang:

```

154 1 -module future.
155 2 empty_future() ->
156 3   receive
157 4     { put, X } -> full_future(X)
158 5   end.
159 6 full_future(X) ->
160 7   receive
161 8     { get, Pid } ->
162 9     Pid ! { reply, X },
163 10    full_future(X);
164 11    { put, _ } ->
165 12    erlang:error("Multiple writes")
166 13 end.
167
168 13 client() ->
169 14 Future = spawn(future, empty_future, []),
170 15 Future ! { put, 5 },
171 16 Future ! { get, self() },
172 17 receive
173 18   { reply, Result } ->
174 19   io:fwrite("~w~n", [Result])
175 20 end.

```

The `empty_future` function awaits a `put` message to set the value of the future (lines 3–5), and transitions to the `full_future` state. A `full_future` receives `get` messages (lines 7–13) containing a process ID used to reply with the future’s value. The `client` function spawns a future (line 14), sends a `put` message followed by a `get` message (lines 15–16), and awaits the result (lines 17–20). The program prints the number 5.

Several communication errors can arise in this example:

- **Protocol violation.** Sending two `put` messages to the future will result in a *runtime* error.
- **Unexpected message.** Sending a message other than `get` or `put` to the future will silently succeed, but the message will never be retrieved, resulting in a memory leak.
- **Forgotten reply.** If the future fails to send a `reply` message after receiving a `get` message the client will be left waiting forever.
- **Self-deadlock.** If the client attempts to receive a `reply` message before sending a `get` message it will be left waiting forever.

All of the above issues can be solved by mailbox typing. We can write the following types:

```

184
185 EmptyFuture  ≐  ?(Put(Int) ◦ Get(ClientSend))*
186 FullFuture   ≐  ?Get(ClientSend)*
187 ClientSend   ≐  !Reply(Int)
188 ClientRecv   ≐  ?Reply(Int)

```

A mailbox type combines a *capability* (either `!` for an output capability, analogous to a PID in Erlang; or `?` for an input capability) with a *pattern*. A pattern is a *commutative regular expression*: in the context of a send mailbox type, the pattern will describe the messages that must be sent; in the context of a receive mailbox type, it describes the messages that the mailbox may contain.

A mailbox name (e.g., `Future`) may have different types at different points in the program. `EmptyFuture` types an input capability of an empty future mailbox, and denotes that the mailbox may contain a single `Put` message with an `Int` payload, and potentially many (`*`) `Get` messages each with a `ClientSend` payload. `FullFuture` types an input capability of the future after a `Put` message has been received, and requires that the mailbox *only* contains `Get` messages. `ClientSend` is an output mailbox type which requires that a `Reply` message must be sent; `ClientRecv` is an input capability for receiving the `Reply`. For each mailbox name, sends and receives must “balance out”: if a message is sent, it must eventually be received.

de'Liguoro and Padovani (2018) introduce a small extension of the asynchronous π -calculus (Amadio et al. 1998), which they call the *mailbox calculus*, and endow it with mailbox types. They express the Future example in the mailbox calculus as follows, where the mailbox is denoted *self*.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{emptyFuture}(self) &\triangleq self?\mathbf{Put}(x) . \text{fullFuture}(self, x) \\
 \text{fullFuture}(self, x) &\triangleq \mathbf{free} \text{ self} . \mathbf{done} \\
 &+ self?\mathbf{Get}(sender) . (sender ! \mathbf{Reply}(x) \parallel \text{fullFuture}(self, x)) \\
 &+ self?\mathbf{Put}(x) . \mathbf{fail} \text{ self} \\
 (\nu \text{future})(\text{emptyFuture}(\text{future}) \parallel \text{future} ! \mathbf{Put}(5) \parallel \\
 (\nu \text{self})(\text{future} ! \mathbf{Get}(self) \parallel (self ? \mathbf{Reply}(x) . \mathbf{free} \text{ self} . \text{print}(\text{intToString}(x))))
 \end{aligned}$$

A process calculus is useful for expressing the essence of concurrent computation, but there is a large gap between a process calculus and a programming language design, the biggest being the separation of static and dynamic terms. A programming language specifies the *program* that a user writes, whereas a process calculus provides a snapshot of the system at a given time. A particular difference comes with name generation: in a process calculus, we can write name restrictions directly; in a programming language, we instead have a language construct (like **new**) that is evaluated to create a fresh name at runtime. Further complexities come with nested evaluation contexts, sequential evaluation, and aliasing. We explore these challenges in greater detail in §2.

We propose Pat¹, a functional programming language that supports mailbox types, in which we express the *future* example as follows (*self* is again the mailbox).

```

230 def emptyFuture(self : EmptyFuture): 1 {
231   guard self: Put ⊙ Get* {
232     receive Put(x) from self ↦
233       fullFuture(self, x)
234   }
235 }
236
237 def fullFuture(self : FullFuture, value : Int): 1 {
238   guard self: Get* {
239     free ↦ ()
240     receive Get(user) from self ↦
241       user ! Reply(value);
242       fullFuture(self, value)
243   }
244 }
245
246 def client(): 1 {
247   let future = new in
248   spawn emptyFuture(future);
249   let self = new in
250   future ! Put(5);
251   future ! Get(self);
252   guard self: Reply {
253     receive Reply(result) from self ↦
254       free self;
255       print(intToString(result))
256   }
257 }

```

The Pat program has a similar structure to the Erlang example with `client`, `emptyFuture` and `fullFuture` functions, and the mailbox types are similar to those in the mailbox calculus specification. There are, however, some differences compared with the Erlang future. The first is that in Pat mailboxes are first-class: we create a new mailbox with **new**, and receive from it using the **guard** expression. A **guard** acts on a mailbox and may contain several guards: **free** $\mapsto M$ frees the mailbox if there are no other references to it and evaluates M ; and **receive** $m(\vec{x})$ from $y \mapsto M$ retrieves a message with tag m from the mailbox, binding its

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Postman_Pat

256 payloads to \vec{x} and re-binding the mailbox variable (with an updated type) to y in continuation
 257 M . There is also **fail** denoting that a mailbox is in an invalid state, but the type system ensures
 258 that this guard is never evaluated. In the above code, **free self** is syntactic sugar (see §3).

259 Pat has all of the characteristics of a programming language, unlike the mailbox calculus.
 260 Static and dynamic terms are distinguished, *i.e.*, we *do not* need to write name restrictions
 261 with dynamic names known *a priori*. Pat provides **let**-bindings, which enable full sequential
 262 composition along with nested evaluation contexts; and we have data types and return types.
 263 Crucially *all of the concurrency errors described earlier result in a type error*: protocol
 264 violations, unexpected messages, and forgotten replies. Although the richer structure of
 265 Pat means that we cannot rule out *inter-process* deadlocks, all *self-deadlocks* are detected
 266 statically.
 267

268
 269 *Contributions.* Despite being a convincing proposal for behavioural typing for actor languages,
 270 mailbox typing has received little attention since its introduction in 2018. The overarching
 271 contribution of this paper, therefore, is the first design and implementation of a concurrent
 272 programming language with support for mailbox types. Concretely, we make four main
 273 contributions:
 274

- 275 (1) We introduce a declarative type system for Pat (§3), a functional programming
 276 language supporting mailbox types, making essential and novel use of quasi-linear
 277 types. We show type preservation, mailbox conformance, and a progress result.
- 278 (2) We introduce a co-contextual algorithmic type system for Pat (§4), making use of
 279 backwards bidirectional typing. We prove that the algorithmic type system is sound
 280 and complete with respect to the declarative type system.
- 281 (3) We extend Pat with sum, product, and list types; higher-order functions; and mailbox
 282 interfaces (§5).
- 283 (4) We detail our implementation (§6), and demonstrate the expressiveness of Pat by
 284 encoding all of the examples from [de’Liguoro and Padovani \(2018\)](#), and all 11 of the
 285 Savina benchmarks ([Imam and Sarkar 2014](#)) used by [Neykova and Yoshida \(2017b\)](#)
 286 in their evaluation of multiparty session types for actor languages (§6.2). We also
 287 detail a larger factory case study.
 288
 289

290 This paper is a significantly extended and revised version of a paper of the same name that
 291 was published at ICFP’23 ([Fowler et al. 2023b](#)). We include all definitions omitted from the
 292 original conference paper, and give more proof details for the main results. Other highlights
 293 include:
 294

- 295 • Full technical details of the sum and product type extensions (§5).
- 296 • A new extension to allow Pat to express and type lists (§5.1.3), and a revised
 297 evaluation showing how to use lists for the relevant Savina examples (§6.2).
- 298 • Full declarative typing rules for extensions of Pat with first-class functions (§5.3) and
 299 mailbox interfaces (§5.4), and full details of how to use contextual type information
 300 to typecheck these features (§5.5).
- 301 • A more complete description of the implementation of the Pat typechecker (§6.1).
- 302 • A new extended example showing how Pat can express the classic *Sleeping Barber*
 303 concurrency problem, along with a more complete discussion of the implementation
 304 of the factory case study (§6.2).
 305
 306

The Pat typechecker is available as an artifact (Fowler et al. 2023a) and on GitHub (<https://www.github.com/SimonJF/mbcheck>). A yet more comprehensive version (Fowler et al. 2025) contains full proofs.

2 Mailbox Types in a Programming Language: What are the Issues?

Session typing was originally studied in the context of process calculi (e.g., (Honda et al. 1998; Vasconcelos 2012)), but later work (Fowler et al. 2023c; Gay and Vasconcelos 2010; Wadler 2014) introduced session types for languages based on the linear λ -calculus. In contrast, the more relaxed view of linearity in the mailbox calculus makes language integration far more challenging: a mailbox name may be used several times to *send* messages, but only once to *receive* a message. The intuition is that while sends simply add messages to a mailbox, it is a receive that determines the future behaviour of the actor. To illustrate, consider the following code that shows part of the future example from (§1):

```

1.  def client(): 1 {
2.    let future = new in
3.    spawn emptyFuture(future);
4.    let self = new in
5.    future ! Put(5);
6.    future ! Get(self);
7.    guard self: Reply {
8.      receive Reply(result) from self ↦
9.        free self;
10.       print(intToString(result))
11.    }
12.  }

```

The client definition uses the *future* mailbox twice to send a message (lines 5 and 6), and similarly uses the *self* mailbox twice: once as a message payload (line 6), and once to receive a message (line 7). In the mailbox calculus, a name remains constant and cannot be aliased; this is at odds with idiomatic programming where expressions are aliased with **let** bindings or function application. Moreover functional languages provide nested evaluation contexts and sequential evaluation.

2.1 Challenge: Mailbox Name Aliasing

Ensuring appropriate mailbox use is challenging in the presence of aliasing. For example, in the `fullFuture` function described earlier, there is a strong expectation on how resources are used: the *self* mailbox name is consumed by the **guard** expression and only re-bound as *self* in the **receive** clause; notably the *self* variable is *not* available in the **free** clause as we would otherwise be able to send to a mailbox after it was deallocated.

We could try to write a function that attempts to use a mailbox after it has been freed:

```

358
359     def unsafeUse1(x : ?Msg()*): 1 {
360         guard x : Msg* {
361             receive Msg() from z ↦
362                 x ! Msg();
363                 unsafeUse1(z)
364             free ↦ x ! Msg()
365         }
366     }

```

367 Unlike in our situation, such errors are not an issue with a fully linear type system, since
368 we *cannot* use a resource after it has been consumed. We could require that a name cannot
369 be used after it has been guarded upon by insisting that the subject and body of a **guard**
370 expression are typable under disjoint type environments. Indeed, such an approach correctly
371 rules out the error in the previous example. Alas, the check can easily be circumvented:
372

```

373     def unsafeUse2(x : ?Msg()*): 1 {
374         let a = x in
375         guard a : Msg* {
376             receive Msg() from z ↦
377                 x ! Msg();
378                 unsafeUse2(z)
379             free ↦ x ! Msg()
380         }
381     }

```

382 In this example we introduce an alias a for the output capability x , and the new name
383 prevents the typechecker from realising that it has been used in the body of the guard. Worse,
384 we must also handle nested evaluation contexts, meaning that the next use of a mailbox
385 variable is not necessarily contained within a subexpression of the guard:
386

```

387     def unsafeUse3(x : ?Msg()*): 1 {
388         let _ =
389         guard x : Msg* {
390             receive Msg() from z ↦
391                 x ! Msg();
392                 unsafeUse3(z)
393             free ↦ x ! Msg()
394         } in x ! Msg()
395     }

```

396 Much of the intricacy arises from using a mailbox name many times as an output capability.
397 In each process, we can avoid the problems above using three principles:
398

- 399 (1) No two distinct variables should represent the same underlying mailbox name.
- 400 (2) Once let-bound to a different name, a mailbox variable is considered out-of scope.
- 401 (3) A mailbox name cannot be used after it has been used in a **guard** expression.

402 These principles ensure syntactic hygiene: the first and second handle the disconnect
403 between static names and their dynamic counterparts, allowing us to reason that two
404 syntactically distinct variables indeed refer to different mailboxes. The third ensures that
405 a mailbox name is correctly ‘consumed’ by a **guard** expression, allowing us to correctly
406 update its type.
407
408

409 *Aliasing through communication.* We further need to consider the possibility that aliasing
 410 is introduced as a consequence of communication. Consider the following example, where
 411 mailbox a receives the message $\mathbf{m}(b)$, where b is already free in the continuation of the
 412 **receive** clause:

```

413           guard a : m {
414             receive m(x) from y ↦
415   a ← m(b)  ||   b ! n(x);           →   b ! n(b);
416             free y                               free a
417           }

```

418 In the above example, $a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(b)$ refers to a message $\mathbf{m}(b)$ that has been sent to mailbox
 419 a . Here, although the code suggests that x and b are distinct, aliasing is introduced through
 420 communication (violating principle 1).
 421

422 2.2 Mailbox Calculus Solution: Dependency Graphs

423 The mailbox calculus uses a *dependency graph* (DG) both to avoid issues with aliasing and to
 424 eliminate cyclic dependencies and hence deadlocks. In a dependency graph, the vertices are
 425 mailbox names, and an edge arises between two vertices if one name depends on another.
 426 Specifically, a dependency arises between two names a and b if b appears as a payload in a
 427 message addressed to a (meaning that a process must receive from a before being able to
 428 use b) or if b appears in the continuation of a process that must first receive from a . As an
 429 example, the mailbox calculus process $(\nu a)(\nu b)(a ! \mathbf{m}(b) \parallel \mathbf{free} b \parallel a ? \mathbf{m}(x) . \mathbf{free} a)$ would
 430 have DG $(\nu a)(\nu b)(\{a, b\})$ due to the dependency arising from sending b over a .
 431

432 Alas, a language implementation *cannot* use this approach as it relies on knowing runtime
 433 names directly. To see why, consider the following Pat program, which evaluates to an
 434 analogous configuration:
 435

```

436           let a = new in
437           let b = new in
438           a ! m(b); spawn (free b);
439           guard a : m {
440             receive m(x) from a ↦ free a
441           }
442

```

443 The first issue is how to create a scoped DG from **new**: one option is to introduce a
 444 scoped construct **let mailbox** x **in** M , but this approach fails as soon as we rename x using a
 445 **let**-binder. A more robust approach could be to follow [Ahmed et al. \(2007\)](#) and [Padovani \(2019\)](#)
 446 and endow mailbox types with a type-level identity by giving **new** an existential type
 447 and introducing a scoped **unpack** construct. However there still remain two issues: first, it is
 448 unclear how to extend DGs to capture the more complex scoping and sequencing induced
 449 by nested contexts. Second, each mailbox type would require an identity (e.g. $!^{\mathbf{Msg}}$) which
 450 becomes too restrictive, since we would need to include identities in message payload types
 451 when communicating names. As an example, each client of the Future example from §1
 452 would require a separate message type.
 453
 454

455 2.3 The Pat Solution: Quasi-Linear Typing

456 The many-sender, single-receiver pattern is closely linked to *quasi-linear typing* ([Kobayashi 1999](#))
 457 ([1999](#)); our formulation is closer to that of [Ennals et al. \(2004\)](#). Quasi-linear types were
 458
 459

originally designed to overcome some limitations of full linear types in the context of memory management and programming convenience and allow a value to be used once as a *first-class* (returnable) value, but several times as a *second-class* value (Osvald et al. 2016). A second-class value can be *consumed* within an expression, for example as the subject of a send operation, but cannot escape the scope in which it is defined.

This distinction maps directly onto the many-writer, single-reader communication model used by the mailbox calculus. We augment mailbox types with a *usage*: either \bullet , a *returnable* reference that allows a type to appear in the return type of an expression; or \circ , a ‘second-class’ reference. The subject of a **guard** must be returnable. With usage information we can ensure that:

- (1) there is *only one* returnable reference for each mailbox name in a process
- (2) only returnable references can be renamed, avoiding problems with aliasing
- (3) the returnable reference is the final lexical use of a mailbox name in a process

Quasi-linear types rule out all three of the previous examples. In `unsafeUse1`, x is consumed by the **guard** expression and cannot be used thereafter. In `unsafeUse2`, since x is the subject of a **let** binding, it must be returnable and therefore cannot be used in the body of the binding. In `unsafeUse3`, since x is used as the subject of a **guard** expression, that use must be first-class and therefore the last lexical occurrence of x , ruling out the use of x in the outer evaluation context. Quasi-linear typing cannot account for inter-process deadlocks, but can still rule out self-deadlocks.

Ruling out aliasing through communication. Quasi-linear types alone do not safeguard against introducing aliasing through communication, and we cannot use DGs for the reasons stated above. However, treating all received names as second-class, coupled with some simple syntactic restrictions (*e.g.* by ensuring that either all message payloads or all variables free in the body of the **receive** clause have base types) eliminates unsafe aliasing.

Summary. Quasi-linear types and the lightweight syntactic checks outlined above ensure that mailboxes are used safely in a concurrent language that allows aliasing, and obviate the need for the static global dependency graph used in the mailbox calculus. We show that the checks are not excessively restrictive by expressing all of the examples shown by de’Liguoro and Padovani (2018), and all of the 11 Savina benchmarks (Imam and Sarkar 2014) used by Neykova and Yoshida (2017b) to demonstrate expressiveness of behavioural type systems for actor languages (§6.2).

3 Pat: A Core Language with Mailbox Types

This section introduces Pat, a core functional programming language with mailbox types, along with a declarative type system and an operational semantics.

3.1 Syntax

Figure 2 shows the syntax for Pat. We defer discussion of types to §3.2.

Programs and definitions. A program $\mathcal{P} = (S, \vec{D}, M)$ consists of a *signature* S which maps message tags to payload types; a set of *definitions* \vec{D} ; and an *initial term* M . Each definition **def** $f(\vec{x} : \vec{A}) : B \{M\}$ is a function with name f , annotated arguments $\vec{x} : \vec{A}$, return type B ,

511	Syntax of types		
512	Mailbox types	J, K	$::= !E \mid ?E$
513	Mailbox patterns	E, F	$::= \emptyset \mid \mathbb{1} \mid \mathbf{m} \mid E \oplus F \mid E \odot F \mid E^*$
514	Base types	C	$::= \mathbf{1} \mid \text{Int} \mid \text{String} \mid \dots$
515	Types	T, U	$::= C \mid J$
516	Usage annotations	η	$::= \circ \mid \bullet$
517	Usage-annotated types	A, B	$::= C \mid J^\eta$
518	Type environments	Γ, Π	$::= \cdot \mid \Gamma, x : A$
519	Syntax of terms		
520	Variables	x, y, z	
521	Definition names	f	
522	Definitions	D	$::= \mathbf{def} f(\overrightarrow{x} : \overrightarrow{A}) : B \{M\}$
523	Values	V, W	$::= x \mid c$
524	Computations	L, M, N	$::= V \mid \mathbf{let} x : T = M \mathbf{in} N \mid f(\overrightarrow{V})$
525			$\mid \mathbf{spawn} M \mid \mathbf{new} \mid V ! \mathbf{m}(\overrightarrow{W}) \mid \mathbf{guard} V \{\overrightarrow{G}\}$
526	Guards	G	$::= \mathbf{fail} \mid \mathbf{free} \mapsto M \mid \mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\overrightarrow{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto M$
527			
528			

Fig. 2. The syntax of Pat, a core language with mailbox types

and body M . We write $\mathcal{P}(f)$ to retrieve the definition for function f , and $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{m})$ to retrieve the payload types for message \mathbf{m} .

Values. It is convenient to introduce a syntactic distinction between values and computations, inspired by *fine-grain call-by-value* (Levy et al. 2003), in order to simplify our typing rules. Values V, W include variables x and constants c ; we assume that the set of constants includes at least the unit value $()$ of type $\mathbf{1}$.

Terms. The functional fragment of the language is largely standard. Every value is a trivial computation. The only evaluation context is $\mathbf{let} x : T = M \mathbf{in} N$, which evaluates term M of type T , binding its result to x in continuation N . The type annotation is a technical convenience used when relating the declarative and algorithmic type systems and is not necessary in our implementation (§3). Function application $f(\overrightarrow{V})$ applies function f to arguments \overrightarrow{V} . As usual, we use $M; N$ as sugar for $\mathbf{let} x : \mathbf{1} = M \mathbf{in} N$, where x does not occur in N .

In the concurrent fragment of the language, $\mathbf{spawn} M$ spawns term M as a separate process, and \mathbf{new} creates a fresh mailbox name. Term $V ! \mathbf{m}(\overrightarrow{W})$ sends message \mathbf{m} with payloads \overrightarrow{W} to mailbox V .

The $\mathbf{guard} V \{\overrightarrow{G}\}$ construct inspects mailbox V and potentially invokes a guard in \overrightarrow{G} . Note that although our examples have included mailbox patterns in \mathbf{guard} expressions for clarity, and some annotations are required by our algorithmic type system (§4), annotations are not required in the core language used by the declarative type system.

The $\mathbf{free} \mapsto M$ guard is triggered when a mailbox is empty and there are no more references to it in the system; and $\mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\overrightarrow{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto M$ is triggered when the mailbox contains a message with tag \mathbf{m} , binding its payloads to \overrightarrow{x} and continuation mailbox with updated mailbox type to y in continuation term M .

In an untyped system, the \mathbf{fail} guard represents an irrecoverable failure and would be invoked if an unexpected message arrives (similar to raising an error in the Erlang Future

example in §1). Given Pat’s type system, **fail** eliminates a mailbox of type $?\emptyset$. As we will see in §3.4, the type system ensures that **fail** can never be evaluated. As an example, consider the following modification of the `fullFuture` example from §1 that includes an explicit **fail** guard if an erroneous **Put** message is received.

```

562     def fullFuture(self: FullFuture, value : Int): 1 {
563         guard self: Get* {
564             free  $\mapsto$  ()
565             receive Get(user) from self  $\mapsto$ 
566                 user ! Reply(value);
567                 fullFuture(self, value)
568             receive Put(x) from self  $\mapsto$ 
569                 guard self:  $\emptyset$  {fail}
570         }
571     }
572 }
573

```

We write **free** V as syntactic sugar for **guard** V {**free** \mapsto ()}, and **fail** V as syntactic sugar for **guard** V {**fail**}. It only makes sense to free the *input* reference to a mailbox; output references are consumed upon sending a message. We require that each clause within a **guard** expression is unique.

3.2 Type System

This section describes a declarative type system for Pat. We begin by discussing mailbox types in more depth, in particular showing how to define subtyping and equivalence.

3.2.1 Types

A mailbox type consists of a *capability*, either *output* $!$ or *input* $?$, and a *pattern*. A system can contain multiple references to a mailbox as an output capability, but only one as an input capability. A *pattern* is a *commutative* regular expression, *i.e.*, a regular expression where composition is unordered. The $\mathbb{1}$ pattern is the unit of pattern composition \odot , denoting the empty mailbox. The \emptyset pattern denotes the *unreliable* mailbox, which has received an unexpected message. It is not possible to send to, or receive from, an unreliable mailbox, but we will show that reduction does not cause a mailbox to become unreliable. The pattern **m** denotes a mailbox containing a single message **m**. Note that unlike in §1, our formalism does not pair a message tag with its payload; instead, tags are associated with payload types via the program signature. This design choice allows us to more easily compare the declarative system with the algorithmic system in §4, and unlike (de’Liguoro and Padovani 2018) means we need not define types and subtyping coinductively. Pattern choice $E \oplus F$ denotes that the mailbox contains either messages conforming to pattern E or messages conforming to pattern F . Pattern composition $E \odot F$ denotes that the mailbox contains messages conforming to E and messages conforming to F (in either order). Finally, E^* denotes replication of E , so **m** * denotes that the mailbox can contain zero or more instances of message **m**. Mailbox patterns obey the usual laws of commutative regular expressions: $\mathbb{1}$ is the unit for \odot , while \emptyset is the unit for \oplus and is cancelling for \odot . Composition \odot is associative, commutative, and distributes over \oplus ; and \oplus is associative and commutative.

613 *Pattern semantics.* It follows that different syntactic representations of patterns may have the
 614 same meaning, e.g. patterns $\mathbb{1} \oplus \mathbb{0} \oplus (\mathbf{m} \odot \mathbf{n})$ and $\mathbb{1} \oplus (\mathbf{n} \odot \mathbf{m})$. Following (de'Liguoro and
 615 Padovani 2018), we define a set-of-multisets semantics for mailbox patterns: the intuition is
 616 that each multiset defines a configuration of messages that could be present in the mailbox.
 617 For example the semantic representation of both of the patterns above is $\{\langle \rangle, \langle \mathbf{m}, \mathbf{n} \rangle\}$. We let
 618 A, B range over multisets.

$$\begin{aligned}
 620 \llbracket \mathbb{0} \rrbracket &= \emptyset & 621 \llbracket \mathbb{1} \rrbracket &= \{\langle \rangle\} & 621 \llbracket E \oplus F \rrbracket &= \llbracket E \rrbracket \cup \llbracket F \rrbracket & 621 \llbracket E \odot F \rrbracket &= \{A \uplus B \mid A \in \llbracket E \rrbracket, B \in \llbracket F \rrbracket\} \\
 622 & & 623 \llbracket \mathbf{m} \rrbracket &= \{\langle \mathbf{m} \rangle\} & 623 \llbracket E^* \rrbracket &= \llbracket \mathbb{1} \rrbracket \cup \llbracket E \rrbracket \cup \llbracket E \odot E \rrbracket \cup \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

624 The pattern $\mathbb{0}$ is interpreted as an empty set; $\mathbb{1}$ as the empty multiset; \oplus as set union; \odot as
 625 pointwise multiset union; \mathbf{m} as the singleton multiset; and E^* as the infinite set containing
 626 any number of compositions of interpretations of E .

628 *Usage annotations.* A type T can be a *base type* C , or a mailbox type J . As discussed in §2,
 629 *quasi-linearity* is used to avoid aliasing issues. *Usage-annotated* types A, B annotate mailbox
 630 types with a usage: either second-class (\circ), or returnable (\bullet). There are no restrictions on the
 631 use of a base type. Only values with a returnable type can be returned from an evaluation
 632 frame.

634 3.2.2 Operations on Types

635 We say that a type is *returnable*, written $\text{returnable}(A)$, if A is a base type C or a returnable
 636 mailbox type J^\bullet . The $[-]$ operator produces a returnable type from a non-annotated type, or
 637 changes an arbitrary mailbox type to be returnable. Similarly, the $[-]$ operator produces a
 638 usable type:

$$640 \llbracket C \rrbracket = C \quad 641 \llbracket T \rrbracket = T^\bullet \quad 642 \llbracket J^\eta \rrbracket = J^\bullet \quad 643 \llbracket C \rrbracket = C \quad 644 \llbracket T \rrbracket = T^\circ \quad 645 \llbracket J^\eta \rrbracket = J^\circ$$

646 We also extend the operators to type environments in the usual way. The $\text{base}(A)$ predicate
 647 holds if A is some base type C . We extend the operator to environments: $\text{base}(\Gamma)$ holds if
 648 for all $x : A \in \Gamma$, it follows that $\text{base}(A)$.

649 *Subtyping.* Subtyping is crucial for mailbox typing. Rather than being an additional feature
 650 to increase the expressiveness of the system, subtyping is the core technical mechanism that
 651 allows us to determine whether an inferred pattern is contained within a specification, for
 652 example checking that $\text{Get} \odot \text{Get}$ is contained within a specification Get^* . Subtyping relies
 653 on *pattern inclusion*. A pattern E is *included* in a pattern F , written $E \sqsubseteq F$, if every multiset
 654 in the semantics of E also occurs in the semantics of pattern F , i.e., $E \sqsubseteq F \triangleq \llbracket E \rrbracket \subseteq \llbracket F \rrbracket$.

655 **Definition 1** (Subtyping). *The subtyping relation is defined by the following rules:*

$$\begin{array}{c}
 656 \\
 657 \frac{}{C \leq C} \qquad \frac{E \sqsubseteq F \quad \eta_1 \leq \eta_2}{?E^{\eta_1} \leq ?F^{\eta_2}} \qquad \frac{F \sqsubseteq E \quad \eta_1 \leq \eta_2}{!E^{\eta_1} \leq !F^{\eta_2}}
 \end{array}$$

660 Usage subtyping is defined as the smallest reflexive operator defined by axioms $\eta \leq \eta$ and
 661 $\bullet \leq \circ$. We write $A \simeq B$ if both $A \leq B$ and $B \leq A$, i.e. either A, B are the same base type, or
 662 are mailbox types with the same capability and pattern semantics.

663

Base types are subtypes of themselves. As with previous accounts of subtyping in actor languages (He et al. 2014), subtyping is *covariant* for mailbox types with a receive capability: a mailbox can safely be replaced with another that can receive more messages. Likewise subtyping is *contravariant* for mailboxes with a send capability: a mailbox can safely be replaced with another that can send a smaller set of messages. Intuitively, as returnable usages are more powerful than second-class usages, returnable types can be used when only a second-class type is required.

Following de’Liguoro and Padovani (2018) we introduce names for particular classes of mailbox types. Intuitively, relevant mailbox names *must* be used, whereas irrelevant names need not be. Likewise reliable and usable names *can* be used, whereas unreliable and unusable names cannot.

Definition 2 (Relevant, Reliable, Usable). *A mailbox type J is relevant if $J \not\leq !\mathbb{1}$, and irrelevant otherwise; reliable if $J \not\leq ?\mathbb{0}$ and unreliable otherwise; and usable if $!\mathbb{0} \not\leq J$ and unusable otherwise.*

A type environment Γ is reliable if all input mailbox types $?E$ in Γ are reliable.

Definition 3 (Unrestricted and Linear Types). *We say that a type A is unrestricted, written $un(A)$, if A is a base type or $A = !\mathbb{1}^\circ$. Otherwise, we say that T is linear.*

Our type system ensures that variables with a linear type must be used, whereas variables with an unrestricted type can be discarded. We extend subtyping to type environments, making it possible to combine type environments (Crafa and Padovani 2017; de’Liguoro and Padovani 2018).

Definition 4 (Environment subtyping). *Environment subtyping $\Gamma_1 \leq \Gamma_2$ is the preorder relation on environments defined as follows:*

$$\frac{}{\Gamma \leq \Gamma} \quad \frac{\Gamma_1 \leq \Gamma_2 \quad \Gamma_2 \leq \Gamma_3}{\Gamma_1 \leq \Gamma_3} \quad \frac{un(A)}{\Gamma, x : A \leq \Gamma} \quad \frac{A \leq B}{\Gamma, x : A \leq \Gamma, x : B}$$

The subtyping relation includes a notion of weakening, allowing an environment Γ to be a subtype environment of Γ' if it contains additional entries of unrestricted type.

Type combination. Mailbox types ensure that sends and receives “balance out”, meaning that every send is matched with a receive. For example, using a mailbox at type **!Put** and **?(Put \odot Get^{*})** results in a mailbox type **?(Get^{*})**. The key technical device used to achieve this goal is *type combination*: combining a mailbox type **!E** and a mailbox type **!F** results in an output mailbox type which must send *both E and F*; combining an input and an output capability results in an input capability that no longer needs to receive the output pattern. We can also combine identical base types. Note that it is *not* possible to combine two input capabilities as this would permit simultaneous reads of the same mailbox.

Definition 5 (Type combination). *Type combination $T \boxplus U$ is the commutative partial binary operator defined by the following axioms:*

$$C \boxplus C = C \quad !E \boxplus !F = !(E \odot F) \quad !E \boxplus ?(E \odot F) = ?F \quad ?(E \odot F) \boxplus !E = ?F$$

Following Crafa and Padovani (2017), for convenience we identify types up to commutativity and associativity, e.g. we do not distinguish between **?(A \odot B)^{*}** and **?(B \odot A)^{*}**, though since

these patterns are semantically equivalent we can always rewrite one into another using subtyping. We may however need to use subtyping to rewrite a type into a form that allows two mailbox types to be combined (*e.g.* to combine $!A$ and $?(A^*)$, we would need to use subtyping to rewrite the latter type to $?(A \odot A^*)$).

The following *usage combination* operator is not commutative because a \circ variable use must occur *before* a \bullet use (ensuring that the returnable use is the variable's last lexical occurrence). Furthermore, note that $\bullet \triangleright \bullet$ is undefined (ensuring that there is only one returnable instance of a variable per thread).

Definition 6 (Usage combination). *The usage combination operator is the partial binary operator defined by the axioms $\circ \triangleright \circ = \circ$ and $\circ \triangleright \bullet = \bullet$.*

We can now define usage-annotated type and environment combination.

Definition 7 (Usage-annotated type combination). *The usage-annotated type combination operator $A \triangleright B$ is the binary operator defined by the axioms $C \triangleright C = C$ and $J^{\eta_1} \triangleright K^{\eta_2} = (J \boxplus K)^{\eta_1 \triangleright \eta_2}$.*

Definition 8 (Environment combination (Γ)). *The usage-annotated environment combination operator $\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2$ is the smallest partial operator on type environments closed under the following rules:*

$$\frac{}{\cdot \triangleright \cdot = \cdot} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Gamma_2) \quad \Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2 = \Gamma}{(\Gamma_1, x : A) \triangleright \Gamma_2 = \Gamma, x : A} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Gamma_1) \quad \Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2 = \Gamma}{\Gamma_1 \triangleright (\Gamma_2, x : A) = \Gamma, x : A}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2 = \Gamma}{(\Gamma_1, x : A) \triangleright (\Gamma_2, x : B) = \Gamma, x : (A \triangleright B)}$$

Since usage combination is not commutative, usage-annotated type combination is only used when typing a thread. When typing multiple processes we use an alternative environment combination operator, described in §3.4.

We use usage-annotated type combination when combining the types of two variables used in subsequent evaluation frames (*i.e.* in the subject and body of a **let** expression). We also require *disjoint* combination, where two environments are only able to share variables of base type:

Definition 9 (Disjoint environment combination). *Disjoint environment combination $\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2$ is the smallest partial operator on type environments closed under the following rules:*

$$\frac{}{\cdot + \cdot = \cdot} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Gamma_2) \quad \Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 = \Gamma}{\Gamma_1, x : A + \Gamma_2 = \Gamma, x : A} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Gamma_1) \quad \Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 = \Gamma}{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2, x : A = \Gamma, x : A}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 = \Gamma}{\Gamma_1, x : C + \Gamma_2, x : C = \Gamma, x : C}$$

3.2.3 Pattern Residual and Pattern Normal Form

Before looking at the typing rules, it is useful to discuss the concepts of a *pattern derivative* and *pattern normal form*, whose formal descriptions are given in Figure 3.

$$\begin{array}{c}
766 \quad \text{Pattern residual} \quad \boxed{E / \mathbf{m}} \\
767 \\
768 \quad \emptyset / \mathbf{m} \triangleq \emptyset \quad \mathbb{1} / \mathbf{m} \triangleq \emptyset \quad \mathbf{m} / \mathbf{m} \triangleq \mathbb{1} \quad \frac{\mathbf{m} \neq \mathbf{n}}{\mathbf{m} / \mathbf{n} \triangleq \emptyset} \quad (E \oplus F) / \mathbf{m} \triangleq (E / \mathbf{m}) \oplus (F / \mathbf{m}) \\
769 \\
770 \\
771 \quad (E^*) / \mathbf{m} = (E / \mathbf{m}) \odot E^* \quad (E \odot F) / \mathbf{m} \triangleq ((E / \mathbf{m}) \odot F) \oplus (E \odot (F / \mathbf{m})) \\
772 \quad \text{Pattern normal form (PNF)} \quad \boxed{\vDash E} \quad \boxed{E \vDash_{\text{lit}} F} \quad \boxed{E \vDash F} \\
773 \quad \frac{E \vDash E}{\vDash E} \quad E \vDash_{\text{lit}} \emptyset \quad E \vDash_{\text{lit}} \mathbb{1} \quad \frac{F \simeq E / \mathbf{m}}{E \vDash_{\text{lit}} \mathbf{m} \odot F} \quad \frac{E \vDash_{\text{lit}} F_1 \quad E \vDash F_2}{E \vDash F_1 \oplus F_2} \quad \frac{E \vDash_{\text{lit}} F}{E \vDash F} \\
774 \\
775 \\
776 \\
777
\end{array}$$

Fig. 3. Pattern Residual and Pattern Normal Form

780 *Pattern Residual.* Whenever we receive a message from a mailbox, the type of the receive
781 reference to that should be updated to reflect that the message is no longer in the mailbox. For
782 example in our Future example, the EmptyFuture type is $?(Put \odot Get^*)$, but the FullFuture
783 type (used after receiving the **Put** message) is $?(Get^*)$ (that is, the EmptyFuture type
784 without the **Put** message).

785 The *pattern residual* E / \mathbf{m} calculates the pattern E after \mathbf{m} is consumed, and corresponds
786 to the Brzozowski derivative (Brzozowski 1964) over a commutative regular expression. The
787 residual of \emptyset , $\mathbb{1}$, or \mathbf{n} (where $\mathbf{n} \neq \mathbf{m}$) with respect to a message tag \mathbf{m} is the unreliable type \emptyset .
788 The residual of \mathbf{m} with respect to \mathbf{m} is $\mathbb{1}$. The residual operator distributes over \oplus , and the
789 residual of composition is the disjunction of the residual of each subpattern. In our example,
790 $(Put \odot Get^*) / Put = Get^*$.

793 *Pattern Normal Form.* When typing **guard** expressions, we require mailbox types to be in
794 *pattern normal form* (PNF). A pattern E is in PNF if it is in the form $E_1 \oplus \dots \oplus E_n$ where
795 each E_i is either \emptyset (used for typing a **fail** guard); $\mathbb{1}$ (used for typing a **free** guard); or of the
796 form $\mathbf{m} \odot F$ (used for typing a **receive** guard, where F is equivalent to E / \mathbf{m}).

797 We express PNF using three judgements: Judgement $E \vDash F$ can be read “pattern F is
798 a subpattern of E , where E is in pattern normal form”. Judgement $E \vDash_{\text{lit}} F$ is similar but
799 requires F to be free of pattern choice constructors (\oplus). Judgement $\vDash E$ can be read “pattern
800 E is in pattern normal form”, and holds if $E \vDash E$.

802 As an example, pattern $\mathbb{1} \oplus \emptyset \oplus (\mathbf{m} \odot \mathbf{n})$ is in PNF: we could guard on a mailbox with this
803 pattern by including a **free** guard, a **fail** guard, and a **receive** guard that receives a message
804 with tag \mathbf{m} . However, the equivalent pattern $(\mathbb{1} \odot \mathbb{1}) \oplus (\mathbb{1} \odot \emptyset) \oplus (\mathbf{m} \odot \mathbf{n})$ is *not* in PNF.

805 The definition of PNF relies on the definition of the pattern residual, and PNF is later used
806 in the typing rule for **guard** expressions.

808 3.2.4 Typing Rules

809 Figure 4 shows declarative typing rules for Pat. As the system is declarative it helps to read
810 the rules top-down.

812 *Programs and definitions.* A program is typable if all of its definitions are typable, and
813 its body has unit type. A definition $\text{def } f(\overrightarrow{x : \overrightarrow{A}}) : B \{M\}$ is typable if M has type B under
814 environment $x : \overrightarrow{A}$.

817	Typing rules for programs and definitions		$\vdash \mathcal{P}$	$\vdash D$
818	$\mathcal{P} = (S, \vec{D}, M) \quad (\vdash_{\mathcal{P}} D_i)_i \quad \cdot \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} M : \mathbf{1}$		$\frac{\overrightarrow{x : \dot{A}} \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} M : B}{\vdash_{\mathcal{P}} \mathbf{def} f(x : \dot{A}) : B \{M\}}$	
819	$\vdash \mathcal{P}$		$\vdash_{\mathcal{P}} \mathbf{def} f(x : \dot{A}) : B \{M\}$	
820	$\vdash \mathcal{P}$		$\vdash_{\mathcal{P}} \mathbf{def} f(x : \dot{A}) : B \{M\}$	
821	Typing rules for values and computations		$\Gamma \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} M : A$	
822	T-VAR		T-CONST	
823	$\frac{}{x : A \vdash x : A}$	$\frac{}{c \text{ has base type } C \quad \cdot \vdash c : C}$	T-APP	
824	$\frac{}{x : A \vdash x : A}$		$\frac{\mathcal{P}(f) = \mathbf{def} f(x : \dot{A}) : B \{M\} \quad (\Gamma_i \vdash V_i : A_i)_{i \in 1..n}}{\Gamma_1 + \dots + \Gamma_n \vdash f(V_1, \dots, V_n) : B}$	
825	$x : A \vdash x : A$		$\Gamma_1 + \dots + \Gamma_n \vdash f(V_1, \dots, V_n) : B$	
826	T-LET		T-SPAWN	
827	$\frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash M : [T] \quad \Gamma_2, x : [T] \vdash N : B}{\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2 \vdash \mathbf{let} x : T = M \mathbf{in} N : B}$	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash M : \mathbf{1}}{[\Gamma] \vdash \mathbf{spawn} M : \mathbf{1}}$		T-NEW
828	$\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2 \vdash \mathbf{let} x : T = M \mathbf{in} N : B$		$[\Gamma] \vdash \mathbf{spawn} M : \mathbf{1}$	
829	$\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2 \vdash \mathbf{let} x : T = M \mathbf{in} N : B$		$\cdot \vdash \mathbf{new} : ?\mathbf{1}^*$	
830	T-SEND		T-GUARD	
831	$\frac{\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{T} \quad (\Gamma'_i \vdash W_i : [T_i])_{i \in 1..n}}{\Gamma \vdash V : !\mathbf{m}^{\circ} \quad \Gamma + \Gamma'_1 + \dots + \Gamma'_n \vdash V !\mathbf{m}(\vec{W}) : \mathbf{1}}$	$\frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash V : ?E^* \quad \{E\} \Gamma_2 \vdash \vec{G} : A \quad \vDash E}{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash \mathbf{guard} V \{\vec{G}\} : A}$	T-SUB	
832	$\Gamma \vdash V : !\mathbf{m}^{\circ} \quad (\Gamma'_i \vdash W_i : [T_i])_{i \in 1..n}$		$\Gamma \leq \Gamma' \quad A \leq B \quad \Gamma' \vdash M : A$	
833	$\Gamma + \Gamma'_1 + \dots + \Gamma'_n \vdash V !\mathbf{m}(\vec{W}) : \mathbf{1}$		$\Gamma \vdash M : B$	
834	$\Gamma + \Gamma'_1 + \dots + \Gamma'_n \vdash V !\mathbf{m}(\vec{W}) : \mathbf{1}$		$\Gamma \vdash M : B$	
835	$\Gamma + \Gamma'_1 + \dots + \Gamma'_n \vdash V !\mathbf{m}(\vec{W}) : \mathbf{1}$		$\Gamma \vdash M : B$	
836	Typing rules for guards		$\{E\} \Gamma \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} \vec{G} : A$	$\{E\} \Gamma \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} G : A$
837	TG-GUARDSEQ		TG-FAIL	
838	$\frac{(\{E_i\} \Gamma \vdash G_i : A)_{i \in 1..n}}{\{E_1 \oplus \dots \oplus E_n\} \Gamma \vdash \vec{G} : A}$		$\frac{}{\{\emptyset\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fail} : A}$	
839	$\{E_1 \oplus \dots \oplus E_n\} \Gamma \vdash \vec{G} : A$		$\{\mathbf{1}\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{free} \mapsto M : A$	
840	$\{E_1 \oplus \dots \oplus E_n\} \Gamma \vdash \vec{G} : A$		$\{\mathbf{1}\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{free} \mapsto M : A$	
841	TG-RECV		$\frac{\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{T} \quad \mathbf{base}(\vec{T}) \vee \mathbf{base}(\Gamma) \quad \Gamma, y : ?E^*, \vec{x} : [\vec{T}] \vdash M : B}{\{\mathbf{m} \odot E\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto M : B}$	
842	$\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{T} \quad \mathbf{base}(\vec{T}) \vee \mathbf{base}(\Gamma) \quad \Gamma, y : ?E^*, \vec{x} : [\vec{T}] \vdash M : B$		$\{\mathbf{m} \odot E\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto M : B$	
843	$\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{T} \quad \mathbf{base}(\vec{T}) \vee \mathbf{base}(\Gamma) \quad \Gamma, y : ?E^*, \vec{x} : [\vec{T}] \vdash M : B$		$\{\mathbf{m} \odot E\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto M : B$	
844	$\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{T} \quad \mathbf{base}(\vec{T}) \vee \mathbf{base}(\Gamma) \quad \Gamma, y : ?E^*, \vec{x} : [\vec{T}] \vdash M : B$		$\{\mathbf{m} \odot E\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto M : B$	

Fig. 4. Declarative typing rules for Pat

848 *Terms.* Term typing has the judgement $\Gamma \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} M : A$, which states that when defined in the
849 context of program \mathcal{P} , under environment Γ , term M has type A . We omit the \mathcal{P} parameter in
850 the rules for readability. Rule T-VAR types a variable in a singleton environment; we account
851 for weakening in T-SUB. Rule T-CONST types a constant under an empty environment; we
852 assume an implicit schema mapping constants to types, and assume the existence of at least
853 the unit value $()$ of type $\mathbf{1}$. Rule T-APP types function application according to the definition
854 in \mathcal{P} . Each argument must be typable under a disjoint type environment to avoid aliasing
855 mailbox names in the body of the function.

856 Rule T-LET types sequential composition. The subject of the **let** expression must be
857 returnable: since $\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2$ is defined, we know that if the subject (typable using Γ_1) contains a
858 returnable variable, then it cannot appear in Γ_2 . This avoids aliasing and unsafe usage errors.

859 Rule T-SPAWN types the **spawn** M construct, which spawns a unit-typed term M as a new
860 process. The type environment used to type M can contain any number of returnable types,
861 but the conclusion of the rule “masks” any returnable types as second-class. Intuitively, this
862 is because there is no need to impose an ordering on how a variable is used in a separate
863 process: while within a single process a **guard** on some name x should not precede a send on
864 x , there is no such restriction if the two expressions are executing in concurrent processes.
865
866
867

868 Rule T-NEW creates a fresh mailbox with type $?1^\bullet$, since subsequent sends and receives must
 869 “balance out” to an empty mailbox.

870 Rule T-SEND types a send expression $V ! \mathbf{m}(\vec{W})$, where a message \mathbf{m} with payloads \vec{W} is
 871 sent to a mailbox V . Value V must be a reference with type $!m^\circ$, meaning that it can be used
 872 to send message \mathbf{m} . The mailbox only needs to be *second-class*, but subtyping means that we
 873 can also send to a returnable name. All payloads \vec{W} must be subtypes of the types defined by
 874 the signature for message \mathbf{m} , and payloads must be typable under separate environments to
 875 avoid aliasing when receiving a message. Unlike in session-typed functional programming
 876 languages, sending is a side-effecting operation of type $\mathbf{1}$; the behavioural typing is instead
 877 enforced using environment composition.

879 Rule T-GUARD types the expression $\mathbf{guard} V \{ \vec{G} \}$, which retrieves from mailbox V using
 880 guards \vec{G} . The first premise ensures that under a type environment Γ_1 , mailbox V has type
 881 $?E^\bullet$: the mailbox should have a receive capability with pattern E , and must be returnable.
 882 Demanding that the mailbox is returnable rules out unsafe usage errors since we cannot use
 883 the mailbox name in the continuation. The second premise states that under type environment
 884 Γ_2 , guards \vec{G} all return a value of type A and correspond to pattern E . The final premise,
 885 $\vDash E$, ensures that E is in pattern normal form.

887 Finally, rule T-SUB allows the use of subtyping. Subtyping on type environments is crucial
 888 when constructing derivations, *e.g.* two patterns may have the same semantics but differ
 889 syntactically. Applying T-SUB makes it possible to rewrite mailbox types so that they can be
 890 combined by the type combination operators. We also allow the usual use of subsumption on
 891 return types, *e.g.* allowing the use of a value with a subtype of a function argument.

893 *Guards.* Rule TG-GUARDSEQ types a sequence of guards, ensuring that each guard is typable
 894 under the same type environment and with the same return type. Rule TG-FAIL types a failure
 895 guard: since the type system will ensure that such a guard is never evaluated, it can have any
 896 type environment and any type, and is typable under pattern literal \emptyset . Rule TG-FREE types a
 897 guard of the form $\mathbf{free} \mapsto M$, where M has type A .

899 Finally, rule TG-RCV types a guard of the form $\mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto M$, which
 900 retrieves a message with tag \mathbf{m} from the mailbox, binding its payloads (whose types are
 901 retrieved from the signature for message \mathbf{m}) to \vec{x} , and re-binding the mailbox to y with an
 902 updated type in continuation M . The payloads are made *second-class* rather than returnable, as
 903 otherwise the payloads could interfere with the names in the enclosing context and potentially
 904 violate the constraints required by quasi-linearity. The rule also introduces a conservative
 905 check to avoid aliasing by communication (§2): either all received payloads must have base
 906 types, or all free variables in the environment must have base types. We discuss a more liberal
 907 version of this condition in §5.5.

909 *Example.* We end this section by showing the derivation for the client definition from
 910 the future example in §1, which creates a future and self mailbox, initialises the future
 911 with a number, and then requests and prints the result. In the following, we abbreviate
 912 *future* to f , *self* to s , and *result* to r . We assume that the program includes a signature
 913 $S = [\mathbf{Put} \mapsto \text{Int}, \mathbf{Get} \mapsto !\mathbf{Reply}, \mathbf{Reply} \mapsto \text{Int}]$, and the `emptyFuture` and `fullFuture`
 914 definitions from §1. We split the derivation into three subderivations. Since it is easier to
 915 read derivations top-down, we start by typing the **guard** expression. In the following, we
 916 refer to the **receive** guard as G , and name the first derivation \mathbf{D}_1 :

918

$$\begin{array}{c}
919 \\
920 \\
921 \\
922 \\
923 \\
924 \\
925
\end{array}
\frac{
\frac{
\frac{
s : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet \vdash s : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet
}{s : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet \text{ free } s : \mathbf{1}}
\quad
r : \text{Int} \vdash \text{print}(\text{intToString}(r)) : \mathbf{1}
}{s : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet, r : \text{Int} \vdash \text{free } s; \text{print}(\text{intToString}(r)) : \mathbf{1}}
\quad
\frac{
s : ?(\text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1})^\bullet \vdash s : ?(\text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1})^\bullet
}{\{\text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1}\} \cdot \vdash}
\quad
\frac{
\text{receive Reply}(r) \text{ from } s \mapsto
\text{free } s; \text{print}(\text{intToString}(r))
}{: \mathbf{1}}
}{: \text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1}}
\frac{
\frac{
\frac{
\frac{
s : ?(\text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1})^\bullet \vdash s : ?(\text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1})^\bullet
}{\{\text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1}\} \cdot \vdash}
\quad
\text{receive Reply}(r) \text{ from } s \mapsto
\text{free } s; \text{print}(\text{intToString}(r))
}{: \mathbf{1}}
}{: \text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1}}
}{s : ?(\text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1})^\bullet \vdash \text{guard } s \{G\} : \mathbf{1}}$$

926 The type of the s mailbox in the subject of the **guard** expression is $?(\text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1})^\bullet$ denoting
927 that the mailbox can contain a single **Reply** message. The **receive** guard binds s at type $? \mathbb{1}^\bullet$
928 and r at Int , freeing s and using r in the **print** expression. The **Reply** annotation on the guard
929 is a subpattern of the pattern of s . The above derivation is used within derivation \mathbf{D}_2 :
930

$$\begin{array}{c}
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\end{array}
\frac{
\frac{
\frac{
f : !\text{Get}^\circ \vdash f : !\text{Get}^\circ
}{f : !\text{Get}^\bullet \vdash f : !\text{Get}^\circ}
\quad
\frac{
s : !\text{Reply}^\circ \vdash s : !\text{Reply}^\circ
}{f : !\text{Get}^\bullet, s : !\text{Reply}^\circ \vdash f !\text{Get}(s) : \mathbf{1}}
}{: \mathbf{D}_1}
\quad
\frac{
\frac{
f : !\text{Put}^\circ \vdash f : !\text{Put}^\circ
}{f : !\text{Put}^\circ \vdash f !\text{Put}(5) : \mathbf{1}}
\quad
\frac{
\cdot \vdash 5 : \text{Int}
}{f : !\text{Put}^\circ \vdash f !\text{Put}(5) : \mathbf{1}}
}{f : !\text{Get}^\bullet, s : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet \vdash}
\quad
\frac{
f !\text{Get}(s);
\text{guard } s \{G\}
}{: \mathbf{1}}
}{f : !(\text{Put} \odot \text{Get})^\bullet, s : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet \vdash}
\quad
\frac{
f !\text{Put}(5); f !\text{Get}(s);
\text{guard } s \{\dots\}
}{: \mathbf{1}}$$

939 Here f is used to send a **Put** and then a **Get** with s of type $!\text{Reply}^\circ$ as payload. As the two
940 sends to the f message are sequentially composed, the type of f at the root of the subderivation
941 is $!(\text{Put} \odot \text{Get})^\bullet$. Since s is used at type $?(\text{Reply} \odot \mathbb{1})^\bullet$ in \mathbf{D}_1 , the send and receive patterns
942 balance out to the empty mailbox type $? \mathbb{1}^\bullet$. Finally, we can construct the derivation for the
943 entire term:
944

$$\begin{array}{c}
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957
\end{array}
\frac{
\frac{
\frac{
f : ?(\text{Put} \odot \text{Get}^*)^\bullet \vdash \text{emptyFuture}(f) : \mathbf{1}
}{f : ?(\text{Put} \odot \text{Get}^*)^\circ \vdash \text{spawn emptyFuture}(f) : \mathbf{1}}
\quad
\frac{
\cdot \vdash \text{new} : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet
}{f : !(\text{Put} \odot \text{Get})^\bullet \vdash}
\quad
\frac{
\cdot \vdash \text{new} : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet
}{f !\text{Put}(5); \dots}
}{: \mathbf{D}_2}
\quad
\frac{
\frac{
\frac{
f : ?(\text{Put} \odot \text{Get}^*)^\bullet \vdash \text{emptyFuture}(f) : \mathbf{1}
}{f : ?(\text{Put} \odot \text{Get}^*)^\circ \vdash \text{spawn emptyFuture}(f) : \mathbf{1}}
\quad
\frac{
\cdot \vdash \text{new} : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet
}{f : !(\text{Put} \odot \text{Get})^\bullet \vdash}
\quad
\frac{
\cdot \vdash \text{new} : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet
}{f !\text{Put}(5); \dots}
}{: \mathbf{1}}
}{\cdot \vdash \text{new} : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet}
\quad
\frac{
\frac{
\frac{
\frac{
f : ?\mathbb{1}^\bullet \vdash
\text{spawn emptyFuture}(f);
\text{let } s = \text{new in}
f !\text{Put}(5); f !\text{Get}(s);
\text{guard } s \{
\text{receive Reply}(r) \text{ from } s \mapsto
\text{free } s;
\text{print}(\text{intToString}(r))
\}
}{: \mathbf{1}}
}{\cdot \vdash}
}{\cdot \vdash}$$

958 Since we let-bind f to **new**, f must have type $? \mathbb{1}^\bullet$. Definition `emptyFuture` requires an
959 argument of type $?(\text{Put} \odot \text{Get}^*)^\bullet$; since the function application appears in the body of the
960 **spawn** we can mask the usage annotation to \circ , and use environment subtyping to rewrite the
961 type of f to $?((\text{Put} \odot \text{Get}) \odot \mathbb{1})^\bullet$. This then balances out with the use of f in \mathbf{D}_2 , completing
962 the derivation.
963

964 3.3 Operational Semantics

965 Figure 5 shows the runtime syntax and reduction rules for Pat. We extend values V with
966 runtime names a . The concurrent semantics of the language is described as a nondeterministic
967 reduction relation on a language of *configurations*, which resemble terms in the π -calculus.
968
969

Runtime syntax

970			
971			
972	Runtime names	a	
973	Names	$u, v, w ::= x \mid a$	
974	Frames	$\sigma ::= \langle x, M \rangle$	
975	Frame stacks	$\Sigma ::= \epsilon \mid \sigma \cdot \Sigma$	
976	Guard contexts	$\mathcal{G} ::= \vec{G}_1 \cdot [] \cdot \vec{G}_2$	
977	Configurations	$C, \mathcal{D} ::= \langle M, \Sigma \rangle \mid a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(\vec{V}) \mid C \parallel \mathcal{D} \mid (va)C$	
978	Runtime type environments	$\Delta ::= \cdot \mid \Delta, u : T$	
979			

Reduction rules

$$C \longrightarrow_{\mathcal{P}} \mathcal{D}$$

980			
981			
982	E-LET	$\langle \mathbf{let} \ x : T = M \ \mathbf{in} \ N, \Sigma \rangle \longrightarrow \langle M, \langle x, N \rangle \cdot \Sigma \rangle$	
983	E-RETURN	$\langle V, \langle x, M \rangle \cdot \Sigma \rangle \longrightarrow \langle M\{V/x\}, \Sigma \rangle$	
984	E-APP	$\langle f(\vec{V}), \Sigma \rangle \longrightarrow \langle M\{\vec{V}/\vec{x}\}, \Sigma \rangle$ (if $\mathcal{P}(f) = \mathbf{def} \ f(x : \vec{A}) : B \ \{M\}$)	
985	E-NEW	$\langle \mathbf{new}, \Sigma \rangle \longrightarrow (va)(\langle a, \Sigma \rangle)$ (a is fresh)	
986	E-SEND	$\langle a ! \mathbf{m}(\vec{V}), \Sigma \rangle \longrightarrow \langle () , \Sigma \rangle \parallel a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(\vec{V})$	
987	E-SPAWN	$\langle \mathbf{spawn} \ M, \Sigma \rangle \longrightarrow \langle () , \Sigma \rangle \parallel \langle M, \epsilon \rangle$	
988			
989	E-FREE	$(va)(\langle \mathbf{guard} \ a \ \{ \mathcal{G}[\mathbf{free} \mapsto M] \}, \Sigma \rangle) \longrightarrow \langle M, \Sigma \rangle$	
990	E-RECV	$\langle \mathbf{guard} \ a \ \{ \mathcal{G}[\mathbf{receive} \ \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \ \mathbf{from} \ y \mapsto M] \}, \Sigma \rangle \parallel a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(\vec{V}) \longrightarrow \langle M\{\vec{V}/\vec{x}, a/y\}, \Sigma \rangle$	
991			
992	E-NU	$\frac{C \longrightarrow \mathcal{D}}{(va)C \longrightarrow (va)\mathcal{D}}$	
993	E-PAR	$\frac{C \longrightarrow C'}{C \parallel \mathcal{D} \longrightarrow C' \parallel \mathcal{D}}$	
994	E-STRUCT	$\frac{C \equiv C' \quad C' \longrightarrow \mathcal{D}' \quad \mathcal{D}' \equiv \mathcal{D}}{C \longrightarrow \mathcal{D}}$	
995			

Fig. 5. Pat operational semantics

996
997
998
999
1000 A thread $\langle M, \Sigma \rangle$ evaluates term M with frame stack Σ (discussed shortly). Configuration
1001 $a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(\vec{V})$ is a message $\mathbf{m}(\vec{V})$ in mailbox a ; name restriction $(va)C$ binds name a in C ;
1002 and $C \parallel \mathcal{D}$ denotes the parallel composition of C and \mathcal{D} . Structural congruence \equiv (omitted)
1003 is standard, capturing scope extrusion and the associativity and commutativity of parallel
1004 composition. The semantics envisages a single static term M (i.e., program text) to be
1005 evaluated in the context of an empty frame stack: $\langle M, \epsilon \rangle$.
1006

1007 *Frame stacks.* We use frame stacks (Ennals et al. 2004; Pitts 1998) rather than evaluation
1008 contexts for technical convenience: specifically, whereas evaluation contexts are defined
1009 directly on the structure of terms, the explicit definition of frame stacks makes it more
1010 convenient to define runtime typing rules that allow us to more easily reason about quasi-
1011 linearity during reduction (see §3.4). A frame $\langle x, M \rangle$ is a pair of a variable x and a continuation
1012 M , where x is free in M . A frame stack is an ordered sequence of frames, where ϵ denotes
1013 the empty stack.
1014

1015 *Reduction rules.* Frame stacks are best demonstrated by the E-LET and E-RETURN rules:
1016 intuitively, $\mathbf{let} \ x : T = M \ \mathbf{in} \ N$ evaluates M , binding the result to x in N . The rule adds a fresh
1017 frame $\langle x, N \rangle$ to the top of a frame stack, and evaluates M . Conversely, E-RETURN returns
1018 V into the parent frame: if the top frame is $\langle x, M \rangle$, then we can evaluate the continuation
1019
1020

1021 M with V substituted for x . Rule E-APP evaluates the body of function f with arguments \vec{V}
 1022 substituted for the parameters \vec{x} .

1023 Rule E-NEW creates a fresh mailbox name restriction and returns it into the calling context.
 1024 Rule E-SEND sends a message with tag \mathbf{m} and payloads \vec{V} to a mailbox a , returning $()$ to the
 1025 calling context and creating a sent message configuration $a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(\vec{V})$. Rule E-SPAWN spawns
 1026 a computation as a fresh process, with an empty frame stack. Rule E-FREE allows a name a to
 1027 be garbage collected if it is not contained in any other thread, evaluating the continuation M
 1028 of the **free** guard. Finally, rule E-RECV handles receiving a message from a mailbox, binding
 1029 the payload values to \vec{x} and updated mailbox name to y in continuation M . The remaining
 1030 rules are administrative.
 1031
 1032

1033 3.4 Metatheory

1034 In this section we describe Pat's metatheory: specifically that well-typed Pat programs will
 1035 never receive an unexpected message (*mailbox conformance*), and are free of self-deadlocks.
 1036 We achieve this by introducing a runtime type system to maintain inductive invariants during
 1037 evaluation, and proving type preservation and a progress result.
 1038

1039 3.4.1 Runtime Typing

1040 To prove metatheoretical properties about Pat we introduce a type system on configurations;
 1041 this type system is used only for reasoning and is not required for typechecking.
 1042

1043 *Runtime type environments.* The runtime typing rules make use of a type environment Δ
 1044 that maps variables to types that *do not* contain usage information. Usage information is
 1045 inherently only useful in constraining *sequential* uses of a mailbox variable, where guards are
 1046 blocking, whereas it makes little sense to constrain *concurrent* usages of a variable. Runtime
 1047 type environment combination $\Delta_1 \bowtie \Delta_2$ is similar to usage-annotated type environment
 1048 combination but with two differences: it is *commutative* to account for the unordered nature
 1049 of parallel threads, and type combination does not include usage information.
 1050

1051 **Definition 10** (Environment combination). *Environment combination $\Delta_1 \bowtie \Delta_2$ is the smallest*
 1052 *partial commutative binary operator on type environments closed under the following rules:*
 1053

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{}{\cdot \bowtie \cdot = \cdot} \qquad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Delta_2) \quad \Delta_1 \bowtie \Delta_2 = \Delta}{(\Delta_1, x:T) \bowtie \Delta_2 = \Delta, x:T} \qquad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Delta_1) \quad \Delta_1 \bowtie \Delta_2 = \Delta}{\Delta_1 \bowtie (\Delta_2, x:T) = \Delta, x:T} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Delta_1 \bowtie \Delta_2 = \Delta}{(\Delta_1, x:T) \bowtie (\Delta_2, x:U) = \Delta, x:(T \boxplus U)}
 \end{array}$$

1054
 1055
 1056
 1057
 1058
 1059
 1060
 1061 We can derive a runtime environment from a type environment by erasing all usage
 1062 annotations.

1063 **Definition 11** (Usage erasure). *The usage erasure operator is defined as follows:*

$$1064 \qquad |C| = C \qquad |J^n| = J$$

1065
 1066 We extend the operator to type environments by applying erasure pointwise on types, i.e.,
 1067 $|x_1 : A_1, \dots, x_n : A_n| = x_1 : |A_1|, \dots, x_n : |A_n|$.
 1068

1069 Disjoint combination on runtime type environments $\Delta_1 + \Delta_2$ (omitted) is defined analogously
 1070 to disjoint combination on Γ .
 1071

		$\Delta \vdash C$
1072	Configuration Typing	
1073		
1074	$\frac{\text{TP-NU}}{\Delta, a : ?\perp \vdash C}$	
1075	$\frac{\text{TP-PAR}}{\Delta_1 \bowtie \Delta_2 \vdash C \parallel \mathcal{D}}$	
1076	$\frac{\text{TP-MESSAGE}}{\Delta_1 + \dots + \Delta_n, a : !\mathbf{m} \vdash a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(\vec{V})}$	$\frac{(\llbracket \Delta_i \rrbracket \vdash V_i : A_i)_{i \in 1..n} \quad \vec{A} \leq [\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{m})]}{\Delta_1 + \dots + \Delta_n, a : !\mathbf{m} \vdash a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(\vec{V})}$
1077		
1078	$\frac{\text{TP-THREAD}}{\Delta \vdash \langle \Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2 \rangle \quad \Gamma_1 \vdash M : A \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash A \blacktriangleright \Sigma}$	$\frac{\text{TP-SUB}}{\Delta \leq \Delta' \quad \Delta' \vdash C}$
1079	$\Delta \vdash \langle M, \Sigma \rangle$	$\Delta \vdash C$
1080		
1081	Frame Stack Typing	$\Gamma \vdash A \blacktriangleright \Sigma$
1082		
1083	$\frac{\text{TF-EMPTY}}{\cdot \vdash A \blacktriangleright \epsilon} \quad \frac{\text{TF-FRAME}}{\Gamma_1, x : A \vdash M : B \quad \text{returnable}(A) \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash B \blacktriangleright \Sigma}$	$\frac{\text{TF-SUB}}{\Gamma_1 \leq \Gamma_2 \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash A \blacktriangleright \Sigma}$
1084	$\cdot \vdash A \blacktriangleright \epsilon$	$\Gamma_1 \vdash A \blacktriangleright \Sigma$
1085	$\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2 \vdash A \blacktriangleright \langle x, M \rangle \cdot \Sigma$	

Fig. 6. Pat runtime typing

1091 *Runtime typing rules.* Figure 6 shows the runtime typing rules. Rule TP-NU types a name
1092 restriction if the name is of type $?\perp$; in turn this ensures that sends and receives on the
1093 mailbox “balance out” across threads. Rule TP-PAR allows configurations C and \mathcal{D} to be
1094 composed in parallel if they are typable under combinable runtime type environments. Rule
1095 TP-MESSAGE types a message configuration $a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(\vec{V})$. Since contexts can only contain a
1096 single occurrence of a variable, name a of type $!\mathbf{m}$ cannot appear in $\Delta_1, \dots, \Delta_n$ and thus cannot
1097 occur in any of the values sent as a payload. This property is ensured in the corresponding
1098 static rule for message sends (T-SEND) because the environments used to type the target of the
1099 sends and the message payloads are combined using the disjoint environment combination
1100 operator $\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2$, and therefore cannot share mailbox-typed variables. Each payload value
1101 V must be a subtype of the type defined by the message signature, under the second-class
1102 lifting of a disjoint runtime type environment. Rule TP-SUB allows subtyping on runtime
1103 type environments; the subtyping relation $\Delta \leq \Delta'$ is analogous to subtyping on Γ .

1106 *Thread and frame stack typing.* Rule TP-THREAD types a thread, consisting of a currently-
1107 evaluating term (typable under Γ_1) and a stack frame (typable under Γ_2). Since the term and
1108 the stack frames execute sequentially, $\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2$ must be defined. Because usage annotations are
1109 thread-local, the runtime environment needed to type the thread is $\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2$ with annotations
1110 erased. TP-THREAD makes use of the frame stack typing judgement $\Gamma \vdash A \blacktriangleright \Sigma$ (inspired
1111 by Ennals et al. (2004)), which can be read “under type environment Γ , given a value of type A ,
1112 frame stack Σ is well-typed”. The empty frame stack is typable under the empty environment
1113 given any type (TF-EMPTY). Rule TF-FRAME details the typing rule for a non-empty frame
1114 stack $\langle x, M \rangle \cdot \Sigma$, which is well-typed if continuation M has type B , given a variable x of
1115 returnable type A . The remainder of the stack must then be well-typed given B . We combine
1116 the environments used for typing the head term and the remainder of the stack using \triangleright as we
1117 wish to account for sequential uses of a mailbox; for example, in the term $x !\mathbf{m}(V); x !\mathbf{n}(W)$,
1118 x would have type $!(\mathbf{m} \odot \mathbf{n})^\circ$. Finally, rule TF-SUB allows the use of subtyping when typing
1119 frame stacks.
1120
1121
1122

3.4.2 Preservation

We can now state some metatheoretical results. We give outlines of the salient proofs here but full proofs can be found in the extended version (Fowler et al. 2025).

Typability is preserved by reduction; the proof is nontrivial since we must do extensive reasoning about environment combination.

To begin with, we need to tame some of the complexity introduced by environment subtyping, since environment subtyping allows a notion of weakening. Read top-down, TP-SUB allows us to use environment subtyping to add a variable with mailbox type $!1$ or base type C , or replace a type with its subtype. It is therefore useful to introduce a definition referring to environments that can be populated by repeated uses of TP-SUB and which might not be used by a term. We call these environments *cruft*.

Definition 12 (Cruft). *A type environment Γ is cruft if $\Gamma \leq \cdot$.*

It also helps to define a stricter version of environment subtyping that does not permit weakening:

Definition 13 (Strict environment subtyping). *An environment Γ is a strict subtype environment of an environment Γ' , written $\Gamma \preceq \Gamma'$ if $\Gamma \leq \Gamma'$ and $\text{dom}(\Gamma) = \text{dom}(\Gamma')$.*

Definition 14 (Cruftless). *We say that an environment is cruftless for a term M if $\Gamma \vdash M : A$ and $\text{dom}(\Gamma) = \text{fv}(M)$.*

The following lemma allows us to separate the type environment required for typing the term from the cruft introduced by environment subtyping, and is used extensively within the preservation proof.

Lemma 1. *If $\Gamma \vdash M : A$, then there exist Π_1, Π_2, Π_3 such that:*

- $\Gamma = \Pi_1, \Pi_2$
- $\Pi_3 \vdash M : A'$
- Π_1 is cruftless for M , and $\Pi_1 \preceq \Pi_3$
- $A' \leq A$
- *cruft*(Π_2)

PROOF. Follows from the definition of environment subtyping: read top-down, each application of environment subtyping will either add a variable with an unrestricted type, or alter the type of an existing variable. \square

One of the most important lemmas uses quasi-linear typing to show that if two environments Π_1, Π_2 are combined with a third environment Γ using the \triangleright operator (i.e., Π_1, Π_2 are used to type an evaluation frame), and all types in environment Π_1 are returnable, then none of the mailbox variables in Π_1 are present in $\Pi_2 \triangleright \Gamma$. This lemma is crucial for reasoning about nested evaluation contexts and follows from the the definition of usage combination.

Lemma 2. *If $(\Pi_1, \Pi_2) \triangleright \Gamma$ is defined and returnable(Π_1), then $(\Pi_1, \Pi_2) \triangleright \Gamma = \Pi_1 + (\Pi_2 \triangleright \Gamma)$.*

PROOF. Follows from the definition of usage combination: the \triangleright operation is not commutative for returnable mailbox types, so the returnable mailbox type must be the last occurrence of that name in the combination. For base types, the definitions of combination for \triangleright and $+$ coincide. \square

The preservation theorem is interesting in that the type environment remains the same before and after reduction, reflecting the observation that sends and receives on a mailbox must eventually “balance out”. This reasoning is exemplified by the key *balancing lemma* used in the proof of preservation, showing the symmetry inherent in pattern inclusions:

Lemma 3 (Balancing (de’Liguoro and Padovani 2018)). *If $\mathbf{m} \odot F \sqsubseteq E$ and $F \not\sqsubseteq 0$, then $F \sqsubseteq E / \mathbf{m}$.*

We need several other lemmas to allow us to do equational reasoning on environments. For example, since we identify mailbox patterns up to associativity and commutativity, we can straightforwardly show that environment combination $\Gamma_1 \triangleright \Gamma_2$ is associative, and that runtime environment combination $\Delta_1 \bowtie \Delta_2$ is both associative and commutative.

Recall that a *type environment* Γ is reliable if all input mailbox types $?E$ in Γ are reliable, specifically that each $?E \not\sqsubseteq ?0$. We extend this definition to runtime environments Δ .

Theorem 1 (Preservation). *If $\vdash \mathcal{P}$, and $\Delta \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} C$ with Δ reliable, and $C \longrightarrow_{\mathcal{P}} \mathcal{D}$, then $\Delta \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} \mathcal{D}$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $C \longrightarrow \mathcal{D}$. □

Preservation implies mailbox conformance: the property that a configuration will never evaluate to a singleton failure guard. To state mailbox conformance, it is useful to define the notion of a *configuration context* $\mathcal{H} ::= (va)\mathcal{H} \mid \mathcal{H} \parallel C \mid (\llbracket _ \rrbracket, \Sigma)$, that allows us to focus on a single thread.

Corollary 1 (Mailbox Conformance). *If $\vdash \mathcal{P}$ and $\Delta \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} C$ with Δ reliable, then $C \not\longmapsto^* \mathcal{H}[\mathbf{fail} V]$.*

This corollary follows because, to evaluate **fail** V , we would need a mailbox with type $?0$ in the environment. This would contradict the premise that Δ is reliable.

3.4.3 Progress

To prove a progress result for Pat, we begin with some auxiliary definitions.

Definition 15 (Message set). *A message set \mathcal{M} is a configuration of the form: $a_1 \leftarrow \mathbf{m}_1(\vec{V}_1) \parallel \dots \parallel a_n \leftarrow \mathbf{m}_n(\vec{V}_n)$. We say that a message set \mathcal{M} contains a message \mathbf{m} for a if $\mathcal{M} \equiv a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(\vec{V}) \parallel \mathcal{M}'$ for some \mathcal{M}' .*

Next, we define *canonical forms*, which give us a global view of a configuration.

Definition 16 (Canonical form). *A configuration C is in canonical form if it is of the form:*

$$(va_1) \dots (va_l) (\llbracket M_1, \Sigma_1 \rrbracket \parallel \dots \parallel \llbracket M_m, \Sigma_m \rrbracket \parallel \mathcal{M})$$

Every process can be written in canonical form; the result follows from repeated application of the structural congruence rules. As a result we can reason about any arbitrary configuration by rewriting it in canonical form.

Proposition 1 (Canonical forms). *For every configuration C , there exists some \mathcal{D} such that $C \equiv \mathcal{D}$ and \mathcal{D} is in canonical form.*

We next need two definitions to characterise a thread that is blocked while waiting for a message to arrive.

1225 **Definition 17** (Waiting). We say that a term M is waiting on mailbox a if M can be written
 1226 **guard** $a \{ \vec{G} \}$ for some pattern E and guards \vec{G} .

1227 We say that a term M is waiting on mailbox a for a message with tag \mathbf{m} , written
 1228 **waiting**(M, a, \mathbf{m}), if M can be written **guard** $a \{ \mathcal{G}[\text{receive } \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \text{ from } y \mapsto N] \}$. We say
 1229 that M is a waiting term if there exists some a such that M is waiting on mailbox a .
 1230

1231 **Definition 18** (Guard Clauses). The guard clauses of a waiting term $M = \text{guard } V \{ \vec{G} \}$ are
 1232 the guards \vec{G} .
 1233

1234 With these definitions in hand, we can state the notion of progress enjoyed by Pat. Let
 1235 $\text{fv}(-)$ denote the set of free variables in a term M or frame stack Σ .

1236 We begin by showing functional reduction, i.e., that threads can always reduce up-to
 1237 communication and concurrency constructs.
 1238

1239 **Lemma 4** (Progress (Functional Reduction)). If $\Delta \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} (\!| M, \Sigma \!|)$, then either:

- 1240 • M is a value and $\Sigma = \epsilon$; or
- 1241 • there exists some M', Σ' such that $(\!| M, \Sigma \!|) \longrightarrow (\!| M', \Sigma' \!|)$; or
- 1242 • M is a communication and concurrency construct, i.e. **new**, or **spawn** M , or
 1243 $V ! \mathbf{m}(\vec{W})$, or **guard** $V \{ \vec{G} \}$.
 1244

1245 **PROOF.** By induction on the derivation of $\Delta \vdash (\!| M, \Sigma \!|)$ and inspection of the reduction
 1246 rules. □
 1247

1248 We can then use canonical forms to characterise a progress result: either a configuration
 1249 can reduce, or each constituent thread has either reduced to a value, or is waiting for a
 1250 message that has not yet been sent by a different thread.
 1251

1252 **Theorem 2** (Partial Progress). Suppose $\vdash \mathcal{P}$ and $\cdot \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} C$ where C is in canonical form:

$$1253 \quad C = (va_1) \cdots (va_l) (\!| M_1, \Sigma_1 \!|) \parallel \cdots \parallel (\!| M_m, \Sigma_m \!|) \parallel M$$

1254 Then either there exists some C' such that $C \longrightarrow C'$, or for each M_i , either:

- 1256 • M_i is a value and $\Sigma_i = \epsilon$; or
- 1257 • M_i is waiting on some mailbox a with guard clauses \vec{G} , and for all \mathbf{m}_j such that
 1258 **waiting**(M_i, a, \mathbf{m}_j), message set \mathcal{M} does not contain a message $a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}_j(V)$, and
 1259 $a \notin \text{fv}(\vec{G}_i) \cup \text{fv}(\Sigma_i)$.
 1260

1261 **PROOF.** Functional reduction enjoys progress (Lemma 4), and the constructs **new**,
 1262 **spawn** M , and $a ! \mathbf{m}(\vec{V})$ can all always reduce by E-NEW, E-SPAWN, or E-SEND. Therefore,
 1263 the body of an irreducible thread $(\!| M_k, \Sigma_k \!|)$ must be waiting; i.e., it must be of the form
 1264 $(\!| \text{guard } a \{ \vec{G} \}, \Sigma_k \!|)$ for some name a and guards \vec{G} .
 1265

1266 There are four cases to consider:

- 1267 (1) That there exists some \mathbf{m} such that **waiting**(M_k, a, \mathbf{m}) and there exists some sent
 1268 message $a \leftarrow \mathbf{m}(V)$ in the message set \mathcal{M} . In this case, we can reduce by E-RECV.
- 1269 (2) That there exist no messages for a in \mathcal{M} , and a does not occur free in \vec{G} , Σ_k , or any
 1270 other thread. In this case by T-NU, a must have some type J such that $?1 \leq J$ and as
 1271 such \vec{G} must include a **free** guard. In this case we can reduce by E-FREE.
- 1272 (3) That a occurs free in \vec{G} or Σ_k . This is impossible because the subject of a guard must
 1273 be returnable, and therefore by Lemma 2 cannot occur in the guards or frame stack.
 1274
 1275

1276 (4) That there exist no messages for a in \mathcal{M} but a occurs free in some other waiting
 1277 thread, indicating a cyclic inter-process dependency. This satisfies the second clause
 1278 of the theorem statement. \square
 1279

1280 A key consequence of Theorem 2 is *self-deadlock-freedom*: since we can only guard on a
 1281 returnable mailbox, and a returnable name must be the last occurrence in the thread, it cannot
 1282 be that the **guard** expression is blocking a send to the same mailbox in the same thread.

1283 As we cannot use dependency graphs (§2.2), our type system does not rule out inter-process
 1284 deadlocks. For example, the following (correct) processes encode a request-response pattern:
 1285

```

1286 def requester(self : ?Response, other : !Request): 1 {
1287   other !Request();
1288   guard self: Response {
1289     receive Response() from self  $\mapsto$  free self
1290   }
1291 }
1292
1293 def responder(self : ?Request, other : !Response): 1 {
1294   guard self: Request {
1295     receive Request() from self  $\mapsto$ 
1296       other !Response();
1297     free self
1298   }
1299 }
1300
1301 def main(): 1 {
1302   let mb1 = new in
1303   let mb2 = new in
1304   spawn requester(mb1, mb2);
1305   spawn responder(mb2, mb1)
1306 }

```

1307 However, if we were to modify the requester process to send the request only after receiving
 1308 the response, which would result in a deadlock, the program would still be accepted by our
 1309 type system because we do not have any static way of ruling out interprocess deadlocks:
 1310

```

1311 def badRequester(self : ?Response, other : !Request): 1 {
1312   guard self: Response {
1313     receive Response() from self  $\mapsto$ 
1314       other !Request();
1315     free self
1316   }
1317 }

```

1318 Although the mailbox calculus can rule out deadlocks using a dependency graph (de'Liguoro
 1319 and Padovani 2018), dependency graphs are difficult to integrate with the richer structure of
 1320 a programming language (see §2.2). We look forward to investigating inter-process deadlock
 1321 detection in future work.
 1322

1323 4 Algorithmic Typing

1324 Writing a typechecker based on Pat's declarative typing rules is challenging due to nondeter-
 1325 ministic context splits, environment subtyping, and pattern inclusion. MC^2 (Padovani 2018b)
 1326 is a typechecker for the mailbox calculus, based on a typechecker for concurrent object
 usage protocols (Padovani 2018c). The MC^2 type system has, however, not been formalised.
 We adopt several ideas from MC^2 , especially algorithmic type combination, and adapt the
 approach for a programming language.

1327	Pattern variables	α, β
1328	Mailbox patterns	$\gamma, \delta ::= \emptyset \mid \mathbb{1} \mid \mathbf{m} \mid \gamma \oplus \delta \mid \gamma \odot \delta \mid \gamma^* \mid \alpha$
1329	Mailbox types	$\varsigma ::= !\gamma \mid ?\gamma$
1330	Types	$\pi, \rho ::= C \mid \varsigma$
1331	Usage-annotated types	$\tau, \sigma ::= C \mid \varsigma''$
1332	Type environments	$\Theta ::= \cdot \mid \Theta, x : \tau$
1333	Nullable type environments	$\Psi ::= \Theta \mid \top$
1334	Constraints	$\phi ::= \gamma <: \delta$
1335	Constraint sets	Φ
1336		
1337	Open signatures	$\widehat{S} ::= \overrightarrow{\mathbf{m} \mapsto \vec{\tau}}$
1338	Annotated definitions	$\widehat{D} ::= \mathbf{def} f(\vec{x} : \vec{\tau}) : \sigma \{ \widehat{M} \}$
1339	Annotated programs	$\widehat{P} ::= (\widehat{S}, \vec{D}, \widehat{M})$
1340	Annotated computations	$\widehat{M}, \widehat{N} ::= V \mid \mathbf{let} x : T = \widehat{M} \mathbf{in} \widehat{N} \mid f(\vec{V})$
1341		$\mid \mathbf{spawn} \widehat{M} \mid \mathbf{new} \mid V ! \mathbf{m}(\vec{W}) \mid \mathbf{guard} V : E \{ \vec{G} \}$
1342	Annotated guards	$\widehat{G} ::= \mathbf{fail} \mid \mathbf{free} \mapsto \widehat{M} \mid \mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto \widehat{M}$
1343		
1344		
1345		
1346		
1347		
1348		
1349		

Fig. 7. Pat syntax extended for algorithmic typing

1350 *Type system overview.* Our algorithmic type system takes a *co-contextual* (Erdweg et al. 2015)
 1351 approach: rather than taking a type environment as an *input* to the type-checking algorithm,
 1352 we produce a type environment as an *output*. The intuition is that (read bottom-up), *splitting*
 1353 an environment into two sub-environments is more difficult than *merging* two environments
 1354 inferred from subexpressions. We also generate *inclusion constraints* on patterns to be solved
 1355 later.

1356 Bidirectional type systems (Dunfield and Krishnaswami 2022; Pierce and Turner 2000)
 1357 split typing rules into two classes: those that *synthesize* a type A for a term \widehat{M} ($\Gamma \vdash \widehat{M} \Rightarrow A$),
 1358 and those that *check* that a term \widehat{M} has type A ($\Gamma \vdash \widehat{M} \Leftarrow A$). Bidirectional type systems are
 1359 syntax-directed and amenable to implementation.

1361 We use a co-contextual variant of bidirectional typing first introduced by Zeilberger (2015).
 1362 The main twist is the variable rule, which becomes a *checking* rule and records the given
 1363 variable-type mapping in the inferred environment.

1365 4.1 Algorithmic Type System

1366 *Extended syntax and annotation.* A key difference in comparison to the declarative type
 1367 system is the addition of *pattern variables* α , which act as placeholders for parts of patterns
 1368 and are generated during typechecking. We can then generate and solve *inclusion constraints*
 1369 ϕ on patterns. Figure 7 shows the extended syntax used in the algorithmic system.

1371 The algorithmic type system requires annotations on **guard** expressions; we will discuss
 1372 the necessity of these annotations when describing the algorithmic typing rules. Annotated
 1373 computations \widehat{M}, \widehat{N} replace the **guard** $V \{ \vec{G} \}$ construct from the declarative system with a
 1374 **guard** $V : E \{ \vec{G} \}$ expression that involves guarding on mailbox V and asserting that it has
 1375 pattern E . Annotated guards \widehat{G} are modified to include annotated expressions in their bodies.
 1376
 1377

1378	Unrestrictedness	$\text{unr}(\tau) \triangleright \Phi$
1379		
1380	$\frac{}{\text{unr}(C) \triangleright \emptyset}$	$\frac{}{\text{unr}(!\gamma^n) \triangleright \{\mathbb{1} <: \gamma\}}$
1381	Subtyping	$\eta_1 \leq \eta_2 \quad \tau \leq \sigma \triangleright \Phi$
1382		
1383	$\frac{}{\eta \leq \eta} \quad \frac{}{\bullet \leq \circ} \quad \frac{}{C \leq C} \triangleright \emptyset$	$\frac{\eta_1 \leq \eta_2}{\varsigma^{\eta_1} \leq \varsigma^{\eta_2} \triangleright \emptyset} \quad \frac{\eta_1 \leq \eta_2}{!\gamma^{\eta_1} \leq !\delta^{\eta_2} \triangleright \delta <: \gamma} \quad \frac{\eta_1 \leq \eta_2}{?\gamma^{\eta_1} \leq ?\delta^{\eta_2} \triangleright \gamma <: \delta}$
1384		
1385	Sequential Merge	$\varsigma_1 \circ \varsigma_2 \triangleright \varsigma; \Phi \quad \tau_1 \circ \tau_2 \triangleright \sigma; \Phi$
1386		
1387	$\frac{}{!\gamma \circ !\delta \triangleright !(\gamma \odot \delta); \emptyset}$	$\frac{\alpha \text{ fresh}}{!\gamma \circ ?\delta \triangleright ?\alpha; \{(\gamma \odot \alpha) <: \delta\}}$
1388		$\frac{\alpha \text{ fresh}}{?\gamma \circ !\delta \triangleright ?\alpha; \{(\gamma \odot \alpha) <: \gamma\}}$
1389		
1390	$\frac{\varsigma_1 \circ \varsigma_2 \triangleright \varsigma; \Phi}{\varsigma_1^{\eta_1} \circ \varsigma_2^{\eta_2} \triangleright \varsigma^{\eta_1 \vee \eta_2}; \Phi}$	$\frac{}{C \circ C \triangleright C; \emptyset}$
1391		
1392	Branching merge	$\varsigma_1 \sqcap \varsigma_2 \triangleright \varsigma; \Phi \quad \tau_1 \sqcap \tau_2 \triangleright \sigma; \Phi$
1393		
1394	$\frac{}{!\gamma \sqcap !\delta \triangleright !(\gamma \oplus \delta); \emptyset}$	$\frac{\alpha \text{ fresh}}{?\gamma \sqcap ?\delta \triangleright ?\alpha; \{\alpha <: \gamma, \alpha <: \delta\}}$
1395		$\frac{\varsigma_1 \sqcap \varsigma_2 \triangleright \varsigma; \Phi}{\varsigma_1^{\eta_1} \sqcap \varsigma_2^{\eta_2} \triangleright \varsigma^{\min(\eta_1, \eta_2)}; \Phi}$
1396		
1397	$\frac{}{C \sqcap C \triangleright C; \emptyset}$	
1398		
1399		

Fig. 8. Pat algorithmic type operations

We also introduce *open signatures* $\widehat{\mathcal{S}}$ that allow message payload types to contain pattern variables; *annotated definitions* $\widehat{\mathcal{D}}$ that allow function arguments and return types to contain pattern variables and where the function body is an annotated computation; and extend a program to include an open signature, annotated definitions, and an annotated body.

Constraints. An important challenge for the algorithmic type system is determining whether one pattern is *included* within another: e.g. $\mathbf{m} \sqsubseteq \mathbf{m}^*$. Given that patterns may contain pattern variables, we may need to defer inclusion checking until more pattern variables are known, so we introduce inclusion constraints $\gamma <: \delta$ which require that pattern γ is included in pattern δ .

Fig. 8 shows the algorithmic type operators.

Unrestrictedness and subtyping. The algorithmic unrestrictedness operation $\text{unr}(\tau) \triangleright \Phi$ states that τ is unrestricted subject to constraints Φ , and the definition reflects the fact that a type is unrestricted in the declarative system if it is a base type or a subtype of $!\mathbb{1}^\circ$. Algorithmic subtyping is similar: a base type is a subtype of itself, and we check that two mailbox types with the same capability are subtypes of each other by generating a contravariant constraint for a send type, and a covariant constraint for a receive type.

Algorithmic sequential merge. Declarative mailbox typing relies on the subtyping rule to manipulate types into a form where they can be combined with the type combination operators, e.g., $!E \boxplus ?(E \odot F) = ?F$. The algorithmic type system cannot apply the same technique as it does not know, *a priori*, the form of each pattern. Instead, the *algorithmic sequential merge* operation allows the combination of two mailbox types irrespective of their syntactic form. Combining two send types is the same as in the declarative system, but combining a send type with a receive type (and vice versa) is more interesting: say we wish to combine $!\gamma$

1429 **Environment sequential merge** $\Theta_1 \circlearrowleft \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$

1430
$$\frac{}{\cdot \circlearrowleft \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta_2) \quad \Theta_1 \circlearrowleft \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}{\Theta_1, x:\tau \circlearrowleft \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta, x:\tau; \Phi} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta_1) \quad \Theta_1 \circlearrowleft \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}{\Theta_1 \circlearrowleft \Theta_2, x:\tau \triangleright \Theta, x:\tau; \Phi}$$

1431

1432

1433

1434
$$\frac{\tau_1 \circlearrowleft \tau_2 \triangleright \sigma; \Phi_1 \quad \Theta_1 \circlearrowleft \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_2}{\Theta_1, x:\tau_1 \circlearrowleft \Theta_2, x:\tau_2 \triangleright \Theta, x:\sigma; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2}$$

1435

1436 **Environment branching merge** $\Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$

1437

1438
$$\frac{}{\cdot \sqcap \cdot \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta_2) \quad \Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}{\Theta_1, x:C \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta, x:C; \Phi} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta_2) \quad \Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}{\Theta_1, x:!\gamma^n \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta, x:!(\gamma \oplus \mathbb{1})^n; \Phi}$$

1439

1440

1441
$$\frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta_1) \quad \Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_2}{\Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2, x:C \triangleright \Theta, x:\tau; \Phi} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta_1) \quad \Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_2}{\Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2, x:!\gamma^n \triangleright \Theta, x:!(\gamma \oplus \mathbb{1})^n; \Phi}$$

1442

1443

1444
$$\frac{\tau_1 \sqcap \tau_2 \triangleright \sigma; \Phi_1 \quad \Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_2}{\Theta_1, x:\tau_1 \sqcap \Theta_2, x:\tau_2 \triangleright \Theta, x:\sigma; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2}$$

1445

1446

1447 **Disjoint combination** $\Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$

1448

1449
$$\frac{}{\cdot + \cdot \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta_2) \quad \Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}{\Theta_1, x:\tau + \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta, x:\tau; \Phi} \quad \frac{x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta_1) \quad \Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}{\Theta_1 + \Theta_2, x:\tau \triangleright \Theta, x:\tau; \Phi} \quad \frac{\Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}{\Theta_1, x:C + \Theta_2, x:C \triangleright \Theta, x:C; \Phi}$$

1450

1451

Fig. 9. Algorithmic environment combination

1452 and δ . In this case, we generate a fresh pattern variable α ; the result is $?\alpha$ along with the constraint that $(\gamma \odot \alpha) <: \delta$: namely, that the send pattern composed with the fresh pattern variable is included in the pattern δ .

1453 As an example, applying the sequential merge to types $!\mathbf{m}$ and $?(n \odot \mathbf{m})$ produces an input mailbox type $?\alpha$ and a constraint $(\mathbf{m} \odot \alpha) <: (n \odot \mathbf{m})$, for which a valid solution is $\alpha \mapsto \mathbf{n}$, and hence the expected combined type $?\mathbf{n}$.

1454 *Algorithmic branching merge.* In the declarative type system branching control flow requires that each branch is typable under the same type environment (using the T-SUB rule). The algorithmic type system instead generates constraints that ensure that each type is used consistently across branches using the *algorithmic branching merge* operation $\tau_1 \sqcap \tau_2 \triangleright \sigma; \Phi$. Two base types are merged if they are identical. In the case of mailbox types, the function takes the minimum (or *least permissive*) usage annotation, i.e., $\min(\bullet, \circ) = \bullet$. It ensures that when merging two output capabilities the patterns are combined using pattern disjunction. Conversely merging two input capabilities generates a new pattern variable that must be included in both merged patterns.

1455 *Algorithmic environment combination.* Figure 9 shows how the algorithmic type combination operators can be extended to type environments.

1456 The environment sequential merge operator $\Theta_1 \circlearrowleft \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$ concatenates Θ_1 and Θ_2 , computing the sequential merge of any types for overlapping variables, and produces constraints Φ . The environment branching merge operator $\Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$ computes the

algorithmic branching merge of Θ_1 and Θ_2 . In the case that a variable is contained in both environments, then the merged type is used in the output environment. If the variable is only contained in one of the environments, then the result depends on the type. If the variable is only contained in one of the environments and has type $!\gamma^n$, then its type is changed to $!(\gamma \oplus \mathbb{1})^n$ to denote the fact that it may not be used. Note that this only applies to mailbox types with an *output* capability since mailbox types with an *input* capability must be treated linearly.

Disjoint environment combination combines two environments; if a variable is used in both environments then it must have an identical base type.

Nullable type environments. Checking a **fail** guard produces a *null* environment \top which can be composed with *any other* type environment, as shown by the following definition:

Definition 19 (Nullable environment combination). *For each combination operator $\star \in \{\circ, \sqcap, +\}$ we extend environment combination to nullable type environments, $\Psi_1 \star \Psi_2 \triangleright \Psi$; Φ by extending each environment combination operation with the following rules:*

$$\frac{}{\top \star \top \triangleright \top; \emptyset} \qquad \frac{}{\top \star \Theta \triangleright \Theta; \emptyset} \qquad \frac{}{\Theta \star \top \triangleright \Theta; \emptyset}$$

The null type environment is a supertype of every defined type environment: $\Theta \leq \top$.

Figure 10 shows the Pat algorithmic typing of programs, definitions and terms. The key idea is to remain in checking mode for as long as possible, in order to propagate type information to the variable rule and construct a type environment. We write $\Theta - \vec{x}$ for $\{y : \tau \mid y : \tau \in \Theta \wedge y \notin \vec{x}\}$.

Synthesis. Our synthesis judgement has the form $\widehat{M} \Rightarrow_{\mathcal{P}} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$, which can be read “synthesise type τ for term \widehat{M} under program \mathcal{P} , producing type environment Θ and constraints Φ ”. Here, \widehat{M} and \mathcal{P} are inputs of the judgement, whereas τ , Θ , and Φ are outputs. The checking judgement $\widehat{M} \Leftarrow_{\mathcal{P}} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$ can be read “check that term \widehat{M} has type τ under program \mathcal{P} , producing type environment Θ and constraints Φ ”. Here, \widehat{M} , \mathcal{P} , and τ are inputs of the judgement, whereas Θ and Φ are outputs. As in the declarative system we omit the \mathcal{P} annotation in the rules for readability.

Rule TS-CONST assigns a known base type to a constant, and rule TS-NEW synthesises a type $?1^\circ$ (analogous to T-NEW); both rules produce an empty environment and constraint set. Rule TS-SPAWN checks that the given computation M has the unit type, synthesises type $\mathbf{1}$, and infers a type environment Θ and constraint set Φ . Like T-SPAWN in the declarative system, the usability annotations are masked as usable since usability restrictions are process-local.

Message sending $V ! \mathbf{m}(\vec{W})$ is a side-effecting operation, and so we synthesise type $\mathbf{1}$. Rule TS-SEND first looks up the payload types $\vec{\pi}$ in the signature, and *checks* that message target V has mailbox type $!\mathbf{m}^\circ$. In performing this check, the type system will produce environment Θ' that contains an entry mapping the variable in V to the desired mailbox type $!\mathbf{m}^\circ$. Next, the algorithm checks each payload value against the payload type described by the signature. The resulting environment is the algorithmic disjoint combination of the environments produced by checking each payload, and the resulting constraint set is the union of all generated constraints.

Function application is similar: rule TS-APP looks up the type signature for function f and checks that all arguments have the expected types. The resulting environment is again the

1531	Constraint generation for programs and definitions	$\vdash \widehat{\mathcal{P}} \triangleright \Phi$	$\vdash_{\widehat{\rho}} \widehat{D} \triangleright \Phi$
1532			
1533	$\widehat{\mathcal{P}} = (\widehat{S}, \vec{\widehat{D}}, \widehat{M})$	$\widehat{M} \leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1$	
1534	$(\vdash_{\widehat{\rho}} \widehat{D}_i \triangleright \Phi_i)_{i \in 1..n} \quad \widehat{M} \leftarrow \mathbf{1} \triangleright \cdot; \Phi$	$\text{check}(\Theta, \vec{x}, \vec{\tau}) = \Phi_2 \quad \Theta - \vec{x} = \cdot$	
1535	$\frac{}{\vdash \widehat{\mathcal{P}} \triangleright \Phi \cup \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_n}$	$\frac{}{\vdash \mathbf{def} f(\vec{x} : \vec{\tau}) : \sigma \{ \widehat{M} \} \triangleright \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2}$	
1536			
1537	Constraint generation (synthesis)		$\widehat{M} \Rightarrow_{\widehat{\rho}} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$
1538			
1539	TS-CONST c has base type C	TS-NEW	TS-SPAWN $\widehat{M} \leftarrow \mathbf{1} \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$
1540	$\frac{}{c \Rightarrow C \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset}$	$\frac{}{\mathbf{new} \Rightarrow ?\mathbb{1}^* \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset}$	$\frac{}{\mathbf{spawn} \widehat{M} \Rightarrow \mathbf{1} \triangleright [\Theta]; \Phi}$
1541			
1542	TS-SEND		
1543		$\widehat{\mathcal{P}}(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{\pi}$	
1544	$V \leftarrow !\mathbf{m}^\circ \triangleright \Theta'; \Phi$	$(W_i \leftarrow [\pi_i] \triangleright \Theta'_i; \Phi'_i)_{i \in 1..n}$	$\Theta' + \Theta'_1 + \dots + \Theta'_n \triangleright \Theta; \Phi''$
1545	$\frac{}{V !\mathbf{m}(\vec{W}) \Rightarrow \mathbf{1} \triangleright \Theta; \Phi \cup \Phi'_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi'_n \cup \Phi''}$		
1546			
1547	TS-APP		
1548	$\widehat{\mathcal{P}}(f) = \mathbf{def} f(\vec{x} : \vec{\tau}) : \sigma \{ \widehat{M} \}$	$(V_i \leftarrow \tau_i \triangleright \Theta_i; \Phi_i)_{i \in 1..n}$	$\Theta_1 + \dots + \Theta_n \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$
1549	$\frac{}{f(V_1, \dots, V_n) \Rightarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi \cup \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_n}$		
1550			
1551	Constraint generation (checking)		$\widehat{M} \leftarrow_{\widehat{\rho}} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$
1552			
1553		TC-LET	
1554	TC-VAR	$\widehat{M} \leftarrow [T] \triangleright \Theta_1; \Phi_1$	$\widehat{N} \leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta_2; \Phi_2$
1555		$\text{check}(\Theta_2, x, [T]) = \Phi_3$	$\Theta_1 \wp \Theta_2 - x \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_4$
1556	$\frac{}{x \leftarrow \tau \triangleright x : \tau; \emptyset}$	$\frac{}{\mathbf{let} x : T = \widehat{M} \mathbf{in} \widehat{N} \leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_4}$	
1557			
1558	TC-GUARD		
1559	$\{E\} \vec{G} \leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Psi; \Phi_1; F$	TC-SUB	
1560	$V \leftarrow ?F^\bullet \triangleright \Theta'; \Phi_2 \quad \Psi + \Theta' \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_3$	$\widehat{M} \Rightarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1$	$\tau \leq \sigma \triangleright \Phi_2$
1561	$\frac{}{\mathbf{guard} V : E \{ \vec{G} \} \leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2 \cup \Phi_3 \cup \{E <: F\}}$		$\frac{}{\widehat{M} \leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2}$
1562	Environment lookup	$\text{check}(\Theta, x, \tau) = \Phi$	$\text{check}(\Theta, \vec{x}, \vec{\tau}) = \Phi$
1563			
1564	$x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta) \quad \text{unr}(\tau) \triangleright \Phi$	$\sigma \leq \tau \triangleright \Phi$	$(\text{check}(\Theta, x_i, \tau_i) = \Phi_i)_{i \in 1..n}$
1565	$\frac{}{\text{check}(\Theta, x, \tau) = \Phi} \quad \frac{}{\text{check}((\Theta, x : \tau), x, \sigma) = \Phi} \quad \frac{}{\text{check}(\Theta, \vec{x}, \vec{\tau}) = \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_n}$		
1566			

Fig. 10. Pat algorithmic typing (programs, definitions, and terms)

disjoint combination of the environments, and the constraint set is the union of all generated constraints.

Checking. Rule TC-VAR checks that a variable x has type τ , producing a type environment $x : \tau$. The TC-LET rule checks that a let-binding $\mathbf{let} x : T = \widehat{M} \mathbf{in} \widehat{N}$ has type τ : first, we check that \widehat{M} has type $[T]$ noting that only values of returnable type may be returned, producing environment Θ_1 and constraints Φ_1 . Next we check that the body \widehat{N} has type τ , producing environment Θ_2 and Φ_2 . The next step is to check whether the types of the variable inferred in Θ_2 corresponds with the annotation. The check meta-function ensures that if x is not contained within Θ_2 , then the type of x is unrestricted; and conversely if x is contained within

1582 Θ_2 , then the annotation is a subtype of the inferred type as the annotation is a *lower bound* on
 1583 what the body can expect of x .

1584 Rule TC-GUARD checks that a guard expression **guard** $V : E \{\vec{G}\}$ has return type τ . First,
 1585 the rule checks that the guard sequence \vec{G} has type τ , producing nullable environment Ψ ,
 1586 constraint set Φ_1 , and pattern F in pattern normal form (recall that a pattern E is in pattern
 1587 normal form if it is a sum of \emptyset , $\mathbb{1}$, or $\mathbf{m} \odot F$ patterns, where F is equivalent to the pattern
 1588 residual of E with respect to \mathbf{m}). Next, the rule checks that the mailbox name V has type
 1589 $?F^\bullet$, producing environment Θ' and constraint set Φ_2 . Finally, the rule calculates the disjoint
 1590 combination of Ψ and Θ' , producing final environment Θ and constraints Φ_3 .

1591 Finally, rule TC-SUB states that if a term \widehat{M} is synthesisable with type τ , where τ is a
 1592 subtype of σ , then \widehat{M} is checkable with type σ . The resulting environment is that produced
 1593 by synthesising the type for \widehat{M} , and the resulting constraint set is the union of the synthesis
 1594 and subtyping constraints.
 1595
 1596

1597 *Un-annotated let expressions.* Although our core calculus assumes an annotation on **let**
 1598 expressions, this is unnecessary if the let-bound variable is used in the continuation \widehat{N} , or \widehat{M}
 1599 has a synthesisable type. Specifically, TC-LETNOANN1 allows us to check the type of the
 1600 continuation and inspect the produced environment for the type of x , which can be used to
 1601 check \widehat{M} . Similarly, TC-LETNOANN2 allows us to type a **let**-binding where x is *not* used in
 1602 the continuation, as long as the type of \widehat{M} is synthesisable and unrestricted.
 1603
 1604

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{TC-LETNOANN1} \\
 \frac{\widehat{N} \leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta_1, x : \tau; \Phi_1 \quad \widehat{M} \leftarrow [\tau] \triangleright \Theta_2; \Phi_2 \quad \Theta_2 \wp \Theta_1 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_3}{\text{let } x = \widehat{M} \text{ in } \widehat{N} \leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2 \cup \Phi_3} \\
 \\
 \text{TC-LETNOANN2} \\
 \frac{\widehat{N} \leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta_1; \Phi_1 \quad x \notin \text{dom}(\Theta_1) \quad \widehat{M} \Rightarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta_2; \Phi_2 \quad \text{returnable}(\tau) \quad \text{unr}(\tau) \triangleright \Phi_3 \quad \Theta_2 \wp \Theta_1 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_4}{\text{let } x = \widehat{M} \text{ in } \widehat{N} \leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_4}
 \end{array}$$

1605 We use the explicitly-typed representation in the core language for simplicity and uniformity;
 1606 however, the implementation follows the above approach to avoid needless annotations.
 1607

1608 *Guards.* Figure 11 shows the typing rules for guards; the judgement $\{E\} \widehat{G} \leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Psi; \Phi; F$
 1609 can be read “Check that guard \widehat{G} has type τ , producing environment Ψ , constraints Φ , and
 1610 closed pattern literal F in pattern normal form with respect to E ”. Rule TCG-GUARDS types
 1611 a guard sequence, producing the algorithmic merge of all environments and the sum of all
 1612 produced patterns. Rule TCG-FAIL types the **fail** guard with any type and produces a null
 1613 type environment, empty constraint set, and pattern \emptyset . Rule TCG-FREE checks that guard
 1614 **free** $\mapsto \widehat{M}$ has type τ by checking that \widehat{M} has type τ ; the guard produces pattern $\mathbb{1}$.

1615 Finally, rule TCG-RECV checks that a receive guard **receive** $\mathbf{m}(\vec{x})$ **from** $y \mapsto \widehat{M}$ has type
 1616 τ . First, the rule checks that \widehat{M} has type τ , producing environment Θ' , $y : ?\gamma^\bullet$ and constraint
 1617 set Φ_1 ; since a mailbox type with input capability is linear, it *must* be present in the inferred
 1618 environment. Next, the rule checks that the inferred types for \vec{x} in Θ' are compatible with the
 1619 payloads for \mathbf{m} declared in the signature, producing constraint set Φ_2 . As with the declarative
 1620 rule, to rule out unsafe aliasing either the payloads or inferred environment must consist only
 1621 of base types. The resulting environment is Θ (i.e., the inferred environment without the
 1622
 1623
 1624
 1625
 1626
 1627
 1628
 1629
 1630
 1631
 1632

1633 **Constraint generation for guards**

$$\boxed{\{E\} \vec{G} \Leftarrow_{\rho} \tau \triangleright \Psi; \Phi; F} \quad \boxed{\{E\} \widehat{G} \Leftarrow_{\rho} \tau \triangleright \Psi; \Phi; F}$$

$$\frac{\text{TCG-GUARDS} \quad (\{E\} \widehat{G}_i \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Psi_i; \Phi_i; F_i)_{i \in 1..n} \quad F = F_1 \oplus \dots \oplus F_n \quad \Psi_1 \sqcap \dots \sqcap \Psi_n \triangleright \Psi; \Phi}{\{E\} \vec{G} \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Psi; \Phi \cup \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_n; F}$$

$$\frac{\text{TCG-FAIL}}{\{E\} \mathbf{fail} \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \top; \emptyset; \emptyset} \quad \frac{\text{TCG-FREE} \quad \widehat{M} \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}{\{E\} \mathbf{free} \mapsto \widehat{M} \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi; \perp}$$

$$\frac{\text{TCG-RECV} \quad \widehat{M} \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta', y : ?\gamma^*; \Phi_1 \quad \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{\pi} \quad \Theta = \Theta' - \vec{x} \quad \text{base}(\vec{\pi}) \vee \text{base}(\Theta) \quad \text{check}(\Theta', \vec{x}, [\vec{\pi}]) = \Phi_2}{\{E\} \mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto \widehat{M} \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2 \cup \{E / \mathbf{m} <: \gamma\}; \mathbf{m} \odot (E / \mathbf{m})}$$

1634 Fig. 11. Pat algorithmic typing (guards)

1635 mailbox variable or any payloads). The resulting constraint set is the union of Φ_1 and Φ_2
 1636 along with an additional constraint which ensures that E / \mathbf{m} is included in γ , allowing us to
 1637 produce the closed PNF literal $\mathbf{m} \odot (E / \mathbf{m})$.

1638 4.2 Metatheory

1639 We can now establish that the algorithmic type system is sound and complete with respect to
 1640 the declarative type system. We begin by introducing the notion of pattern substitutions and
 1641 solutions.

1642 A *pattern substitution* Ξ is a mapping from type variables α to (fully-defined) patterns E ;
 1643 applying Ξ to a pattern γ substitutes all occurrences of a type variable α for $\Xi(\alpha)$. We extend
 1644 application of pattern substitutions to types and environments. We write $\text{pv}(E)$ for the set of
 1645 pattern variables in a pattern and extend it to types and environments.

1646 **Definition 20** (Pattern solution). *A pattern substitution Ξ is a pattern solution for a constraint*
 1647 *set Φ (or solves Φ) if $\text{pv}(\Phi) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Xi)$ and for each $\gamma <: \delta \in \Phi$, we have that $\Xi(\gamma) \sqsubseteq \Xi(\delta)$.*
 1648 *A solution Ξ is a usable solution if its range does not contain any pattern equivalent to \emptyset .*

1649 It is useful to define the notion of a *covering solution* to characterise a solution that resolves
 1650 all pattern variables present in an algorithmic typing derivation.

1651 **Definition 21** (Covering solution). *We say that a pattern substitution Ξ is a covering solution*
 1652 *for a derivation $\widehat{M} \Rightarrow_{\rho} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$ or $\widehat{M} \Leftarrow_{\rho} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$ if given $\vdash \mathcal{P} \triangleright \Phi'$, it is the case that*
 1653 *Ξ is a usable solution for $\Phi \cup \Phi'$ such that $\text{pv}(\tau) \cup \text{pv}(\mathcal{P}) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Xi)$.*

1654 4.2.1 Algorithmic Soundness

1655 If a term is well typed in the algorithmic system then, given a covering solution, the term is also
 1656 well typed in the declarative system. Proving this result involves establishing several auxiliary
 1657 results on the soundness of the various type operators and type combination operators. Full
 1658 proof details can be found in the extended version.

1684 *Properties of pattern variables and solutions.* The first auxiliary result states that a solution
 1685 for a set of constraints is also a solution for a subset of those constraints.

1686 **Lemma 5.** *If Ξ is a solution for a constraint set $\Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2$, then Ξ is a solution for Φ_1 .*
 1687

1688 **PROOF.** Since Ξ is a solution for $\Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2$, it follows that $\text{dom}(\Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Xi)$. The
 1689 result follows from the fact that $\text{dom}(\Phi_1) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Xi)$. \square
 1690

1691 We also need to reason about the provenance of pattern variables that appear in an inferred
 1692 environment. Specifically, any pattern variable that appears in an inferred environment must
 1693 either occur in the type of an expression, in the program, or in the constraint set.

1694 **Lemma 6.** *If $\widehat{M} \Rightarrow_{\widehat{P}} \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta$; Φ or $\widehat{M} \Leftarrow_{\widehat{P}} \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta$; Φ , then $\text{pv}(\Theta) \subseteq \text{pv}(\tau) \cup \text{pv}(\widehat{P}) \cup \text{pv}(\Phi)$.*
 1695

1696 **PROOF.** By mutual induction on the two derivations, noting that whenever a pattern variable
 1697 is introduced fresh, it is always added to the constraint set. \square
 1698

1699 *Properties of type operations.* Next, we need to show the relation between algorithmic and
 1700 declarative versions of the various type operations. Given a usable solution of a constraint
 1701 set, we can show the soundness of algorithmic subtyping.
 1702

1703 **Lemma 7.** *If $\tau \leq \sigma \blacktriangleright \Phi$ and Ξ is a usable solution of Φ with $\text{pv}(\tau) \cup \text{pv}(\sigma) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Xi)$,
 1704 then $\Xi(\tau) \leq \Xi(\sigma)$.*

1705 **PROOF.** By case analysis on the derivation of $\tau \leq \sigma \blacktriangleright \Phi$. Base types are trivial, and the
 1706 property follows for mailbox types from the definition of a usable solution. \square
 1707

1708 We can also show the soundness of the algorithmic unrestrictedness operation.
 1709

1710 **Lemma 8.** *If $\text{unr}(\tau) \blacktriangleright \Phi$ and Ξ is a usable solution of Φ with $\text{pv}(\tau) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Xi)$, then there
 1711 exists some A such that $\text{un}(A)$ and $\Xi(\tau) \leq A$.*

1712 **PROOF.** By case analysis on the derivation of $\text{unr}(\tau) \blacktriangleright \Phi$, noting that cases are undefined
 1713 for linear types, and that the result follows immediately for base types. The only interesting
 1714 case is $\text{unr}(!\gamma^n) \blacktriangleright \mathbb{1} <: \gamma$; since Ξ is a usable solution, we have that $\mathbb{1} \sqsubseteq \llbracket \Xi(\gamma) \rrbracket$. Since $\bullet \leq \circ$
 1715 we can therefore show that $!(\Xi(\gamma))^n \leq !\mathbb{1}^\circ$ where $\text{un}(!\mathbb{1}^\circ)$ as required. \square
 1716

1717 *Properties of type combination operations.* Finally we need to show the soundness of the
 1718 merge operators; in both cases this follows by case analysis on the respective derivations.
 1719

1720 **Lemma 9** (Soundness of algorithmic sequential merge). *If $\tau_1 \circ \tau_2 \blacktriangleright \sigma$; Φ and Ξ is a usable
 1721 solution of Φ such that $\text{pv}(\tau_1) \cup \text{pv}(\tau_2) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Xi)$, then there exist $\tau'_1 \leq \Xi(\tau_1)$, $\tau'_2 \leq \Xi(\tau_2)$
 1722 where $\tau'_1 \blacktriangleright \tau'_2 = \Xi(\sigma)$.*
 1723

1724 **Lemma 10** (Soundness of algorithmic branching merge). *If $\tau_1 \sqcap \tau_2 \blacktriangleright \sigma$; Φ and Ξ is a usable
 1725 solution of Φ such that $\text{pv}(\tau_1) \cup \text{pv}(\tau_2) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Xi)$, then $\Xi(\sigma) \leq \Xi(\tau_1)$ and $\Xi(\sigma) \leq \Xi(\tau_2)$.*
 1726

1727 To relate annotated terms with unannotated terms in the declarative system, we define an
 1728 erasure operator $\text{erase}(\widehat{M}) = M$ on annotated computations that removes annotations on
 1729 guard expressions. The erasure operator is defined by the homomorphic extension of the
 1730 following rule over computations and guards:
 1731

$$1732 \text{erase}(\mathbf{guard} V : E \{\widehat{G}\}) = \mathbf{guard} V \{\widehat{\text{erase}(\widehat{G})}\}$$

1733
 1734

We also extend the erasure operator to definitions and programs:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{erase}(\mathbf{def} f(\vec{\tau}): \sigma \{\widehat{M}\}) &= \mathbf{def} f(\vec{\tau}): \sigma \{\text{erase}(\widehat{M})\} \\ \text{erase}((\widehat{S}, \vec{D}, \widehat{M})) &= (\widehat{S}, \text{erase}(\vec{D}), \text{erase}(\widehat{M})) \end{aligned}$$

With these auxiliary results defined, we can show that the algorithmic type system is sound with respect to the declarative type system, meaning that our algorithmic type system will never accept ill-typed terms.

Theorem 3 (Algorithmic Soundness).

- If Ξ is a covering solution for $\widehat{M} \Rightarrow_{\widehat{\rho}} \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi$, then $\Xi(\Theta) \vdash_{\text{erase}(\Xi(\widehat{\rho}))} \text{erase}(\widehat{M}) : \Xi(\tau)$.
- If Ξ is a covering solution for $\widehat{M} \Leftarrow_{\widehat{\rho}} \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi$, then $\Xi(\Theta) \vdash_{\text{erase}(\Xi(\widehat{\rho}))} \text{erase}(\widehat{M}) : \Xi(\tau)$.

The result follows from a more generalised version of algorithmic soundness on all of the typing judgements (for values, computations, guards, and guard sequences), which is established by mutual induction.

4.2.2 Algorithmic Completeness

We also obtain a completeness result, but only for the checking direction. This is because the type system *requires* type information to construct a type environment. In practice the lack of a completeness result for synthesis is unproblematic since all functions have return type annotations, and therefore the only terms typable in the declarative system but unsynthesisable are top-level terms containing free variables. Recall that by the definition in §3, program \mathcal{P} is *closed*, i.e., no definitions or message payloads contain type variables.

Again, the proof of algorithmic completeness requires several auxiliary lemmas. Full proofs can be found in the extended version.

Closed and satisfiable constraint sets. We firstly define *closed* and *satisfiable* constraint sets.

Definition 22 (Closed and satisfiable constraint sets). *A constraint set Φ is closed if $\rho\nu(\Phi) = \emptyset$. A closed constraint set Φ is satisfiable if the empty solution is a solution for Φ (i.e., $\Phi = (E_i <: F_i)_{i \in 1..n}$ and $(E_i \sqsubseteq F_i)_{i \in 1..n}$).*

Checkability of values and synthesisable terms. Values are checkable, without creating any additional constraints.

Lemma 11. *If $\Gamma \vdash V : A$, then there exists some Γ' such that $\Gamma \leq \Gamma'$ and $V \Leftarrow A \blacktriangleright \Gamma'; \emptyset$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $\Gamma \vdash V : A$. T-VAR and T-CONST follow immediately, and T-SUB follows from the IH and the transitivity of subtyping. \square

Next, any synthesisable term is checkable with the same type, without needing to introduce any additional constraints.

Lemma 12. *If $\widehat{M} \Rightarrow \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi$, then $\widehat{M} \Leftarrow \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi$.*

PROOF. Follows from the definition of TC-SUB, noting that the subtyping constraint is instantiated as $\tau \leq \tau \blacktriangleright \emptyset$. \square

1786 *Properties of type operations.* When proving completeness of the algorithmic type system
 1787 with respect to T-SUB, it is useful to consider two properties of the subtyping operations.

1788 First, algorithmic subtyping on closed types is transitive.

1789
 1790 **Lemma 13** (Transitivity of algorithmic subtyping). *If $A \leq A' \triangleright \Phi$ where Φ is satisfiable,*
 1791 *and $A' \leq B$, then $A \leq B \triangleright \Phi'$ and Φ' is satisfiable.*

1792 **PROOF.** By case analysis on the derivation of $A \leq A' \triangleright \Phi$ and the transitivity of pattern
 1793 inclusion. □

1795 Second, it is useful to show that if a term is checkable at some type A , then it is also
 1796 checkable at some supertype B .

1797
 1798 **Lemma 14** (Checkability at a supertype). *If $\widehat{M} \leftarrow_{\mathcal{P}} A \triangleright \Theta; \Phi$ where Ξ is a usable solution*
 1799 *of Φ , and $A \leq B$, then there exist Θ', Φ' such that $\widehat{M} \leftarrow_{\mathcal{P}} B \triangleright \Theta'; \Phi'$ where Ξ is a usable*
 1800 *solution of Φ' and $\Xi(\Theta) \preceq \Xi(\Theta')$.*

1801
 1802 **PROOF.** Follows from a more generalised result that proceeds by mutual induction, making
 1803 essential use of Lemma 13. □

1805 Next, we need to show the completeness of the check meta-function, which arises as a
 1806 direct corollary of the completeness of subtyping. The completeness of subtyping follows by
 1807 cases analysis on the derivation of $\Xi(\tau) \leq \Xi(\sigma)$ and the definition of pattern inclusion.

1808
 1809 **Lemma 15** (Completeness of subtyping). *Given a pattern substitution Ξ such that $\Xi(\tau) \leq$*
 1810 *$\Xi(\sigma)$, then $\tau \leq \sigma \triangleright \Phi$ and Ξ is a usable solution of Φ .*

1811
 1812 **Corollary 2** (Completeness of check meta-function). *Given a pattern substitution Ξ such*
 1813 *that $\Xi(\Theta, x : \tau) \preceq \Xi(\Theta')$ then $\text{check}(\Theta', x, \tau) = \Phi$ and Ξ is a usable solution of Φ .*

1814
 1815 *Properties of type combination operations.* The final set of lemmas concentrate on the
 1816 completeness of the type combination operators. Both proofs follow by case analysis on the
 1817 respective declarative derivations and appeal to the underlying pattern semantics.

1818
 1819 **Lemma 16** (Completeness of algorithmic sequential merge). *If $A_1 \triangleright A_2 = B$ where $A_1 \leq$*
 1820 *$\Xi_1(\tau_1)$ and $A_2 \leq \Xi_2(\tau_2)$ for pattern substitutions Ξ_1, Ξ_2 such that $\text{pv}(\Xi_1) \cap \text{pv}(\Xi_2) = \emptyset$, then*
 1821 *there exist σ, Φ such that $\tau_1 \wp \tau_2 \triangleright \sigma; \Phi$, and there exists a usable solution $\Xi \supseteq \Xi_1 \cup \Xi_2$ of*
 1822 *Φ such that $B \leq \Xi(\sigma)$.*

1823
 1824 **Lemma 17** (Completeness of algorithmic branching merge). *If $A \leq \Xi_1(\tau_1)$ and $A \leq \Xi_2(\tau_2)$*
 1825 *for pattern substitutions Ξ_1, Ξ_2 such that $\text{pv}(\Xi_1) \cap \text{pv}(\Xi_2) = \emptyset$, then there exist σ, Φ such*
 1826 *that $\tau_1 \sqcap \tau_2 \triangleright \sigma; \Phi$ and there exists a usable solution $\Xi \supseteq \Xi_1 \cup \Xi_2$ of Φ such that $A \leq \Xi(\sigma)$.*

1827
 1828 *Algorithmic completeness.* With these intermediate results in hand, we can state the com-
 1829 pleteness of the algorithmic type system with respect to the declarative type system.

1830 To relate unannotated terms that are typable in the declarative system to annotated terms
 1831 required for the algorithmic type system, we introduce type-directed annotation rules. The
 1832 main interesting rule is the rule for guard expressions, which makes use of the mailbox type
 1833 to annotate the guard. The remaining rules (detailed in the extended version) are defined
 1834 recursively.
 1835
 1836

$$\frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash V : ?E^\bullet \quad \{E\} \Gamma_2 \vdash \vec{G} : A \xrightarrow{\text{ann}} \vec{G} \quad \vDash E}{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash \mathbf{guard} V \{\vec{G}\} : A \xrightarrow{\text{ann}} \mathbf{guard} V : E \{\vec{G}\}}$$

Finally, we can state our algorithmic completeness result.

Theorem 4 (Algorithmic Completeness). *If $\vdash \mathcal{P}$ where $\Gamma \vdash_{\mathcal{P}} M : A \xrightarrow{\text{ann}} \widehat{M}$, then there exist some Θ, Φ and usable solution Ξ of Φ such that $\widehat{M} \leftarrow_{\mathcal{P}} A \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi$ where $\Gamma \leq \Xi(\Theta)$.*

The proof in the extended version is again by mutual induction using a generalised statement showing completeness for values, guards, and guard sequences.

Although the completeness result is aided by the explicit annotations on let-bindings, an unannotated **let** binding $\mathbf{let} x = \widehat{M} \mathbf{in} \widehat{N}$ is also typable by the algorithmic type system if either x occurs free in \widehat{N} , or the type of \widehat{M} is synthesisable. In practice this encompasses both base types and linear usages of mailbox types, covering the vast majority of use cases.

4.3 Constraint Solving

Constraint solving is covered in depth by [Padovani \(2018c\)](#), and is not a contribution of this work. However, as an informal overview, we can break down constraint solving into the following phases:

Identify and group bounds A *pattern bound* is of the form $\gamma <: \alpha$ i.e. a constraint whose right-hand-side is a pattern variable. We firstly group all pattern bounds using pattern disjunction, e.g. a constraint set $\{\gamma <: \alpha, \delta <: \alpha\}$ would result in the constraint $\gamma \oplus \delta <: \alpha$.

Calculate closed-form solutions [Hopkins and Kozen \(1999\)](#) define a closed-form solution for a set of pattern bounds $(\gamma_i <: \alpha_i)_{i \in 1..n}$: there exists a solution δ_i for each γ_i such that $\alpha_i \notin \text{pv}(\delta_i)$. We can then substitute each closed pattern through the system to eliminate all pattern variables in the remaining constraints and obtain a system of closed inclusion constraints.

Translate to Presburger formulae and check satisfiability Finally, we translate the closed constraints into Presburger formulae. Commutative regular expressions, and therefore patterns, can be expressed as semilinear sets ([Parikh 1966](#)) that describe Presburger formulae ([Ginsburg and Spanier 1966](#)). Since checking the satisfiability of a Presburger formula is decidable, an external solver like Z3 ([de Moura and Bjørner 2008](#)) can be used to determine whether each constraint holds. In our case, we use Z3's quantifier elimination pass and its quantifier-free linear integer arithmetic solver.

5 Extensions

In this section we show how we can extend the base of Pat to include additional language features, and describe how this impacts typechecking.

It is straightforward to extend Pat with product and sum types, and building on these allows us to introduce list types, which are a stepping stone towards extending Pat with general recursive data types in the future.

We then show how to extend Pat with first-class functions, and *interfaces* that describe the set of messages a mailbox is allowed to receive, which in turn increase the precision

1888 **Additional Syntax**

1889 Types $A, B ::= \dots \mid A \times B$
 1890 Values $V, W ::= \dots \mid (V, W)$
 1891 Computations $M, N ::= \dots \mid \mathbf{let} (x, y): (A_1 \times A_2) = V \mathbf{in} M$

1892 **Additional Declarative Typing Rules**

$$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash V : A} \quad \boxed{\Gamma \vdash M : A}$$

1893 T-PAIR

1894 $\Gamma_1 \vdash V : A$ $\Gamma_2 \vdash W : B$
 1895 returnable(A) returnable(B)
 1896 -----
 1897 $\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash (V, W) : A \times B$

T-LETPAIR

1894 $\Gamma_1 \vdash V : A_1 \times A_2$ $\Gamma_2, x : A_1, y : A_2 \vdash M : B$
 1895 -----
 1896 $\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash \mathbf{let} (x, y): (A_1 \times A_2) = V \mathbf{in} M : B$

1898 **Additional Algorithmic Typing Rules**

$$\boxed{M \Rightarrow_{\rho} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi} \quad \boxed{M \Leftarrow_{\rho} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}$$

1899 TC-PAIR

1900 $V \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta_1; \Phi_1$
 1901 $W \Leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta_2; \Phi_2$ returnable(τ) returnable(σ) $\Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_3$
 1902 -----
 1903 $(V, W) \Leftarrow \tau \times \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2 \cup \Phi_3$

1904 TC-LETPAIR

1905 $V \Leftarrow A \times B \triangleright \Theta_1; \Phi_1$
 1906 $M \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta_2; \Phi_2$ check(Θ_2, x, A) = Φ_3 check(Θ_2, y, B) = Φ_4 $\Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_5$
 1907 -----
 1908 $\mathbf{let} (x, y): (A \times B) = V \mathbf{in} M \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_5$

1909 TC-LETPAIRNoANN

1910 $M \Leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta_1, x : \tau_1, y : \tau_2; \Phi_1$ $V \Leftarrow \tau_1 \times \tau_2 \triangleright \Theta_2; \Phi_2$ $\Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_3$
 1911 -----
 1912 $\mathbf{let} (x, y) = V \mathbf{in} M \Leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2 \cup \Phi_3$

1913 Fig. 12. Extension of Pat with product types

1914
 1915
 1916 of typechecking and allow finer-grained alias control. The latter two extensions require
 1917 contextual typing information prior to constraint generation.
 1918

1919 **5.1 Data Types**1920 **5.1.1 Product Types**

1921
 1922 An advantage of adding product types is that we can avoid nested **guard** clauses, by allowing a
 1923 **guard** expression to return a pair of a received value and an updated mailbox name. Consider
 1924 the following two expressions: the term on the left receives two integers and returns their sum
 1925 using nested **guard** expressions, whereas the term on the right avoids nesting by returning a
 1926 pair of the returned result and the updated mailbox.
 1927

1928
 1929
 1930 **guard** $mb : \mathbf{Arg} \odot \mathbf{Arg} \{$
 1931 **receive** $\mathbf{Arg}(x)$ **from** $mb' \mapsto$
 1932 **guard** $mb' : \mathbf{Arg} \{$
 1933 **receive** $\mathbf{Arg}(y)$ **from** $mb'' \mapsto$
 1934 **free** $mb'';$
 1935 $x+y$
 1936 **}**
 1937 **}**

1928
 1929
 1930 **let** $(x, mb') =$
 1931 **guard** $mb : \mathbf{Arg} \odot \mathbf{Arg} \{$
 1932 **receive** $\mathbf{Arg}(x)$ **from** $mb' \mapsto$
 1933 (x, mb')
 1934 **}** **in**
 1935 **guard** $mb' : \mathbf{Arg} \{$
 1936 **receive** $\mathbf{Arg}(y)$ **from** $mb'' \mapsto$
 1937 **free** $mb''; x+y$
 1938 **}**

Additional Syntax

Types $A, B ::= \dots \mid A + B$
 Values $V, W ::= \dots \mid \mathbf{inl} V \mid \mathbf{inr} V$
 Computations $M, N ::= \dots \mid \mathbf{case} V \mathbf{of} \{\mathbf{inl} x : A_1 \mapsto M; \mathbf{inr} y : A_2 \mapsto N\}$

Additional Declarative Typing Rules

	$\Gamma \vdash V : A$		$\Gamma \vdash M : A$
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash V : A \quad \text{returnable}(A) \quad \text{returnable}(B)}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{inl} V : A + B}$	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash V : B \quad \text{returnable}(A) \quad \text{returnable}(B)}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{inr} V : A + B}$	$\frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash V : A_1 + A_2 \quad \Gamma_2, x : A_1 \vdash M : B \quad \Gamma_2, y : A_2 \vdash N : B}{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash \mathbf{case} V \mathbf{of} \{\mathbf{inl} x : A_1 \mapsto M; \mathbf{inr} y : A_2 \mapsto N\} : B}$	

Additional Algorithmic Typing Rules

	$M \Rightarrow_{\rho} \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi$		$M \Leftarrow_{\rho} \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi$
$\frac{\text{TC-INL} \quad V \Leftarrow \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi \quad \text{returnable}(\tau) \quad \text{returnable}(\sigma)}{\mathbf{inl} V \Leftarrow \tau + \sigma \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi}$	$\frac{\text{TC-INR} \quad V \Leftarrow \sigma \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi \quad \text{returnable}(\tau) \quad \text{returnable}(\sigma)}{\mathbf{inr} V \Leftarrow \tau + \sigma \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi}$	$\frac{\text{TC-CASE} \quad V \Leftarrow A_1 + A_2 \blacktriangleright \Theta_1; \Phi_1 \quad M \Leftarrow \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta_2; \Phi_2 \quad N \Leftarrow \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta_3; \Phi_3 \quad \text{check}(\Theta_2, x, A_1) = \Phi_4 \quad \text{check}(\Theta_3, y, A_2) = \Phi_5 \quad (\Theta_2 - x) \sqcap (\Theta_3 - y) \blacktriangleright \Theta_4; \Phi_6 \quad \Theta_1 + \Theta_4 \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi_7}{\mathbf{case} V \mathbf{of} \{\mathbf{inl} x : A_1 \mapsto M; \mathbf{inr} y : A_2 \mapsto N\} \Leftarrow \tau \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_7}$	
$\frac{\text{TC-CASENoANN} \quad N \Leftarrow \sigma \blacktriangleright \Theta_2, y : \tau_2; \Phi_2 \quad V \Leftarrow \tau_1 + \tau_2 \blacktriangleright \Theta_3; \Phi_3 \quad \Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2 \blacktriangleright \Theta_4; \Phi_4 \quad \Theta_3 + \Theta_4 \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi_5}{\mathbf{case} V \mathbf{of} \{\mathbf{inl} x \mapsto M; \mathbf{inr} y \mapsto N\} \Leftarrow \sigma \blacktriangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_5}$			

Fig. 13. Extension of Pat with sum types

This pattern can avoid deeply-nested guard blocks when a process wants to make several receives in a row. Additionally, recall from §3 that **receive** clauses use a conservative check to rule out communication-based aliasing, where either all payloads of a message must be base types, or all variables free in the body of the **receive** clause must be base types. Returning received values along with the continuation of the mailbox is a useful tool to increase expressiveness in the presence of this restriction.

Formalism. Figure 12 shows how to extend Pat with product types. The rules for constructing and deconstructing pairs (T-PAIR and T-LETPAIR) are standard aside from the condition that the types of both values used to construct the pair are returnable. If we were to lift this restriction then we would be able to violate the quasilinearity conditions, for example by using pair construction and deconstruction to subvert the condition that only the last lexical occurrence of a variable can be returnable. We prefer T-LETPAIR to individual projection functions due to the possibility that one of the pair components may be linear, though we can use the usual syntactic sugar (e.g., $\mathbf{fst} V \triangleq \mathbf{let} (x, y) = V \mathbf{in} x$ for fresh x, y). Since product types can only consist of returnable types, they cannot be used to replace n -ary argument sequences in function definitions and **receive** clauses in full generality.

As for the algorithmic rules, pair construction (TC-PAIR) checks that both components have the given types, and that both given types are returnable. Environment combination and constraints are handled as usual. Deconstructing the pair in general requires an annotation (TC-LETPAIR); as with the let rule, we check that the pair has the given annotation and that the types inferred in the environment of the continuation are consistent with the annotation. If both components are used within the continuation then we can omit the annotation (TC-LETPAIRNOANN): the rule first checks that the continuation has the given type, and inspects the resulting environment to construct the product type used for checking V .

5.1.2 Sum Types

It is also useful to include sum types in order to express multiple ways of constructing data. The main principles are the same as supporting product types.

Formalism. Figure 13 shows how to extend Pat with sum types, which largely follows the development for product types. Again, the declarative rules are unremarkable except for the requirement that sum components must be returnable in the introduction rules. As for the algorithmic rules, sum injections are checking cases; similar to the product rules we must ensure that the constituent types are both returnable. We also have two separate rules for case expressions that allow annotations to be elided if both x and y are used within continuations M and N respectively.

5.1.3 List Types

We can apply a similar approach to extend Pat to support inductively-defined lists.

Lists are useful as they allow us to encode patterns such as broadcasting a message to a number of clients. For example, the following code (adapted from the k -fork benchmark described in §6.2) broadcasts a request to a list of actor references:

```
def broadcast(actorMbs : List(!Request)): 1 {
  caseL (actorMbs : List(!Request)) of {
    nil ↦ ()
    mb :: mbs ↦ mb !Request (); broadcast(mbs)
  }
}
```

Formalism. Figure 14 shows how to extend Pat with list types, which follows the development for product and sum types presented above. As one might expect, constructing a list is similar to constructing a product after injecting into a sum, while pattern matching on a list is similar to case matching on a sum followed by deconstructing a product.

The declarative rules are unremarkable aside from the type of values in the list needing to be returnable in the introduction rules. Since sums and lists are currently the only types in Pat that can be pattern matched against, we use different syntax for each: **case** and **caseL** to avoid overloading. A future extension introducing general recursive types would aim to unify these and allow for general pattern matching against the constructors of any data type, but this extension is outside of the scope of the current work.

In the algorithmic rules, list construction with TC-CONS also requires that the type of list elements is returnable, and environment combination and constraints are handled as in the

2041 **Additional Syntax**

2042 Types $A, B ::= \dots \mid \text{List}(A)$
 2043 Values $V, W ::= \dots \mid \text{nil} \mid V :: W$
 2044 Computations $M, N ::= \dots \mid \text{caseL } (x : \text{List}(A)) \text{ of } \{\text{nil} \mapsto M; y :: ys \mapsto N\}$

2045 **Additional Declarative Typing Rules**

$$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash V : A} \quad \boxed{\Gamma \vdash M : A}$$

2046 T-NIL T-CONS
 2047 $\text{returnable}(A)$ $\Gamma_1 \vdash V : A \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash W : \text{List}(A)$
 2048 $\frac{}{\cdot \vdash \text{nil} : \text{List}(A)}$ $\frac{}{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash V :: W : \text{List}(A)}$
 2049
 2050 T-CASEL
 2051 $\frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash V : \text{List}(A) \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash M : B \quad \Gamma_2, y : A, ys : \text{List}(A) \vdash N : B}{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{caseL } (V : \text{List}(A)) \text{ of } \{\text{nil} \mapsto M; y :: ys \mapsto N\} : B}$
 2052
 2053

2054 **Additional Algorithmic Typing Rules**

$$\boxed{M \Rightarrow_{\rho} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi} \quad \boxed{M \Leftarrow_{\rho} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi}$$

2055 TC-NIL TC-CONS
 2056 $\frac{\text{returnable}(\tau)}{\text{nil} \Leftarrow \text{List}(\tau) \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset}$ $\frac{V \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta_1; \Phi_1 \quad W \Leftarrow \text{List}(\tau) \triangleright \Theta_2; \Phi_2 \quad \Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_3}{V :: W \Leftarrow \text{List}(\tau) \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2 \cup \Phi_3}$
 2057
 2058 TC-CASEL
 2059 $\frac{V \Leftarrow \text{List}(A) \triangleright \Theta_1; \Phi_1 \quad M \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta_2; \Phi_2 \quad N \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta_3; \Phi_3 \quad \text{check}(\Theta_3, y, A) = \Phi_4 \quad \text{check}(\Theta_3, ys, \text{List}(A)) = \Phi_5 \quad \Theta_2 \sqcap ((\Theta_3 - y) - ys) \triangleright \Theta_4; \Phi_6 \quad \Theta_1 + \Theta_4 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_7}{\text{caseL } (V : \text{List}(A)) \text{ of } \{\text{nil} \mapsto M; y :: ys \mapsto N\} \Leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_7}$
 2060
 2061
 2062 TC-CASELNOANN
 2063 $\frac{M \Leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta_1; \Phi_1 \quad N \Leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta_2, y : \tau, ys : \text{List}(\tau); \Phi_2 \quad V \Leftarrow \text{List}(\tau) \triangleright \Theta_3; \Phi_3 \quad \Theta_1 \sqcap \Theta_2 \triangleright \Theta_4; \Phi_4 \quad \Theta_3 + \Theta_4 \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_5}{\text{caseL } V \text{ of } \{\text{nil} \mapsto M; y :: ys \mapsto N\} \Leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_5}$
 2064
 2065
 2066
 2067
 2068
 2069
 2070
 2071
 2072
 2073

Fig. 14. Extension of Pat with list types

2074 analogous product rule. Case expressions, like sums, have two separate rules allowing the
 2075 annotation to be elided if both y and ys are used in the continuation N .

2077 **5.2 Towards More Liberal Data Types**

2078 We have required that the data contained within each of the described data types must be
 2079 returnable. This ensures that we cannot deconstruct a data type containing a second-class
 2080 name and unpackage it later, thus breaking the lexical scoping requirements of quasi-linearity.
 2081 However, this approach can be restrictive.

2082 A potential solution is to allow the construction of data types that may contain names with
 2083 second-class types, but only to allow them to be deconstructed in a situation where unsafe
 2084 aliasing cannot occur: namely where the continuation M of a **let** $(x, y) = V$ **in** M construct or
 2085 the relevant continuations of a **case** construct do not close over any mailbox types (or, as we
 2086 will see in §5.4, do not close over any mailbox types that might lead to aliasing). We can
 2087 formalise the declarative rules for product types as follows; the corresponding rules for sums
 2088 and lists are similar.
 2089
 2090
 2091

$$\frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash V : A \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash W : B}{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash (V, W) : A \times B} \quad \frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash V : A_1 \times A_2 \quad \Gamma_2, x : A_1, y : A_2 \vdash M : B}{(\text{returnable}(A_1) \wedge \text{returnable}(A_2)) \vee \text{base}(\Gamma_2)}{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash \mathbf{let} (x, y) = V \mathbf{in} M : B}$$

This approach has the advantage that it rules out problematic cases that introduce unsafe aliasing, where we have two static names for the same underlying runtime name, for example:

```

let mb = new in
let pair = (mb, 1) in
let (a, b) = pair in
x ! m(a);
guard mb {
  receive m(y) from mb ↦ free mb
}

```

This code snippet packages *mb* (with type $!1^\circ$) into a pair, then uses pair deconstruction to alias the first component of the pair to *a*, and would be ruled out as mailbox names *x* and *mb* are free in the continuation of the pair deconstruction construct.

However, the approach is not sound according to our declarative rules due to quasi-linearity, and does not rule out self-deadlocks. For example, the following code would be well-typed even though it introduces a self-deadlock:

```

let mb = new in
let pair = (mb, 1) in
guard mb {
  receive m() from mb ↦ free mb
};
let (x, y) = pair in
x ! m()

```

We have optionally implemented this approach in our typechecker, but we expect finer-grained alias analysis techniques to be an important area of future work. None of the examples presented in our evaluation rely on this more liberal treatment of datatypes.

5.3 First-class Functions

We can extend Pat with first-class functions, but this requires care with quasi-linearity and requires additional typing information during typechecking. We will discuss quasi-linearity now but defer discussion of typechecking to §5.5.

Quasi-linearity. Consider the following expression (where the \square annotation on the function abstraction denotes a *linear* function abstraction that must be applied precisely once):

```

let mb = new in
let f = ( $\lambda^\square$ (): 1 . mb ! m()) in
guard mb : m {
  receive m() from mb ↦ free mb
};
f()

```

2143 **Additional Syntax**

2144	Linearity annotations	$\diamond ::= \square \mid \blacksquare$
2145	Modified types	$A, B ::= \dots \mid \vec{A} \overset{\diamond}{\rightarrow} B$
2146	Modified values	$V, W ::= \dots \mid \lambda^\diamond(x : \vec{A}) : B . M$
2147	Modified computations	$M, N ::= \dots \mid V(\vec{W})$

2148 **Additional Declarative Typing Rules** $\Gamma \vdash M : A$

2150	$\frac{\text{T-LINLAMBDA}}{\Gamma, x : \vec{A} \vdash M : B \quad \text{returnable}(\Gamma)}$	$\frac{\text{T-UNLAMBDA}}{\Gamma, x : \vec{A} \vdash M : B \quad \text{returnable}(\Gamma) \quad \text{un}(\Gamma)}$
2151	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \lambda^\square(x : \vec{A}) : B . M : \vec{A} \overset{\square}{\rightarrow} B}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda^\square(x : \vec{A}) : B . M : \vec{A} \overset{\square}{\rightarrow} B}$	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \lambda^\blacksquare(x : \vec{A}) : B . M : \vec{A} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} B}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda^\blacksquare(x : \vec{A}) : B . M : \vec{A} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} B}$
2152		
2153		
2154	$\frac{\text{T-APPLAMBDA}}{\Gamma \vdash V : \vec{A} \overset{\diamond}{\rightarrow} B \quad (\Gamma_i \vdash W_i : A_i)_{i \in 1..n}}$	
2155		$\Gamma + \Gamma_1 + \dots + \Gamma_n \vdash V(\vec{W}) : B$
2156		
2157		

2158 **Reduction Rule** $M \longrightarrow_M N$

$$2159 \quad \llbracket (\lambda^\diamond(x : \vec{A}) : B . M)(\vec{V}), \Sigma \rrbracket \longrightarrow \llbracket M\{\vec{V}/\vec{x}\}, \Sigma \rrbracket$$

2160 **Additional Auxiliary Definitions**

$$2161 \quad \text{un}(\vec{A} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} B) \quad \text{returnable}(\vec{A} \overset{\diamond}{\rightarrow} B) \quad (\vec{A} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} B) \triangleright (\vec{A} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} B) = \vec{A} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} B$$

$$2162 \quad \frac{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 = \Gamma}{(\Gamma_1, x : \vec{A} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} B) + (\Gamma_2, x : \vec{A} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} B) = \Gamma, x : \vec{A} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} B}$$

2168 Fig. 15. Additional Syntax, Typing Rules, and Reduction Rules for First-Class Functions

2169
2170
2171 Here we bind f to a function that sends message \mathbf{m} to mailbox mb ; note that it is used
2172 lexically before the **guard**, which aligns with type combination. However, after reducing the
2173 expression (assuming that a is chosen as a runtime name), we obtain the following term:

$$2174 \quad \mathbf{guard} \ a : \mathbf{m} \{$$

$$2175 \quad \quad \mathbf{receive} \ \mathbf{m}() \ \mathbf{from} \ mb \mapsto \mathbf{free} \ mb$$

$$2176 \quad \quad \};$$

$$2177 \quad \quad (\lambda^\square(): \mathbf{1} . mb ! \mathbf{m}())()$$

2178
2179 After substituting the function body for f we now have a second-class use *after* the
2180 first-class use, violating the ordering of returnable and second-class usages.

2181
2182 *Formalism.* Figure 15 shows the additional syntax, declarative typing rules, and reduction rule
2183 for extending Pat with first-class functions. We defer discussion of algorithmic typing rules
2184 to §5.5. We extend values with fully-annotated, n -ary anonymous functions $\lambda^\diamond(x : \vec{A}) : B . M$,
2185 where \diamond is a linearity annotation that specifies whether a function is linear or unrestricted. We
2186 include n -ary functions rather than using currying because anonymous functions may only
2187 close over returnable values, to ensure they do not violate the quasilinearity conditions on
2188 lexical scoping once applied, and therefore unary functions would be less expressive. We
2189 also extend computations with n -ary function application $V(\vec{W})$.

2190
2191 Rule T-LINLAMBDA types a linear function, *i.e.* a function that must be applied precisely
2192 once. A linear function may, for example, close over returnable mailbox output capabilities.

2193

2194 The rule is similar to the regular function abstraction rule, but binds multiple parameters
 2195 and requires that the function body closes over only variables with returnable types. Rule
 2196 T-UNLAMBDA types an unrestricted function and is similar, but requires that the function
 2197 closes over only variables with unrestricted types.

2198 The reduction rule for function application is the standard β -reduction rule adapted for
 2199 frame stacks. We extend the $\text{un}(-)$ predicate to account for unrestricted functions. Since
 2200 functions always close over returnable environments, function types are returnable, and the
 2201 sequential combination of two unrestricted function types does not affect the argument or
 2202 result types.
 2203

2204 *Metatheory.* The addition of first-class functions does not violate the metatheoretical proper-
 2205 ties of the system: preservation and self-deadlock-freedom are maintained because we restrict
 2206 λ -abstractions to close over only returnable variables and thus applying a function cannot
 2207 break the invariants on combining usage annotations.
 2208
 2209

2210 5.4 Mailbox Interfaces

2211 In the core Pat language, a global signature maps message tags to payload types. While
 2212 technically convenient, this can be inflexible. First, distinct entities may wish to use the same
 2213 mailbox tags with different payload types. For example, a client may send a **Login** message
 2214 containing credentials to a server, which may then send a **Login** message containing the
 2215 credentials and a timestamp to a session management server. Second, we need a syntactic
 2216 check on a **receive** guard to avoid aliasing introduced by communication, as outlined in §2:
 2217 either the received payloads or free variables in the guard body must be base types. Consider
 2218 the following expression:
 2219
 2220

```

2221     def waitAndSend(mb): 1 {
2222       guard mb : M1  $\odot$  M2 {
2223         receive M1(x) from mb'  $\mapsto$ 
2224         guard mb' : M2 {
2225           receive M2(y) from mb''  $\mapsto$ 
2226             x ! Go();
2227             y ! Go();
2228           free mb''
2229         }
2230       }
2231     }
2232 
```

2233 The `waitAndSend` definition waits for messages **M1** and **M2** from mailbox `mb`. The messages
 2234 carry mailbox names `x` and `y` respectively. After receiving both messages, the function sends
 2235 a **Go** message to both `x` and `y` before freeing `mb`. This safe code is *not* typable in the calculus
 2236 without interfaces, because the mailbox variable `x` occurs free in the second **receive** guard.
 2237

2238 To address this issue we can associate each mailbox with an *interface* `I` that maps tags to
 2239 payload types, and allows us to syntactically distinguish different kinds of mailbox (*e.g.* a
 2240 future and its client).

2241 Since a name cannot have two interfaces at once, we can loosen our syntactic check on
 2242 **receive** guards to require only that the *interfaces* of mailbox names in the payloads and free
 2243 variables differ, as typing guarantees that they will refer to different mailboxes. We could
 2244

2245 **Modified Syntax**

2246	Interface names	I
2247	Interfaces	$\iota ::= \overrightarrow{\mathbf{m}} : \overrightarrow{T}$
2248	Interface mapping	$\mathcal{I} ::= \overrightarrow{I \mapsto \iota}$
2249	Modified programs	$\mathcal{P} ::= (I, \overrightarrow{D}, M)$
2250	Modified mailbox types	$J, K ::= !^I E \mid ?^I F$
2251	Modified computations	$M, N ::= \dots \mid \mathbf{new}[I]$

2253 **Modified Typing Rules for Computations** $\Gamma \vdash M : A$

2254	TI-NEW	TI-GUARD
2255	$\frac{}{\cdot \vdash \mathbf{new}[I] : ?^I \mathbb{1}^\bullet}$	$\frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash V : ?^I E^\bullet \quad \{I; E\} \Gamma_2 \vdash \overrightarrow{G} : A \quad \vDash E}{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \vdash \mathbf{guard} V \{ \overrightarrow{G} \} : A}$

2258 **Typing rules for guards**

2259		$\boxed{\{I; E\} \Gamma \vdash_{\varphi} \overrightarrow{G} : A}$	$\boxed{\{I; E\} \Gamma \vdash_{\varphi} G : A}$
2260	TGI-GUARDSEQ	TGI-FAIL	TGI-FREE
2261	$\frac{(\{I; E_i\} \Gamma \vdash G_i : A)_{i \in 1..n}}{\{I; E_1 \oplus \dots \oplus E_n\} \Gamma \vdash \overrightarrow{G} : A}$	$\frac{}{\{I; \emptyset\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fail} : A}$	$\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash M : A}$
2262	$\{I; E_1 \oplus \dots \oplus E_n\} \Gamma \vdash \overrightarrow{G} : A$	$\{I; \emptyset\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fail} : A$	$\{I; \mathbb{1}\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{free} \mapsto M : A$
2263			
2264	TGI-RECV		
2265	$\frac{I(\mathbf{m}) = \overrightarrow{T} \quad \text{interfaces}(\overrightarrow{T}) \cap \text{interfaces}(\Gamma) = \emptyset \quad \Gamma, y : ?^I E^\bullet, \overrightarrow{x} : \overrightarrow{ T } \vdash M : B}{\{I; \mathbf{m} \odot E\} \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{receive} \mathbf{m}(\overrightarrow{x}) \mathbf{from} y \mapsto M : B}$		

2268 Fig. 16. Extension of Pat to support mailbox interfaces

2269 therefore type the waitAndSend example above, as long as we statically know x and y have
 2270 different interfaces, and therefore must be different mailboxes.

2271 *Formalism.* Figure 16 shows the extensions to Pat to support mailbox interfaces. We modify
 2272 the definition of programs $(\mathcal{S}, \overrightarrow{D}, M)$ (where \mathcal{S} is a mapping from message tags to sequences
 2273 of payload types) to $(I, \overrightarrow{D}, M)$, where I is a mapping from *interface names* I to interfaces ι .
 2274 Like signatures in the unextended core calculus, interfaces ι map message tags to sequences
 2275 of payload types. Given some program $\mathcal{P} = (I, \overrightarrow{D}, M)$ and interface name I , we write $I(\mathbf{m})$
 2276 as syntactic sugar for $I(I(\mathbf{m}))$.

2277 We extend mailbox types $!^I E$ and $?^I E$ to include their interface name. The main alteration
 2278 to the term syntax is to require an annotation on the **new** construct to specify the interface of
 2279 the newly-created mailbox.

2280 We update the judgement form for guards to include the interface name of the current
 2281 mailbox. Rule TI-NEW includes the specified interface in the mailbox type, and rule TI-GUARD
 2282 uses the mailbox type's interface name when typing the guards. Instead of using the program
 2283 signature to determine message types, rule TGI-RECV looks up the message tag in the given
 2284 interface, and also includes a more liberal check that only requires that the sets of interfaces
 2285 of mailbox types contained in the payload type and the interfaces of any mailbox types used
 2286 in typing M are disjoint.

2287 We also require that combination of two mailbox types, and mailbox subtyping, is only
 2288 defined if the two types have the same interface.

2295

5.5 Using Contextual Type Information: Typechecking First-Class Functions and Mailbox Interfaces

Section 4 showed how Pat’s typechecker uses a *co-contextual* approach in order to generate the pattern inclusion constraints required for algorithmic typechecking. While this suffices for Pat without extensions and Pat with the data type extensions, typechecking first-class functions and mailbox interfaces requires *contextual* type information *before* the constraint generation pass.

5.5.1 Issues with typechecking first-class functions and mailbox interfaces

Typechecking first-class functions. Consider typechecking the application of a first-class function:

$$(\lambda(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int} . x)(5)$$

The annotated λ expression allows us to synthesise a type and use a rule similar to TS-APP. Unfortunately, the lack of contextual type information means that the approach fails as soon as we stray from applying function literals, for example:

$$\text{let } f = (\lambda(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int} . x) \text{ in } f(5)$$

This is because we *do not* have information about the type of f when attempting to type $f(5)$. A typical backwards bidirectional typing approach requires *synthesising* function argument types, but this is too inflexible in our setting as each mailbox name argument would need a type annotation.

Typechecking mailbox interfaces. The complexity with typing mailbox interfaces comes with recording the interface associated with each mailbox name. In Pat without extensions, the required type information can be gained from context (*i.e.* through the message tag) and globally-available (*i.e.* through the program’s message signature S).

For example, when typing a message $\text{send } a ! \mathbf{m}(5)$, the base Pat type system would look up message tag \mathbf{m} in the program’s signature and see that the message had payload type Int , before checking that 5 had the corresponding type Int and a had type $! \mathbf{m}$. However, in a system with interfaces, we need knowledge of a ’s interface in order to look up the payload types. The checking judgement also requires knowledge of a ’s interface in addition to the expected pattern.

Typechecking strategy. We implement the above extensions via a contextual type-directed elaboration pass. We can annotate variables with an annotation that is useful when typing function applications. As for interfaces, users specify an interface when creating a mailbox ($\text{new}[I]$); our pass then annotates sends and guards with interface information (*i.e.* $V !^I \mathbf{m}(\vec{W})$ and $\text{guard}^I V : E \{\vec{G}\}$) for use in constraint generation.

5.5.2 Extended syntax

Figure 17 shows the additional syntax required to add first-class functions and interfaces.

Types and pre-types. Pre-types R, S are similar to types τ but type mailbox variables differently. Unlike the types we have seen so far, pre-types can be inferred and checked algorithmically using an entirely standard *contextual* approach. The key difference between pre-types and types is that mailbox names have type $\text{Mailbox}(I)$ and therefore do not contain either a capability or a pattern. The main benefit of using pre-types is that they allow us to propagate

2347 **Modified Syntax**

2348	Interface names	I
2349	Interfaces	$\iota ::= \overrightarrow{\mathbf{m}} : \overrightarrow{\pi}$
2350	Modified programs	$\mathcal{P} ::= (I, \overrightarrow{D}, \widehat{M})$
2351	Modified mailbox types	$J, K ::= !^I \gamma \mid ?^I \delta$
2352	Modified types	$\pi, \rho ::= C \mid J \mid \overrightarrow{\tau} \overset{\circ}{\rightarrow} \sigma$
2353	Modified usage-annotated types	$\tau, \sigma ::= C \mid J^n \mid \overrightarrow{\tau} \overset{\circ}{\rightarrow} \sigma$
2354	Pre-types	$R, S ::= C \mid \text{Mailbox}(I) \mid \overrightarrow{\tau} \overset{\circ}{\rightarrow} \sigma$
2355	Modified annotated values	$\widehat{V}, \widehat{W} ::= \dots \mid x^R \mid \lambda^\circ(\overrightarrow{x} : \overrightarrow{\tau}) : \sigma . \widehat{M}$
2356	Modified annotated computations	$\widehat{M}, \widehat{N} ::= \dots \mid \widehat{V}(\overrightarrow{W}) \mid \mathbf{new}[I] \mid \mathbf{guard}^I \widehat{V} : E \{ \overrightarrow{G} \}$
2357		$\mid \widehat{V} !^I \mathbf{m}(\overrightarrow{W})$
2358		
2359		

2360 **Promotion from Pre-Types to Types**

$$\boxed{\uparrow(R) = \pi}$$

$$\uparrow(C) = C \quad \uparrow(\overrightarrow{\tau} \overset{\circ}{\rightarrow} \sigma) = \overrightarrow{\tau} \overset{\circ}{\rightarrow} \sigma \quad \uparrow(\text{Mailbox}(I)) \text{ undefined}$$

2363 **Demotion from Types to Pre-Types**

$$\boxed{\downarrow(\pi) = R}$$

$$\downarrow(C) = C \quad \downarrow(\overrightarrow{\tau} \overset{\circ}{\rightarrow} \sigma) = \overrightarrow{\tau} \overset{\circ}{\rightarrow} \sigma \quad \downarrow(!^I \gamma) = \text{Mailbox}(I) \quad \downarrow(?^I \gamma) = \text{Mailbox}(I)$$

2366 Fig. 17. Extension of Pat to support typechecking of first-class functions and interfaces (1)

2367 mailbox interface information, and to annotate (non-mailbox-typed) variables with type
 2368 information that can be used in constraint generation (e.g., when typing functions). Pre-types
 2369 that are not mailbox types can be *promoted* to a full type using the promotion operator $\uparrow(R)$,
 2370 and all types can be *demoted* into a pre-type using the demotion operator $\downarrow(\pi)$.

2371 We modify types to include *interface-annotated* mailbox types, as well as n -ary function
 2372 types $\overrightarrow{\tau} \overset{\circ}{\rightarrow} \sigma$.

2373 *Values and computations.* Since first-class functions can refer to computations, we add an
 2374 additional syntactic class \widehat{V} of annotated values (thus allowing first-class functions to contain
 2375 function bodies that have annotated **guard** expressions used for typechecking). We also
 2376 extend variables x with a pre-type annotation.

2377 *Mailbox terms.* We extend computations so that a user specifies an interface I when creating
 2378 a mailbox (**new**[I]). Furthermore, we also augment send and guard expressions with the
 2379 interface of the mailbox they operate on.

2380 Only the annotation on **new** must be specified by a user: annotations on variables, send
 2381 expressions, and guard expressions (shaded) are instead added by type-directed elaboration.

2382 **5.5.3 Type-directed elaboration**

2383 We propagate pre-type annotations via a contextual type-directed elaboration phase (Figure 18).

2384 Pre-type environments Ω map variables to pre-types. We use the judgements $\Omega \vdash_{\widehat{\mathcal{P}}} \widehat{M} \Rightarrow R \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \widehat{M}'$
 2385 (read “under pre-type environment Ω and in the context of program $\widehat{\mathcal{P}}$, synthesise pre-type
 2386 R for computation \widehat{M} , and produce elaborated term \widehat{M}'), and $\Omega \vdash_{\widehat{\mathcal{P}}} \widehat{M} \Leftarrow R \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \widehat{M}'$ (read
 2387 “under pre-type environment Ω and in the context of program $\widehat{\mathcal{P}}$, check that computation \widehat{M}
 2388 has pre-type R , and produce elaborated term \widehat{M}'). We use analogous judgements for values
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$ \begin{array}{c} \text{ELAB-VAR} \\ \hline x : R \in \Omega \\ \hline \Omega \vdash x \Rightarrow R \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} x^R \end{array} $	$ \begin{array}{c} \text{ELAB-NEW} \\ \hline \Omega \vdash \mathbf{new}[I] \Rightarrow \text{Mailbox}(I) \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \mathbf{new}[I] \end{array} $
$ \begin{array}{c} \text{ELAB-SEND} \\ \hline \Omega \vdash \widehat{V} \Rightarrow \text{Mailbox}(I) \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \widehat{V}' \quad I(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{\pi} \\ (\Omega \vdash \widehat{W}_i \Leftarrow \downarrow (\pi_i) \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \widehat{W}'_i)_{i \in I} \\ \hline \Omega \vdash \widehat{V} ! \mathbf{m}(\vec{W}) \Rightarrow \mathbf{1} \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \widehat{V}' ! \mathbf{m}(\vec{W}') \end{array} $	$ \begin{array}{c} \text{ELAB-GUARD} \\ \hline \Omega \vdash \widehat{V} \Rightarrow \text{Mailbox}(I) \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \widehat{V}' \\ (\{I\} \Omega \vdash \widehat{G}_i \Rightarrow R \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \widehat{G}'_i)_{i \in I} \\ \hline \Omega \vdash \mathbf{guard} \widehat{V} : E \{\vec{G}\} \Rightarrow R \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \mathbf{guard}' \widehat{V}' : E \{\vec{G}'\} \end{array} $

Fig. 18. Type-directed Elaboration (Selected Rules)

and guards. The rules for each judgement follow the usual bidirectional typing rules for the simply-typed λ -calculus, so we concentrate on the pertinent elaboration rules.

Rule **ELAB-VAR** annotates a variable with its pre-type, and rule **ELAB-NEW** synthesises type $\text{Mailbox}(I)$, where I corresponds to the user-specified interface. Rule **ELAB-SEND** states that if type $\text{Mailbox}(I)$ can be synthesised for the target mailbox, then the rule looks up the payload types for the message in interface I and checks all payloads against the (demoted) payload types. The result is a send expression annotated with the interface I . Finally, rule **ELAB-GUARD** synthesises type $\text{Mailbox}(I)$ for the given mailbox, and then checks that each guard synthesises the same type. The interface is passed to the guard synthesis judgement so that the payload types can be retrieved when typing a **receive** guard. Again, the result is the guard annotated with interface I .

5.5.4 Constraint generation rules

Figure 19 shows the constraint generation rules for the extended calculus. We require three new rules for first-class functions: rule **TS-LINLAM** types a linear anonymous function by checking that the body has the given result type, and the inferred environment uses variables consistently with the parameter annotations: the rule synthesises a type consistent with the annotation. Further, we require that the inferred environment only closes over variables with returnable types. Rule **TS-UNLAM** is similar, but additionally requires that the inferred environment is unrestricted. Rule **TS-FNAPP** synthesises a type for the function (made possible using either the type annotation on the function abstraction, or the annotation on the function variable); it then checks that the arguments and results have the correct types.

As for the rules that support interfaces, rule **TS-SEND** is similar but looks up the types according to the interface rather than the global signature, and checks that the target mailbox has the given interface. Rule **TS-NEW** synthesises a mailbox type with the user-supplied interface. Finally, we modify the shape of the guard typing judgement to record the interface of the mailbox being guarded upon, and use this to look up the desired payload types in **TCG-RECV**.

Example. To illustrate this approach, consider our earlier troublesome example:

$$\mathbf{let} \ f = (\lambda^\blacksquare(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int} . x) \ \mathbf{in} \ f(5)$$

This example cannot be typed purely co-contextually since we do not have the required type information for f when typing the function application.

Modified constraint generation rules

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\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\boxed{\widehat{M} \Rightarrow_{\widehat{\rho}} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi} \quad \boxed{\widehat{M} \leftarrow_{\widehat{\rho}} \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi} \quad \boxed{\{E; I\} \widehat{G} \leftarrow_{\widehat{\rho}} \tau \triangleright \Psi; \Phi; F} \\
\text{TS-UNLAM} \\
\text{TS-LINLAM} \\
\frac{\widehat{M} \leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta'; \Phi_1 \quad \Theta'' = \lfloor \Theta' \rfloor \quad \Theta'' = \lfloor \Theta' \rfloor \quad \text{check}(\vec{x}, \vec{\tau}, \Theta'') = \Phi_2}{\Theta = \Theta'' - \vec{x} \quad \text{check}(\vec{x}, \vec{\tau}, \Theta'') = \Phi_2} \quad \frac{\widehat{M} \leftarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta'; \Phi_1}{\Theta = \Theta'' - \vec{x} \quad \text{unr}(\Theta) \triangleright \Phi_3} \\
\frac{\lambda^{\blacksquare}(\vec{x} : \vec{\tau}) : \sigma. \widehat{M} \Rightarrow \vec{\tau} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2}{\lambda^{\blacksquare}(\vec{x} : \vec{\tau}) : \sigma. \widehat{M} \Rightarrow \vec{\tau} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2 \cup \Phi_3} \\
\text{TS-VAR} \\
\frac{\uparrow(R) = \tau}{x^R \Rightarrow \tau \triangleright x : \tau; \emptyset} \quad \text{TS-FNAPP} \\
\frac{\widehat{V} \Rightarrow \vec{\tau} \overset{\circ}{\rightarrow} \sigma \triangleright \Theta_V; \Phi_V}{(\widehat{W}_i \leftarrow \tau_i \triangleright \Theta_i; \Phi_i)_{i \in 1..n} \quad \Theta_V + \Theta_1 + \dots + \Theta_n \triangleright \Theta; \Phi} \\
\frac{}{\widehat{V}(\vec{W}) \Rightarrow \sigma \triangleright \Theta; \Phi \cup \Phi_V \cup \Phi_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi_n} \\
\text{TS-SEND} \\
\frac{I(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{\pi} \quad \widehat{V} \leftarrow !^I \mathbf{m}^\circ \triangleright \Theta_V; \Phi_V}{(\widehat{W}_i \leftarrow [\pi_i] \triangleright \Theta_i; \Phi'_i)_{i \in 1..n} \quad \Theta_V + \Theta_1 + \dots + \Theta_n \triangleright \Theta; \Phi} \quad \text{TS-NEW} \\
\frac{}{\widehat{V} !^I \mathbf{m}(\vec{W}) \Rightarrow \mathbf{1} \triangleright \Theta; \Phi \cup \Phi_V \cup \Phi'_1 \cup \dots \cup \Phi'_n} \quad \frac{}{\text{new}[I] \Rightarrow ?^I \mathbf{1}^\bullet \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset} \\
\text{TC-GUARD} \\
\frac{\{E; I\} \widehat{G} \leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Psi; \Phi_1; F \quad \widehat{V} \leftarrow ?^I F^\bullet \triangleright \Theta'; \Phi_2 \quad \Psi + \Theta' \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_3}{\text{guard}^I \widehat{V} : E \{ \widehat{G} \} \leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2 \cup \Phi_3 \cup \{E <: F\}} \\
\text{TCG-RECV} \\
\frac{\widehat{M} \leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta', y : ?^I \gamma^\bullet; \Phi_1 \quad I(\mathbf{m}) = \vec{\pi} \quad \Theta = \Theta' - \vec{x} \quad \text{interf}(\vec{\pi}) \cap \text{interf}(\Theta) = \emptyset \quad \text{check}(\Theta', \vec{x}, [\vec{\pi}]) = \Phi_2}{\{E; I\} \text{ receive } \mathbf{m}(\vec{x}) \text{ from } y \mapsto \widehat{M} \leftarrow \tau \triangleright \Theta; \Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2 \cup \{E / \mathbf{m} <: \gamma\}; \mathbf{m} \odot (E / \mathbf{m})}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 19. Extension of Pat to support typechecking of first-class functions and interfaces (2)

Let $\Omega = f : \text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int}$. The type-directed elaboration phase results in the following derivation:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{x : \text{Int} \vdash x \Rightarrow \text{Int} \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} x^{\text{Int}}} \\
\frac{}{x : \text{Int} \vdash x \leftarrow \text{Int} \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} x^{\text{Int}}} \\
\frac{}{\cdot \vdash \lambda^{\blacksquare}(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int}. x \Rightarrow \text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int} \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \lambda^{\blacksquare}(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int}. x^{\text{Int}}} \\
\frac{}{\cdot \vdash f \Rightarrow \text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int} \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} f^{\text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int}}} \quad \frac{}{\cdot \vdash f \leftarrow \text{Int} \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} f^{\text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int}}} \\
\frac{}{\cdot \vdash \lambda^{\blacksquare}(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int}. x \text{ in } f(5) \Rightarrow \text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int} \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \lambda^{\blacksquare}(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int}. x^{\text{Int}} \text{ in } f^{\text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int}}(5)} \quad \frac{}{\cdot \vdash f(5) \Rightarrow \text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int} \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} f^{\text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int}}(5)} \\
\frac{}{\cdot \vdash \text{let } f = (\lambda^{\blacksquare}(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int}. x) \text{ in } f(5) \Rightarrow \text{Int} \overset{\text{elab}}{\rightsquigarrow} \text{let } f = (\lambda^{\blacksquare}(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int}. x^{\text{Int}}) \text{ in } f^{\text{Int} \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} \text{Int}}(5)}
\end{array}$$

Finally, we can type the expression with the modified constraint generation rules. We omit the straightforward environment operations in the premises of the rules for simplicity. Let \mathbf{D} be the following subderivation:

Fig. 20. Pat type checking pipeline

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{}{f^{\text{Int} \rightarrow \text{Int}} \Rightarrow \text{Int} \multimap \text{Int} \triangleright f : \text{Int} \multimap \text{Int}; \emptyset} \quad \frac{5 \Rightarrow \text{Int} \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset}{5 \Leftarrow \text{Int} \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset} \\
 \hline
 f^{\text{Int} \rightarrow \text{Int}}(5) \Rightarrow \text{Int} \triangleright f : \text{Int} \multimap \text{Int}; \emptyset \\
 \hline
 f^{\text{Int} \rightarrow \text{Int}}(5) \Leftarrow \text{Int} \triangleright f : \text{Int} \multimap \text{Int}; \emptyset
 \end{array}$$

Then, we can construct the whole derivation using T-LETNOANN1:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{}{x^{\text{Int}} \Leftarrow \text{Int} \triangleright x : \text{Int}; \emptyset} \\
 \frac{\lambda^{\text{Int}}(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int} . x^{\text{Int}} \Rightarrow \text{Int} \multimap \text{Int} \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset}{\mathbf{D} \quad \lambda^{\text{Int}}(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int} . x^{\text{Int}} \Leftarrow \text{Int} \multimap \text{Int} \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset} \\
 \hline
 \mathbf{let} f = \lambda^{\text{Int}}(x : \text{Int}) : \text{Int} . x^{\text{Int}} \mathbf{in} f^{\text{Int} \rightarrow \text{Int}}(5) \Leftarrow \text{Int} \triangleright \cdot; \emptyset
 \end{array}$$

6 Implementation and Expressiveness

We outline the implementation of a mailbox type checker written in OCaml, and evidence the expressiveness of Pat via a selection of representative example programs taken from the literature. We first show that using quasi-linear typing in place of dependency graphs (cf. §2.3) does not prevent Pat from expressing *all* of the examples in (de’Liguoro and Padovani 2018). The Savina benchmarks (Imam and Sarkar 2014) capture typical concurrent communication patterns and are used both to compare actor languages and to demonstrate expressiveness; we show that Pat (once extended with sums, products, and lists) can express all of the 11 Savina expressiveness benchmarks used by Neykova and Yoshida (2017b). This selection captures typical concurrency and communication patterns to confirm that our language can express real-world scenarios that arise in concurrent and distributed computing. We base our choice of Savina programs on the selection implemented by (Neykova and Yoshida 2017b) in order to demonstrate that mailbox types are at least as expressive as multiparty session types for actor systems, at least within the context of this set of examples.

Finally, we describe the *Sleeping Barber* example in detail, and show a case study provided by an industrial partner that develops control software for factories.

6.1 Implementation Overview

Pat programs consist of *interface definitions* that detail the messages and payload types supported by a mailbox; a series of *function definitions*; and finally a *program body* that serves as an entrypoint. Programs are type checked in the six-stage pipeline outlined in Fig. 20 and are described as follows:

Lexical analysis Performs standard lexing and parsing using the OCaml Menhir library.

Tbl. 1. Typechecking concurrent actor examples in Pat

#	Name	Description	Strict	SLOC	Time (ms)
<i>Original mailbox calculus models taken from de'Liguoro and Padovani (2018)</i>					
1	Lock	Concurrent lock modelling mutual exclusion	•	35	29.4
2	Future	Future variable that is written to once and read multiple times	•	32	25.0
3	Account	Concurrent accounts exchanging debit and credit instructions	•	38	20.0
4	AccountF	Concurrent accounts where debit instructions are effected via futures	•	65	37.1
5	Master-Worker	Master-worker parallel network	•	70	29.8
6	Session Types	Session-typed communicating actors using one arbiter	◦	96	85.3
<i>Selected micro-benchmarks adapted from Imam and Sarkar (2014), based on Neykova and Yoshida (2017b)</i>					
7	Ping Pong	Process pair exchanging k ping and pong messages	•	47	26.9
8	Thread Ring	Ring network where actors cyclically relay one token with counter k	◦	76	40.6
9	Counter	One actor sending messages to a second that sums the count, k	◦	56	30.0
10	K-Fork	Fork-join pattern where a central actor delegates k requests to workers	•	41	8.0
11	Fibonacci	Fibonacci server delegating terms $(k - 1)$ and $(k - 2)$ to parallel actors	•	43	27.1
12	Big	Peer-to-peer network where actors exchange k messages randomly	◦	108	64.8
13	Philosopher	Dining philosophers problem	◦	90	73.8
14	Smokers	Centralised network where one arbiter allocates k messages to actors	◦	82	40.7
15	Log Map	Computes the term $x_{k+1} = r \cdot x_k (1 - x_k)$ by delegating to parallel actors	◦	103	63.2
16	Transaction	Request-reply actor communication initiated by a central teller actor	◦	96	51.2
17	Barber	Multiple customers who awaken and interact with one 'sleeping' barber	◦	100	77.5

Desugaring Desugars the sugared form of guards (i.e., transforming **free** V to **guard** $V : \mathbb{1} \{ \text{free} \mapsto () \}$ and **fail** V to **guard** $V : \mathbb{0} \{ \text{fail} \}$), and adds omitted pattern variables.

IR conversion Transforms the surface language (supporting nested expressions) to our explicitly-sequenced intermediate representation.

Contextual type-checking Performs a (standard) bidirectional typing pass to propagate contextual type information (§5.5).

Constraint generation Implements the algorithmic type system from Section 4, and generates a set of pattern inclusion constraints.

Constraint solving Applies the constraint solving approach detailed in Section 4.3, and invokes Z3 (de Moura and Bjørner 2008) to determine whether the generated constraints are satisfiable.

The Pat typechecker operates in two *modes* that determine how receive guards are type checked. *Strict* mode uses the lightweight syntactic checks outlined in §3 and §4, whereas *interface* mode uses interface type information (§5.5) to relax these checks. This means that every Pat program accepted in strict mode is also accepted in interface mode.

6.2 Expressiveness and Typechecking Time

Tbl. 1 lists the examples implemented in Pat. Examples 1-6 are the mailbox calculus examples from (de'Liguoro and Padovani 2018, Ex. 1–3, and Sec. 4.1–4.3). Examples 7-17 are the suite of Savina benchmarks (Imam and Sarkar 2014, Table 1, No. 1–4, 6, 7, 12–16) used in (Neykova and Yoshida 2017b). The table indicates whether a Pat program can be checked in strict (denoted by •), *in addition* to interface mode (denoted by ◦). We report the mean typechecking time, excluding phases 1–3 of the pipeline. Measurements are made on a

MacBook M1 Pro with 8GB of memory, running macOS 15.4 and OCaml 5.2. To minimise variability we report the mean time from 1000 repetitions. The number of repetitions was determined empirically by calculating the coefficient of variation (CV) (Devore and Berk 2012), *i.e.* the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean, $CV = \sigma/\bar{x}$, for different repetitions until an adequately-low value ($< 10\%$) was obtained.

6.2.1 Benchmarks

Tbl. 1 shows that all but one of the mailbox calculus examples from (de'Liguoro and Padovani 2018) can be checked in strict mode. The Savina examples capture typical concurrent programming patterns, namely, master-worker (K-Fork, Fibonacci, Log Map), client-server (Ping Pong, Counter), and peer-to-peer (Big), and common network topologies such as star (Philosopher, Smokers, Transaction) and ring (Thread Ring). Most of these programs require contextual type information (8, 9, and 12–16) to type check.

The new list extension (§5.1.3) allows us to implement some examples more idiomatically, and one example for the first time. Lists make it possible to express examples that use fixed collections, *i.e.* examples 8, 10, and 12–16 idiomatically, *i.e.* as lists. The original implementations in (Fowler et al. 2023b) emulated the collections using parameters. The examples reveal the benefits of mailbox typing. Runtime checks, such as manual error handling (§1.2) are unnecessary since errors (*e.g.* unexpected messages) are *statically* ruled out by the type system. Mailbox types also have an edge over session typing tools for actor systems, *e.g.* (Neykova and Yoshida 2017b; Tabone and Francalanza 2022) where developers typically specify protocols in external tools and write code to accommodate the session typing framework. In contrast, mailbox typing *naturally* fits idiomatic actor programming.

This flexibility does not incur high typechecking runtimes (see Tbl. 1). The aim of benchmarking typechecking time is to show that mailbox typechecking is not prohibitively expensive, rather than to claim comparative results. Comparisons with other implementations of (non-mailbox-typed versions of) the benchmarks written in other languages are unlikely to strengthen our results as the benchmark source code would be different, and we would be measuring *e.g.* Java's entire type system implementation rather than the essence of the typechecking algorithm.

Nevertheless, for this set of benchmarks we can see that typechecking times universally remain under 100ms. The benchmark that takes the longest to typecheck is the *Session Types* benchmark, which has 12 different messages that can be exchanged along with 12 different guard expressions. The benchmark that has the smallest typechecking time is *K-Fork* which has only one type of message and a single guard expression, and therefore a much simpler communication structure. This would suggest that, as would be expected, constraint solving is likely to take the most time during typechecking.

6.2.2 Extended Savina Example: Sleeping Barber

This section describes the development of the *Sleeping Barber* benchmark in Pat in greater detail. The Sleeping Barber problem is a classic synchronisation problem, originally specified by Dijkstra (2002):

- A barber is working in a barber shop with a waiting room.
- When the barber is ready for the next customer, they check the waiting room.

- 2653 – If the waiting room has waiting customers, then the barber calls the next customer
- 2654 in for their haircut. Once the barber is finished cutting the customer’s hair, they
- 2655 check the waiting room again.
- 2656 – If the waiting room is empty, then the barber will sleep.
- 2657 • When a customer enters the barber shop, they check to see if the waiting room has
- 2658 space. If there is space, then the customer will wait; if there is no space, then the
- 2659 customer will leave. If the barber is asleep, then the customer will need to wake the
- 2660 barber.
- 2661

2662 The Savina benchmarks implement an (untyped) actor-based version of the problem by
 2663 modelling the barber, customers, and waiting room as individual actors. We take a similar
 2664 approach in Pat, and begin by defining interfaces for the three types of mailbox.
 2665

2666 *Interfaces.* The `WaitingRoom` will receive three types of message:

```
2667 1 interface WaitingRoom { Enter(Customer!), Next(Barber!), Sleeping(Barber!) }
2668
```

2669 The `Enter` message is received from a customer when they enter the barber shop, and
 2670 contains an output reference to the customer’s mailbox. The `Next` message is received from the
 2671 barber to signify that they are ready to service the next customer, and the `Sleeping` message
 2672 is received from the barber to signify that the barber has gone to sleep. Both of the latter
 2673 messages contain an updated output reference to the barber’s mailbox.
 2674

2675 The Barber will also receive three types of message:

```
2676 1 interface Barber { Wake(WaitingRoom!), CustomerReady(Customer!, WaitingRoom!),
2677 2     RoomEmpty(WaitingRoom!) }
```

2678 The `Wake` message is received from an empty waiting room when a customer has entered and
 2679 the barber is asleep. The `CustomerReady` and `RoomEmpty` messages are received from the waiting
 2680 room in response to a `Next` message sent by the barber; the former notifies the barber of the
 2681 next customer, and the latter notifies the barber that the room is empty and that they can go to
 2682 sleep. The `CustomerReady` message includes a reference that the barber can use to communicate
 2683 with the customer, and both messages include an updated `WaitingRoom` reference.
 2684

2685 Finally, the Customer can receive four types of message:

```
2686 1 interface Customer { Full(), Wait(), Start(), Done() }
2687
```

2688 After entering the waiting room, the customer will either receive a `Full` or `Wait` message
 2689 from the waiting room to state that the customer should leave or wait in the waiting room
 2690 respectively. When the barber is ready to cut the customer’s hair, the barber will send the
 2691 customer a `Start` message, and when the barber is finished with the haircut, the barber will
 2692 send a `Done` message.
 2693

2694 *Customer.* The implementation of the customer is fairly straightforward. A customer must
 2695 send an `Enter` message to the waiting room, and then wait for a response:

```
2696 1 def customer(self: Customer?, waitingRoom: WaitingRoom!): Unit {
2697 2     waitingRoom ! Enter(self);
2698 3     guard self : Full + (Wait.Start.Done) {
2699 4         receive Full() from self ->
2700 5             print("Room is full. Oh well, best go somewhere else");
2701 6             free(self)
2702 7         receive Wait() from self ->
2703
```

```

2704 8         print("Waiting");
2705 9         waitingCustomer(self)
2706 10     }
2707 11 }

```

2708 There are two possible responses from the waiting room: either a `Full` message to say that
 2709 the waiting room is full (at which point there are no possible interactions and the only thing
 2710 to do is to free the mailbox), or a `Wait` message. If the latter, the mailbox types *also* guarantee
 2711 that the customer will need to handle a `Start` message (when the barber begins their haircut),
 2712 and a `Done` message (when the barber has finished their haircut).

2714 The `waitingCustomer` function processes the `Start` and `Done` messages and frees the cus-
 2715 tomer's mailbox after the haircut is finished:

```

2716 1 def waitingCustomer(self: Customer?): Unit {
2717 2     guard self : Start.Done {
2718 3         receive Start() from self ->
2719 4             print("Barber is starting my haircut");
2720 5         guard self : Done {
2721 6             receive Done() from self ->
2722 7                 print("Haircut finished!");
2723 8                 free(self)
2724 9         }
2725 10     }
2726 11 }

```

2729 *Waiting Room.* To obtain precise mailbox types, we model the waiting room as two mutually-
 2730 recursive functions: one for when the barber is asleep, and one for when there are waiting
 2731 customers.

```

2732 1 def waitingRoomSleepingBarber(self: WaitingRoom?, barber: Barber!,
2733 2     capacity: Int): Unit {
2734 3     guard self : Enter* {
2735 4         free -> ()
2736 5         receive Enter(customer) from self ->
2737 6             let buffer = new[WaitingRoomBuffer] in
2738 7                 buffer ! WaitingCustomer(customer);
2739 8                 customer ! Wait();
2740 9                 barber ! Wake(self);
2741 10                waitingRoom(self, buffer, 1, capacity)
2742 11     }
2743 12 }

```

2744 The `waitingRoomSleepingBarber` function takes an input mailbox reference to its own mailbox,
 2745 an output mailbox reference to the barber, and an integer denoting the capacity of the waiting
 2746 room. In this state, the barber is asleep and cannot send any more messages until they are
 2747 awake, and so the waiting room can only receive `Enter` messages (or free itself if no more
 2748 `Enter` messages can be sent). When the waiting room receives an `Enter` message, it creates
 2749 a new mailbox buffer that is used to model the queue of customers waiting for the barber;
 2750 stores the request in the queue by sending the buffer a `WaitingCustomer` message containing
 2751 an output reference to the customer's mailbox; sends the customer a `wait` message; sends the
 2752 barber a `wake` message to wake them up; and then transitions to the non-empty state.

2754

2755 In the non-empty state, the waiting room's mailbox can also receive many Enter messages
2756 from customers, but also must eventually receive a Next message from the barber:

```
2757 1 def waitingRoom(self: WaitingRoom?, buffer WaitingRoomBuffer?,
2758 2     numCustomers: Int, capacity: Int): Unit {
2759 3     guard self : Enter* . Next {
2760 4         receive Enter(customer) from self -> ...
2761 5         receive Next(barber) from self -> ...
2762 6     }
2763 7 }
```

2764 Processing an Enter message is similar to before: if the number of customers exceeds
2765 the capacity of the waiting room, then the waiting room will respond with a Full message;
2766 otherwise, the waiting room will queue the request and send the customer a Wait message:
2767

```
2768 1 receive Enter(customer) from self ->
2769 2     if (numCustomers >= capacity) {
2770 3         customer ! Full();
2771 4         waitingRoom(self, buffer, numCustomers, capacity)
2772 5     } else {
2773 6         buffer ! WaitingCustomer(customer);
2774 7         customer ! Wait();
2775 8         waitingRoom(self, buffer, numCustomers + 1, capacity)
2776 9     }
```

2777 To process a Next message, the waiting room will inspect the buffer, which may contain
2778 zero or more WaitingCustomer messages:

```
2779 1 receive Next(barber) from self ->
2780 2     guard buffer : WaitingCustomer* {
2781 3         receive WaitingCustomer(customer) from buffer ->
2782 4             barber ! CustomerReady(customer, self);
2783 5             waitingRoom(self, buffer, numCustomers - 1, capacity)
2784 6         free ->
2785 7             # In this case there are no more customers.
2786 8             # Notify the barber that he can sleep; move to sleeping state
2787 9             barber ! RoomEmpty(self);
2788 10            guard self : Enter* . Sleeping {
2789 11                # Receive notification that barber is asleep
2790 12                receive Sleeping(barber) from self ->
2791 13                    waitingRoomSleepingBarber(self, barber, capacity)
2792 14            }
2793 15 }
```

2794 When processing a WaitingCustomer message, the waiting room responds to the barber with
2795 a CustomerReady message containing the output reference with which to communicate with the
2796 customer, and recursively invokes the waitingRoom function with a decremented customer count.
2797 If the free guard is triggered, we know that there are no pending WaitingCustomer messages
2798 and therefore that the waiting room is empty. So the function notifies the barber that the room
2799 is empty, awaits a Sleeping notification, and transitions to the waitingRoomSleepingBarber
2800 state.

2801
2802 *REMARK.* We use a mailbox, rather than a list, for storing the contents of the waiting room
2803 to avoid the potential for unsafe aliasing. Consider a signature of the waitingRoom function
2804 that maintains the waiting room as a list:
2805

```

2806 1 def waitingRoom(self: WaitingRoom?, buffer: List(Customer!),
2807 2     numCustomers: Int, capacity: Int): Unit

```

2808 *Here we would also need to modify the **receive** clause for the Enter message to add the*
 2809 *customer to the waiting room:*

```

2810
2811 1 receive Enter(customer) from self ->
2812 2   if (numCustomers >= capacity) {
2813 3     customer ! Full();
2814 4     waitingRoom(self, buffer, numCustomers, capacity)
2815 5   } else {
2816 6     buffer ! WaitingCustomer(customer);
2817 7     customer ! Wait();
2818 8     waitingRoom(self, customer :: buffer, numCustomers + 1, capacity)
2819 9   }

```

2820 *However there is no guarantee that a reference for the customer does not already exist in*
 2821 *the buffer, and therefore deconstructing the list could introduce unsafe aliasing. Moreover we*
 2822 *can only safely store returnable values in a buffer, whereas the customer reference must be*
 2823 *treated as second-class. Both issues are avoided by using a mailbox to model the waiting*
 2824 *room as Pat's type system allows us to safely reason about one customer at a time.*

2825 *It is also possible (if slightly less elegant) to model the Sleeping Barber problem without a*
 2826 *separate buffer mailbox by using self-messages.*

2827
 2828 *Barber.* Finally, the barber process begins in the sleepingBarber state, where they have only
 2829 a reference to a Barber mailbox. The self mailbox has pattern Wake + 1 indicating that the
 2830 barber is able to respond to a wake message (when a customer enters the waiting room), or be
 2831 able to free itself if no customers are ever spawned. When the barber receives a wake message,
 2832 the process sends a Next message to the waiting room provided in the message. Once awoken,
 2833 the barber calls the barber function that models an awake barber.

```

2834
2835 1 def sleepingBarber(self: Barber?): Unit {
2836 2   guard self : Wake + 1 {
2837 3     free -> ()
2838 4     receive Wake(room) from self ->
2839 5       room ! Next(self);
2840 6       barber(self)
2841 7   }
2842 8 }

```

2843 The barber process again takes a reference to the barber's mailbox. However this time we
 2844 know that the waiting room must respond with either a RoomEmpty message if there are no
 2845 waiting customers, at which point the barber can go back to sleep, or a CustomerReady message
 2846 if another customer was waiting.

```

2847
2848 1 def barber(self: Barber?): Unit {
2849 2   guard self : RoomEmpty + CustomerReady {
2850 3     receive RoomEmpty(room) from self ->
2851 4       print("Room empty; going to sleep");
2852 5       room ! Sleeping(self);
2853 6       sleepingBarber(self)
2854 7     receive CustomerReady(customer, room) from self ->
2855 8       customer ! Start();
2856 9       print("Cutting hair");

```

```

2857 10     print("Finished cutting hair; notifying customer and waiting room");
2858 11     customer ! Done();
2859 12     room ! Next(self);
2860 13     barber(self)
2861 14 }
2862 15 }

```

2863 If the room is empty, the barber will send a `RoomEmpty` message to the waiting room before
 2864 calling the `sleepingBarber` function, which models the barber falling asleep. When the barber
 2865 receives a `CustomerReady` message, which contains a reference to the customer and the room,
 2866 the barber will send a `Start` message to the customer at the start of their haircut and a `Done`
 2867 message at the end of their haircut, before notifying the waiting room by sending a `Next`
 2868 message.
 2869

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2874 *Discussion.* Perhaps surprisingly, many of the messages exchanged between participants
 2875 contain references to the sender, even though a reference may already be in scope. For
 2876 example, a mailbox with the `Barber` interface can receive `Wake`, `CustomerReady`, and `RoomEmpty`
 2877 messages from the `WaitingRoom`, and all contain a `WaitingRoom` reference with which to respond.

2878 As there is only one waiting room it is common practice in some actor languages, like
 2879 Erlang, to spawn the barber process with a reference to it, simplifying the `Barber` interface:
 2880

```

2881 1 interface Barber { Wake(WaitingRoom!),
2882 2     CustomerReady(Customer!, WaitingRoom!), RoomEmpty(WaitingRoom!) }
2883 3 def barber(self: Barber?, room: WaitingRoom!): Unit { ... }
2884 4 def sleepingBarber(self: Barber?, room: WaitingRoom!): Unit { ... }

```

2885 The drawback of this approach is a loss of typing precision. With the previous approach we
 2886 know statically that the barber will *only have a reference to the waiting room when processing*
 2887 *a request from the room* and this allows us to specify two precise mailbox types for the
 2888 two states of the waiting room. Specifically, when the barber is awake, the `self` mailbox in
 2889 the `waitingRoom` function has type `WaitingRoom?(Enter* . Next)`, meaning that it mailbox can
 2890 contain many `Enter` messages from customers, but also will eventually contain a *single* `Next`
 2891 message from the barber when they are ready for the next customer. When the barber is
 2892 asleep, the barber will *not* have a reference to the waiting room, and thus we know statically
 2893 that the waiting room *cannot* contain a `Next` message; we can therefore give the `self` mailbox
 2894 the type `WaitingRoom?Enter*` in the `waitingRoomSleepingBarber` function.
 2895

2896 If we were instead to keep the `room` variable in scope across both functions, we would need
 2897 to use the less precise mailbox type `WaitingRoom?(Enter*.Next*)` in both states of the waiting
 2898 room, since there are no guarantees of the state of the barber, nor the fact that the barber
 2899 might not use the reference to send multiple messages.
 2900

2901 The idiom of sending a mailbox reference even when it could be in scope may seem
 2902 contrary to common practice in untyped languages like Erlang. It does, however, closely
 2903 mirror the style employed by Akka's typed references (Akka Team 2026), where messages
 2904 often include an actor reference that allows a process to respond with a message of a different
 2905 type. We posit that the practice of re-sending actor references with a different type is therefore
 2906 more of a typed actor idiom rather than being specific to mailbox typing.
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Fig. 21. Factory use case

6.2.3 Factory Case Study

Finally we describe a real-world use case provided by *Actyx AG*², who develop control software for factories. The use case captures a scenario where multiple robots on a factory floor acquire parts from a warehouse that provides access through a single door. Robots negotiate with the door to gain entry into the warehouse and obtain the part they require. The behaviour of our three entities, *Robot*, *Door*, and *Warehouse* is shown in Fig. 21. Our concrete syntax closely follows the core calculus of §3, without requiring that pattern variables in mailbox types are specified explicitly. Type checking our case study relies on contextual type information (see §5), and takes ≈ 89.6 ms.

Interfaces. The messages accepted by the *Robot*, *Door*, and *Warehouse* are defined by the following interfaces.

```

1 interface Robot {
2   GoIn(Door!), GoOut(Door!), Busy(), Delivered(Warehouse!, Door!)
3 }
4
5 interface Door {
6   Want(Int, Robot!), Inside(Robot!), Outside(),
7   WantLeave(Robot!), Prepared(Warehouse!),
  
```

²<https://www.actyx.com>

```

2959 8  TableIdle()
2960 9  }
2961 10
2962 11 interface Warehouse {
2963 12   Prepare(Int, Door!), Deliver(Robot!, Door!), PartTaken()
2964 13 }

```

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```

2978 14 def idle(self: Robot?, door: Door!): Unit {
2979 15   door ! Want((), self);
2980 16   guard self: (Busy + GoIn) {
2981 17     receive Busy() from self →
2982 18     free(self)
2983 19     receive GoIn(door) from self →
2984 20     door ! Inside(self);
2985 21     working(self)
2986 22   }
2987 23 }

```

2988

2989

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2993

2994

2995

```

2996 36 def clear(self: Door?, wh: Warehouse!): Unit {
2997 37   guard self: Want* {
2998 38     free → ()
2999 39     receive Want(part, robot) from self →
3000 40     robot ! GoIn(self);
3001 41     wh ! Prepare(part, self);
3002 42     busy(self)
3003 43   }
3004 44 }

```

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Robot. Each Robot is initially idle and issues a `Want` message to the Door to obtain access to the Warehouse (line 15). The Door replies either with the message `Busy`, in which case the Robot terminates (lines 17–18), or `GoIn`, to which the Robot replies by an `Inside` message before transitioning to the working state (lines 19–21). When in working state, the Robot expects one `Delivered` message to inform the Robot that the part is delivered by the Warehouse, as asserted by the guard on line 25. The recipient Robot replies by replying to the Warehouse with the `PartTaken` message, and notifies the Door that it wants to exit by sending a `WantLeave` message on lines 28–29. It then awaits a `GoOut` message and finalises its negotiation with the Door through an `Outside` message.

```

24 def working(self: Robot?): Unit {
25   let self = guard self: Delivered {
26     receive Delivered(wh, door)
27     from self →
28     wh ! PartTaken();
29     door ! WantLeave(self); self
30   } in guard self: GoOut {
31     receive GoOut(door) from self →
32     door ! Outside();
33     free(self)
34   }
35 }

```

Door. The Door accepts zero or more `Want` messages, replying to each with `Busy` or `GoIn`. In the latter case, the Door informs the Warehouse of an inbound Robot by sending it a `Prepare` message, and transitioning to the busy state (lines 39–42). Both `GoIn` and `Prepare` include an updated self-reference to ensure precise types. The `free` guard on line 38 handles the case where no Robots are present, i.e., no `Want` messages are received by the Door.

When busy, the Door mailbox potentially contains an `Inside` message from the admitted Robot, a `Prepared` message from the Warehouse, and `Want` messages sent by other Robots requesting access (line 46). These `Want` messages are answered with `Busy`, as lines 47–49 show. Once the Door receives the `Inside` message, it awaits a `Prepared` message issued by the

3010 Warehouse, before notifying the latter that the Robot is collecting its part via Deliver (lines
3011 50–53).

```

3012 45 def busy(self: Door?): Unit {
3013 46   guard self: Inside.Prepared.Want* {
3014 47     receive Want(partNum, robot) from self →
3015 48     robot ! Busy();
3016 49     busy(self)
3017 50   receive Inside(robot) from self →
3018 51     guard self: Prepared.Want* {
3019 52       receive Prepared(wh) from self →
3020 53       wh ! Deliver(robot, self);
3021 54       guard self: WantLeave.TableIdle.Want* {
3022 55         receive WantLeave(robot) from self →
3023 56         robot ! GoOut(self);
3024 57         ready(self, wh)
3025 58       }
3026 59     }
3027 60   }
3028 61 }

```

3028 Eventually, the Robot requests to exit the Warehouse by sending WantLeave to the Door, which
3029 handles it on lines 55–56. The Door transitions to the ready state, whereupon it confirms that
3030 the Robot has exited and that the Warehouse is available; these interactions are captured by the
3031 outside and TableIdle messages respectively (lines 66–75). Finally, the Door transitions back
3032 to clear on lines 69 and 74, ready to service other Robots.

```

3034 62 def ready(self: Door?, wh: Warehouse!): Unit {
3035 63   guard self: Outside.TableIdle.Want* {
3036 64     # Handle messages Outside and TableIdle in
3037 65     # any order (code omitted) and clear door.
3038 66     receive Outside() from self →
3039 67     guard self: TableIdle.Want* {
3040 68       receive TableIdle(wh) from self →
3041 69       clear(self, wh)
3042 70     }
3043 71     receive TableIdle(wh) from self →
3044 72     guard self: Outside.Want* {
3045 73       receive Outside() from self →
3046 74       clear(self, wh)
3047 75     }
3048 76   }
3049 77 }

```

3049

3050

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3052

3053 Warehouse. The Warehouse in its empty state expects a Prepare message (if there are Robots
3054 in the system), or none (if no Robot requests access), *i.e.* the guard Prepared + 1 on line 79.
3055 When a part is requested, the Warehouse transitions to the engaged state and awaits a Deliver
3056 message from the Door, notifying the Robot collecting the part via a Delivered message (lines
3057 88–95), and then transitions to the given state (lines 96–102). The Robot acknowledges the
3058 delivery by sending PartTaken, as required by the guard on line 97. To conclude its interaction
3059 with the Door, the Warehouse sends TableIdle before transitioning back to the empty state.

3060

```

3061
3062
3063
3064 78 def empty(self: wh?): Unit {
3065 79   guard self: Prepare + 1 {
3066 80     free → ()
3067 81     receive Prepare(partNum, door)
3068 82     from self →
3069 83     door ! Prepared(self);
3070 84     engaged(self)
3071 85   }
3072 86 }
3073 87
3073 88 def engaged(self: wh?): Unit {
3074 89   guard self: Deliver {
3075 90     receive Deliver(robot, door)
3076 91     from self →
3077 92     robot ! Delivered(self, door);
3078 93     given(self, door)
3079 94   }
3080 95 }

96 def given(self: wh?, door: Door!): Unit {
97   guard self : PartTaken {
98     receive PartTaken() from self →
99     door ! TableIdle(self);
100    empty(self)
101  }
102 }
103
104 # Launcher function.
105 def main(): Unit {
106   # n Robot mailboxes.
107   let roboti = new[Robot] in
108   let door = new[Door] in
109   let wh = new[Warehouse] in
110   # Door.
111   spawn { clear(door, wh) };
112   # n Robots.
113   spawn { idle(roboti, door) };
114   # Warehouse.
115   spawn { empty(wh) }
116 }

```

The `main()` function creates n Robot mailboxes, together with a Door and Warehouse mailbox, spawning the respective processes on lines 111–115.

7 Related work

Behaviourally-typed actors. The asymmetric nature of mailboxes makes developing behavioural type systems for actor languages challenging. [Mostrous and Vasconcelos \(2011\)](#) investigate session typing for Core Erlang, using selective message reception and unique references to encode session-typed channels. [Tabone and Francalanza \(2021, 2022\)](#) develop a tool that statically checks Elixir ([Jurić 2019](#)) actors against binary session types to prove session fidelity. [Neykova and Yoshida \(2017b\)](#) propose a programming model for dynamically checking actor communication against multiparty session types ([Honda et al. 2016](#)), later implemented in Erlang by [Fowler \(2016\)](#). [Neykova and Yoshida \(2017a\)](#) show how causality information in global types can support efficient recovery strategies. [Harvey et al. \(2021\)](#) use multiparty session types with explicit connection actions ([Hu and Yoshida 2017](#)) to give strong guarantees about actors that support runtime adaptation, but an actor can only participate in one session at a time. [Fowler and Hu \(2026\)](#) introduce a language design that allows session-typed actor communication by enforcing multiparty session typing using a flow-sensitive effect system, and their language allows actors to be involved in multiple sessions by using ideas from event-driven programming.

Session types are helpful when there are clear, structured communication flows between a fixed class of participants. Session types also provide a convenient top-down development methodology, whereas mailbox types need to be added to individual components in a more bottom-up fashion. However, the big disadvantage of using session types over mailbox types is that session types are specified using point-to-point interactions, and this requires either designing applications with session types from the beginning, or rewriting existing applications to use a session-typed communication style. In contrast, our mailbox typing approach naturally fits idiomatic actor programming paradigms.

3111

3112 Bagherzadeh and Rajan (2017) define a type system for active objects (de Boer et al. 2007)
3113 which can rule out data races; this work targets an imperative calculus and is not validated via
3114 an implementation. Kamburjan et al. (2016) apply session-based reasoning to a core active
3115 object calculus where types encode remote calls and future resolutions; communication
3116 correctness is ensured by static checks against session automata (Bollig et al. 2013).

3117 Mailbox types are inspired by behavioural type systems (Crafa and Padovani 2017) for
3118 the *objective join calculus* (Fournet and Gonthier 1996). The technique can be implemented
3119 in Java using code generation via *matching automata* (Gerbo and Padovani 2019), and
3120 dependency graphs can rule out deadlocks (Padovani 2018a), but the authors do not consider
3121 a programming language design. Scalas et al. (2019) define a behavioural type system for
3122 Scala actors. Types are written in a domain-specific language, and type-level model checking
3123 determines safety and liveness properties. Their system focuses on the behaviour of a process,
3124 rather than the state of the mailbox.

3125
3126 *Session-typed functional languages.* Session types (Honda 1993; Honda et al. 1998) were
3127 originally considered in the setting of process calculi; Gay and Vasconcelos (2010) were first
3128 to integrate session types in a functional language by building on the linear λ -calculus, and
3129 their approach has been adopted by several other works (e.g. (Almeida et al. 2022; Lindley
3130 and Morris 2015)). Linear types are insufficient for mailbox typing since we require *multiple*
3131 uses of a mailbox name as a sender; we believe our use of quasi-linearity for behavioural
3132 typing is novel, and we conjecture that it could be used to support other paradigms (e.g.
3133 publish-subscribe) that require non-linear variable use.

3134
3135 *Co-contextual typing.* Co-contextual typing (Erdweg et al. 2015) was originally introduced to
3136 support efficient incremental type-checking, and has also been used to support intrinsically-
3137 typed compilation (Rouvoet et al. 2021). Padovani (2014) uses a co-contextual type algorithm
3138 for the linear π -calculus with sums, products, and recursive types; and Ciccone and Padovani
3139 (2022) use it when analysing fair termination properties. *Backwards bidirectional typing* (Zeil-
3140 berger 2015) is a co-contextual formulation of bidirectional typing, and to the best of our
3141 knowledge we are first to use it in a language implementation. Co-contextual typing has
3142 parallels with the co-de Bruijn nameless variable representation (McBride 2018), where
3143 subterms are annotated with the variables they contain.

3144
3145 *Safety via static analysis.* Christakis and Sagonas (2011) implement a static analyser for
3146 Erlang that detects errors such as receiving from an empty mailbox, payload mismatches,
3147 redundant patterns, and orphan messages. All of these issues can be detected with mailbox
3148 types, which also allow us to specify the mailbox state. Harrison (2018) implements an
3149 approach incorporating both typechecking and static analysis to detect errors such as orphan
3150 messages and redundant patterns.

3151 8 Conclusion and Future Work

3152
3153
3154
3155 Concurrent and distributed applications can harbour subtle and insidious bugs, includ-
3156 ing protocol violations and deadlocks. Behavioural types ensure *correct-by-construction*
3157 communication-centric software, but are difficult to apply to actor languages. We have
3158 proposed the *first* language design incorporating *mailbox types* which characterise mailbox
3159 communication. The multiple-writer, single-reader nature of mailbox-oriented messaging
3160 makes the integration of mailbox types in programming languages highly challenging. We
3161
3162

3163 have addressed these challenges through a novel use of quasi-linear types and have formalised
3164 and implemented an algorithmic type system based on backwards bidirectional typing (§4),
3165 proving it to be sound and complete with respect to the declarative type system (§3). Our
3166 approach can flexibly express common communication patterns (*e.g.* master-worker) and a
3167 real-world case study based on factory automation.
3168

3169 *Ongoing and future work.* Mailbox typing is a young field and there are many areas that are
3170 ripe for exploration.

3171 We are currently investigating using mailbox types to verify communication behaviour in
3172 mainstream actor languages such as Erlang. In Pat an actor may have multiple mailboxes
3173 and *explicitly* creates and destroys each mailbox. In contrast mainstream actor languages
3174 *implicitly* create a single, *monolithic*, mailbox that holds messages from all protocols. Our
3175 approach overlays multiple virtual mailboxes on a monolithic mailbox, and annotates the
3176 code to indicate what messages are expected by **receives** and when a mailbox should be
3177 created or reused.
3178

3179 An important area is better inference: both at the level of mailbox patterns in order to allow
3180 developers to elide annotations on **guard** expressions, and at the level of types in order to
3181 support more interesting type system features (*e.g.*, polymorphism or set-theoretic typing).
3182 For mailbox types to be adopted in practice, it is also important to consider how mailbox
3183 types can be adapted to handle failure.
3184

3185 Another avenue for future work is finer-grained deadlock- and alias detection. Quasilinearity
3186 provides some guarantees, but since we cannot easily adopt the dependency graph formalism
3187 introduced by de'Liguoro and Padovani (2018) we cannot guarantee inter-process deadlock
3188 freedom. Approaches such as *priorities* (Kobayashi 2006; Kokke and Dardha 2023; Padovani
3189 2014) may prove a useful starting point, but it is not yet clear how to adapt these to the
3190 many-sender, single-receiver model supported by mailboxes.

3191 This paper has concentrated on the design and implementation of a *typechecker* for
3192 Pat. In future work we also plan to investigate efficient ways of faithfully implementing
3193 Pat's semantics (*e.g.*, using distributed reference counting), which is not immediately
3194 straightforward due to features like the **free** guard.
3195

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3203

3204 *Declaration of competing interests*

3206 The authors have no competing interests to declare.
3207

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